

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.7 - Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 2

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

PENDING EC APPROVAL

PENDING EC APPROVAL

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101096405	Acronym	UP2030	
Full Title	Urban Planning and design ready for 2030			
Start Date	01/01/2023	Duration	36 months	
Project Website	https://up2030-he.eu/			
Deliverable	D3.7 - Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 2			
Work Package	WP3 – UP-SKILLING - Empowering the city’s stakeholder ecosystem to co-develop urban planning and design enabled transformation pathways			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	17/12/2025	Actual	17/12/2025
Nature	PU	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	University of Cambridge			
Author(s)	<p>Buro Happold: Peter Scheibstock, Felicitas Leithner, Jill Theobald, Sara Rossi,</p> <p>TSPA: Aurelija Matuleviciute,</p> <p>GGGI: Diana Kupper, Alexandros Gkatsikos,</p> <p>UCCRN: Mattia Leone, Cristina Visconti, Giovanni Nocerino</p> <p>AQUATEC: Montse Martinez, David Suñer</p> <p>LNEC: Maria Adriana Cardoso, Rita Salgado Brito, Maria do Céu Almeida, Rita Ribeiro, Maria João Rosa, Catarina Jorge</p> <p>Deltares: Hans Gehrels, Dirk Eilander,</p> <p>LINKS Foundation: Giacomo Blanco, Erica Bruno, Giulia Melis,</p> <p>Maggioli: Kostas Kalaboukas, Michalis Bourbos,</p> <p>Mapping for Change: Louise Francis, Amanda Newton</p> <p>University of Cambridge: Will Brown, Kristen MacAskill</p> <p>Each tool provider is responsible for the content related to their own tool</p>			
Reviewer(s)	Alisa Krumm (USTUTT), Constanza Vera (USTUTT), Eloise Deshayes (UIC) & Nor Touati (UIC)			
Abstract	This deliverable presents the technical and user requirements of each tool included within UP2030’s Task 3.3, alongside a detailed case study of each tool’s use in UP2030 and a general step-by-step guide. Each tool focuses on supporting enhanced approaches to climate neutrality. Included in this document are 16 tools from 11 technical partners.			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	17/12/2025	Draft	Final version of Deliverable 3.7	Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, GGGI, LINKS Foundation, LNEC, Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN and the University of Cambridge
0.2		Draft review	Review of table of content and executive summary	USTUTT
0.3		Draft	First version of the deliverable	Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, GGGI, LINKS Foundation, LNEC, Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN and the University of Cambridge
0.4		Draft review	Review of first draft	UIC
0.5		Draft	Second version of the deliverable	Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, GGGI, LINKS Foundation, LNEC, Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN and the University of Cambridge
0.6		Draft review	Coordination review	USTUTT
1.0		Final	Final version ready for submission	Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, GGGI, LINKS Foundation, LNEC, Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN and the University of Cambridge

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EUROPEAN UNION or the EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The content, format, citations, and sources presented in this report are the sole responsibility of the author. While efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the content presented, there may be gaps in the information provided, or the information may become outdated over time. Readers are encouraged to independently verify any information presented in this report to ensure its accuracy and relevance to their specific needs or circumstances.

Copyright message

© UP2030 Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Contents

1.1	Executive summary	13
1.2	Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	14
	Acronyms.....	15
2	Introduction.....	18
2.1	Background.....	18
2.2	Purpose and scope.....	18
2.3	Step-by-Step Guide Key	20
2.4	Document structure	21
3	Aquatec.....	22
3.1	Resilience Strategies Database and Tool	22
3.1.1	Software Requirements	22
3.1.2	Data Requirements	23
3.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	23
3.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use.....	23
3.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	24
3.1.6	Tool Limitations	24
3.1.7	City Journey	24
3.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide.....	25
3.1.9	Case Study	26
4	Buro Happold.....	30
4.1	Quick Checks on Climate Impacts (Climate Proofing)	30
4.1.1	Software Requirements	30
4.1.2	Data Requirements	30
4.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	31
4.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use.....	31
4.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	31
4.1.6	Tool Limitations	32
4.1.7	City Journey	32
4.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide.....	33
4.1.9	Case Study	34
5	Deltares.....	39
5.1	HydroFlows.....	39
5.1.1	Software Requirements	39

5.1.2	Data Requirements	39
5.1.3	Expertise Requirements	40
5.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	40
5.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	40
5.1.6	Tool Limitations	40
5.1.7	City Journey	40
5.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide	40
5.1.9	Case Study	42
6	LINKS Foundation.....	50
6.1	Air quality monitoring and forecasting	50
6.1.1	Software Requirements	50
6.1.2	Data Requirements	51
6.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	51
6.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	51
6.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	51
6.1.6	Tool Limitations	51
6.1.7	City Journey	52
6.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide	53
6.1.9	Case Study	54
6.2	Ecosystem Services Assessment	58
6.2.1	Software Requirements	58
6.2.2	Data Requirements	58
6.2.3	Expertise Requirements.....	58
6.2.4	Potential Barriers to Use	58
6.2.5	Tool Use Context.....	59
6.2.6	Tool Limitations	59
6.2.7	City Journey	59
6.2.8	Step-by-Step Guide	60
6.2.9	Case Study	61
7	LNEC.....	65
7.1	Resilience Assessment Framework	65
7.1.1	Software Requirements	65
7.1.2	Data Requirements	65
7.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	66

7.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	66
7.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	66
7.1.6	Tool Limitations	66
7.1.7	City Journey	66
7.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide	66
7.1.9	Case Study	68
7.2	B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources.....	78
7.2.1	Software Requirements	78
7.2.2	Data Requirements	78
7.2.3	Expertise Requirements.....	79
7.2.4	Potential Barriers to Use	79
7.2.5	Tool Use Context.....	79
7.2.6	Tool Limitations	79
7.2.7	City Journey	79
7.2.8	Step-by-Step Guide	79
7.2.9	Case Study	81
7.3	B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse	86
7.3.1	Software Requirements	86
7.3.2	Data Requirements	86
7.3.3	Expertise Requirements.....	86
7.3.4	Potential Barriers to Use	86
7.3.5	Tool Use Context.....	86
7.3.6	Tool Limitations	87
7.3.7	City Journey	87
7.3.8	Step-by-Step Guide	87
7.3.9	Case Study	88
8	Maggioli SpA	94
8.1	MIRA Digital Twins Platform	94
8.1.1	Software Requirements	94
8.1.2	Data Requirements	95
8.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	96
8.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	96
8.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	96
8.1.6	Tool Limitations	96

- 8.1.7 City Journey 97
- 8.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide 97
- 8.1.9 Case Study 98
- 9 Mapping for Change 108
 - 9.1 Community Maps and GeoKey 108
 - 9.1.1 Software Requirements 108
 - 9.1.2 Data Requirements 109
 - 9.1.3 Expertise Requirements 110
 - 9.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use 110
 - 9.1.5 Tool Use Context..... 110
 - 9.1.6 Tool Limitations 110
 - 9.1.7 City Journey 111
 - 9.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide 112
 - 9.1.9 Case Study 113
- 10 TSPA..... 118
 - 10.1 City Scan 118
 - 10.1.1 Software Requirements 118
 - 10.1.2 Data Requirements 119
 - 10.1.3 Expertise Requirements 119
 - 10.1.4 9.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use 119
 - 10.1.5 Tool Use Context..... 120
 - 10.1.6 Tool Limitations 120
 - 10.1.7 City Journey 120
 - 10.1.8 Step-by-Step guide..... 121
 - 10.1.9 Case Study 122
- 11 UCCRN 132
 - 11.1 UDCW Methodology 132
 - 11.1.1 Software Requirements 132
 - 11.1.2 Data Requirements 132
 - 11.1.3 Expertise Requirements 132
 - 11.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use 133
 - 11.1.5 Tool Use Context..... 133
 - 11.1.6 Tool Limitations 133
 - 11.1.7 City Journey 133

11.2	UDCW Simulation Toolkit.....	133
11.2.1	Software Requirements	134
11.2.2	Data Requirements	134
11.2.3	Expertise Requirements.....	135
11.2.4	Potential Barriers to Use	136
11.2.5	Tool Use Context.....	136
11.2.6	Tool Limitations	136
11.2.7	City Journey	136
11.3	UDCW Facilitation Toolkit.....	137
11.3.1	Software Requirements	137
11.3.2	Data Requirements	137
11.3.3	Expertise Requirements.....	138
11.3.4	Potential Barriers to Use	138
11.3.5	Tool Use Context.....	138
11.3.6	Tool Limitations	139
11.3.7	City Journey	139
11.3.8	Step-by-Step Guide	140
11.3.9	Case Study 1.....	141
11.3.10	Case Study 2.....	150
12	University of Cambridge	165
12.1	Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping	165
12.1.1	Software Requirements	165
12.1.2	Data Requirements	165
12.1.3	Expertise Requirements.....	167
12.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	167
12.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	167
12.1.6	Tool Limitations	167
12.1.7	City Journey	168
12.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide	168
12.1.9	Case Study	170
13	GGGI	180
13.1	UGEM Tool.....	180
13.1.1	Software Requirements	180
13.1.2	Data Requirements	180

13.1.3	Expertise Requirements	181
13.1.4	Potential Barriers to Use	181
13.1.5	Tool Use Context.....	181
13.1.6	Tool Limitations	181
13.1.7	City Journey	182
13.1.8	Step-by-Step Guide	182
13.1.9	Case Study	183
14	Conclusion	184
	References	185

Figures

Figure 1: Key for process flow diagrams 20

Figure 2: Resilience Strategies Database and Tool process flow diagram 25

Figure 3: Results of the cost-efficiency analysis using RESCCUE tool 27

Figure 4: Results of the multicriteria analysis using RESCCUE tool 28

Figure 5: Climate Proofing Methodology process flow diagram 33

Figure 6: Climate Proofing Diagram 36

Figure 7: Workshops and engagement with authorities/governance 37

Figure 8: HydroFlows is a library of automated modular workflows for conducting flood risk assessments in a standardized and reproduceable manner..... 41

Figure 9: Location map of Rio de Janeiro and the Acari River Basin. 43

Figure 10: Results of the flood risk assessment for the Acari River Basin in Rio de Janeiro. (a). digital elevation model; (b). time series of local rainfall; (c). rainfall statistics (hyetographs) turned into event sets for specific return periods (RPs); (d). hazard 46

Figure 11: Comparison between flood map derived with global (left) and local rainfall data (right). Dots indicate measurement locations where the difference between observed and simulated water levels is known. RMSE values show to what extent local datasets on rain 47

Figure 12: Evaluation of the impact of measures on flood hazard reduction. Maps show depth differences of flood maps with and without reservoirs (top) and with and without dredging (bottom), for frequent (left) and extreme (right) rainfall events. 47

Figure 13: Evaluation of the impact of measures on flood risk reduction. Top left map shows Expected Annual Damage (EAD) for the current state without measures. All other maps show differences in EAD with the current state, for dredging (mid) and reservoirs (right) 48

Figure 14: Air quality monitoring and forecasting process flow diagram 53

Figure 15: NO2 2024 yearly hazard risk map produced with the high-resolution tool output..... 55

Figure 16: NO2 2024 yearly hazard risk map delta with respect to 2019 produced with the high-resolution tool output 56

Figure 17: Web-based application for the inspection of air quality tool output 56

Figure 18: Ecosystem Services Assessment process flow diagram 60

Figure 19: Levels of ecosystem services assessment application 61

Figure 20: Example of carbon storage assessment output 63

Figure 21: Example of urban cooling assessment output 64

Figure 22: Resilience Assessment Framework step-by-step 67

Figure 23: Alvalade parish and the São Miguel Rugby Club sports facility 69

Figure 24: RAF application in Barcelona (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c) 71

Figure 25: RAF application in Bristol (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c) 71

Figure 26: RAF application in Lisbon (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c) 71

Figure 27: Overall assessment..... 73

Figure 28: Assessment per UP2030 pillar..... 73

Figure 29: Overall assessment..... 74

Figure 30: Assessment per UP2030 pillar..... 74

Figure 31: Initial situation..... 76

Figure 32: Improvement solution..... 76

Figure 33: Overall assessment..... 76

Figure 34: Assessment per UP2030 pillar..... 76

Figure 35: : B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources step-by-step 80

Figure 36: São Miguel Rugby Club | Rugby Field with Artificial Grass 82

Figure 37: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: initial menu 83

Figure 38: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Supply, available or planned water supplies for satisfying non-potable water uses on the Bulldogs Rugby Field 83

Figure 39: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Supply, general characteristics (inc. water quality and production), water losses (distribution network), geographical position (supply point). . 84

Figure 40: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Demand, planned water demand related to non-potable water uses on the Bulldogs Rugby Field..... 84

Figure 41: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Demand, time series data: water and fertiliser need..... 84

Figure 42: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Alternatives, defined matchmaking solutions 85

Figure 43: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Alternatives, water demand satisfaction within the Water Reuse alternative 85

Figure 44: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for urban water reuse step-by-step..... 87

Figure 45: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: initial menu 88

Figure 46: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, potential biological and chemical hazards 89

Figure 47: B-WaterSmart WS Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, potential exposure routes with an impact on human health and the environment..... 89

Figure 48: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, identified hazardous events likely to have an impact on the achievement of the objective (safe water reuse)..... 90

Figure 49: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, locations where exposure to hazards may occur..... 90

Figure 50: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, exposure to hazards on activities in the field 90

Figure 51: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, people and environmental receptors (vulnerability-based classification) that may be exposed to hazards..... 91

Figure 52: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, selected barriers (i.e., risk mitigation measures to reduce hazards concentration in water or likelihood of exposure to hazards) to control risk associated with water reuse 91

Figure 53: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, selected and defined preventive measures to support risk mitigation and the management of the water reuse system 92

Figure 54: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: analysis, menu to build the risk scenarios 92

Figure 55: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: analysis, results of the risk assessment process (2 stages) regarding non-potable water reuse on the Bulldogs Rugby Field (conclusion) 93

Figure 56: MIRA Digital Twins Platform process flow diagram 97

Figure 57: Map of Istanbul 99

Figure 58: Map of Kadikoy district 100

Figure 59: City Digital Twin aggregating different hierarchical DT levels..... 101

Figure 60: Technological enablers for City Digital Twins solutions 102

Figure 61: MIRA digital twin platform 102

Figure 62: MIRA map and numeric output..... 105

Figure 63: MIRA map and visualizations 105

Figure 64: Community Maps process flow diagram..... 112

Figure 65: Community Maps interface highlighting citizens’ contributions 115

Figure 66: Presentation of Community Maps at Budapest’s Healthy Streets Conference 117

Figure 67: City Scan process flow diagram..... 121

Figure 68: Diagram presenting the process steps 124

Figure 69: Scenario matrix diagram, representing how axis were defined 125

Figure 70: Example of axonometric view of building heights distribution of NM scenario 126

Figure 71: Cooling analysis example 127

Figure 72: Electric Equipment analysis example 127

Figure 73: Heating analysis example 127

Figure 74: Lighting analysis example..... 127

Figure 75: Section of the data sheet for each scenario metrics..... 128

Figure 76: Comparison of energy demand (in kWh) among all four scenarios. The diagram represents difference of energy demands related to different urban form (e.g. density, spatial configuration), revealing which urban design choice might be more suitable in the 129

Figure 77: UDCW methodology and tools flow diagram..... 140

Figure 78: Phasing of Prototype development and collaboration with the City 144

Figure 79: Comfort outdoor simulations 3D Modelling: Current State and Business as Usual 145

Figure 80: Comfort outdoor simulations 3D Modelling: Best Practice 146

Figure 81: Phases of tools implementation and collaboration with the City..... 152

Figure 82: UDCW Facilitation City Visioning, co-design session..... 153

Figure 83: UDCW Facilitation Collaborative Mapping, digital results 155

Figure 84: UDCW Simulation, masterplan and heat wave simulations, thermal outdoor comfort 2050 scenario 155

Figure 85: UDCW Facilitation City Visioning, Old Lachanagora Market- 2025-2030 and 2050 scenarios 156

Figure 86: UDCW Simulation, Solar Energy potential available on the selected buildings in 2050Solar Energy Production - 2050 Scenario 157

Figure 87: UDCW Simulation, Heatwave Hazard - Old Lachanagora Market- 2030 scenario 157

Figure 88: UDCW Simulation, Heatwave Hazard - Old Lachanagora Market- 2050 scenario 158

Figure 89: Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping process flow diagram 169

Figure 90: Map of Linen Quarter project area (pink line) and the census data zones which have a footprint within it (green). There are three gaps, the one at the top is due to that data zone not having a presence in the project area, and the two at the bottom have a limited presence. 171

Figure 91: Estimated household carbon emissions (associated with energy use) within the Linen Quarter. The numbers correspond to the annual carbon emissions of each Census data zone. The boundaries of some data zones which fall outside the project area have been included in calculations. 173

Figure 92: Annual resident mobility kgCO2/year per person map. The emissions have been presented in terms of per person emissions due to the significant influence of population size on the findings, with a difference of 675 people when comparing the largest and smallest data zones. 174

Figure 93: This map demonstrates the clustering of different levels of household emissions. This map combines data zones and loosely, but not exactly, maps onto the different communities within the Linen Quarter – with the original Linen Quarter BID mapped in black..... 178

Figure 94: Estimated carbon emission reductions associated with solar installations presented as a proportion of possible reductions through insulation interventions. If the data zone is blue, this means that installing solar panels may reduce more carbon emissions compared to those where insulation would be more impactful (green) 178

Figure 95: UGEM process flow diagram 182

Tables

Table 1: Key information covered in the reporting of each tool..... 18

Table 2: Main characteristics of the São Miguel Rugby Club 81

Table 3: Application of the Community Maps/ GeoKey tools in the different planning phases 111

Table 4: co-designed measures generated by the UDCW process 154

Table 5: Current Climate Scenario and assessments 159

Table 6: Future Climate Scenario and Assessments..... 160

Table 7: GIS Tools outputs and indicators..... 161

Table 8: Facilitation toolkit results summary 162

1.1 Executive summary

Cities across the globe are intensively working towards reducing their carbon footprint, with the pursuit of climate neutrality being a cornerstone of UP2030. The task of effectively reducing carbon emissions within the urban realm is a deeply complex one which involves not only the actions of city authorities, but the alignment of numerous different segments of society. Such alignment is essential to support just transitions towards more resilient and sustainable cities. This includes (but is not limited to) city government, residents and citizens, the private sector and academia – as well as different urban systems such as the built and natural environments, utilities, power supply and transportation and mobility infrastructure. To support cities in this endeavour, a range of tools have been developed within UP2030. This document outlines 16 tools developed from 11 organizations within the UP2030 programme, which embody a diversity of operations, from digital twins and flood modelling to carbon mapping and citizen engagement. This background information is supported by a general step-by-step guide for their implementation, each supported by a process flow diagram, and a detailed case study of each tool being used within UP2030. Below is a list of the tools presented in this report:

Aquatec (Barcelona, ES)

Resilience strategies database and tool (RESCCUE)

Buro Happold (Berlin, GER)

Climate Proofing

Deltares (Delft, NED)

HydroFlows

LINKS Foundation (Turin, IT)

Ecosystem Services Assessment (inVEST)

Equal Services & Facilities Assessment

Urban Heat Island Risk Analysis

Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC) (Lisbon, PT)

Resilience Assessment Framework (RAF)

B-WaterSmart tools

Maggioli SpA (Santarcangelo di Romagna, IT)

MIRA Digital Twins Platform

Mapping for Change (London, UK)

Community Maps and GeoKey

Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture (TSPA) (Berlin, GER)

City Scan

Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN) (Napoli, IT)

UDCW Urban Design and Climate Workshop Methodology

UDCW Simulation Toolkit

UDCW-Facilitation toolkit

University of Cambridge (UCAM) (Cambridge, UK)

Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping

Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) (Budapest, HUN)

Urban Green Economy Model (GEM)

The tools are designed to support better mitigation and/or adaptation approaches, stakeholder engagement, data-use and design, all in the name of enhancing decision-making. Each tool is described in this report, covering the following attributes:

- An introductory overview detailing why a city should use the tool
- The software, data and expertise required to use the tool
- Potential barriers to use and limitations of the tool
- The context and point in a city’s journey the tool should be utilised within
- A high-level step-by-step guide on how to implement the tool, with supporting process flow diagram
- A detailed case study of the tool being used within UP2030

1.2 Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package's structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with Aquatec, Buro Happold, Deltares, Global Green Institute (GGGI), LINKS Foundation, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (LNEC), Maggioli SpA, Mapping for Change, TSPA, UCCRN, University of Cambridge and WP3. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D 3.6 Digital Planning and Design Tools for Climate Neutral Cities 1	
D 3.2 Transformative pathways roadmaps: strategic integration of solutions and interoperability 2	n.a.

This deliverable is designed for city practitioners and decision makers who are looking to advance their approaches towards carbon neutrality. It serves as a means of outlining each tool and, therefore, can be utilised at the start of a project (when deciding which tools to use) or during a project’s operation (when deciding how to scale the project).

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
AAD	Algorithm Aided Design
AEIS	Áreas de Especial Interesse Social
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APAC	Áreas de Proteção do Ambiente Cultural
BAU	Business As Usual
BIM	Building Information Modelling
COR	Operational Control Centre of Rio de Janeiro
D	Deliverable
dbh	Diameter at Breast Height
DT	Digital Twin
CLDs	Causal Loop Diagrams
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
CRSM	São Miguel Rugby Club
DCAP	District Climate Action Plan
EPW	Energy Plus Weather
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEM	Green Economy Model
GGGI	Global Green Growth Institute
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUNAM	Güneş Enerjisi Araştırma ve Uygulama Merkezi (Middle East Technical University Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications)
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning

IBAM	Istituto Bem Ambiental
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
InVEST	Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAEP	Local Area Energy Plan
LULC	Land Use/Land Cover
LNEC	Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering)
M	Milestone
MaaS	Mobility as a Service
MCA	Multicriteria Analysis
METU	Middle East Technical University
MDAT	Major Development Agency Thessaloniki
NBS	Nature-Based Solutions
OUC	Operação Urbana Consorciada Porto Maravilha
P-GIS	Participatory Geographic Information System
PEU	Primary Energy Use
PMV	Predicted Mean Vote
PUC-Rio	Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Rio de Janeiro
PV	Photovoltaic
RAF	Resilience Assessment Framework
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathways
RP	Return Periods
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service

SD	System Dynamics
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
SMAC	Secretaria Municipal de Meio Ambiente da Cidade
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways
SUDS	Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems
TABULA	Typology Approach for Building Stock Energy Assessment
TSNI	Travel Survey Northern Ireland
TSPA	Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture
UCAM	University of Cambridge
UCCRN	Urban Climate Change Research Network
UDCW	Urban Design Climate Workshop
UGEM	Urban Green Economy Model
UP2030	UP2030 Horizon Europe project
UTCI	Universal Thermal Climate Index
WP	Work package

2 Introduction

2.1 Background

This document covers the technical and user requirements, as well as providing case study examples and step-by-step guides of each of the tools included within UP2030’s Task 3.3: *Data governance and digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities*. This task features a total of 10 tool providers (Buro Happold, TSPA, UCCRN, Deltares, LINKS Foundation, Mapping for Change, Maggioli, LNEC, AQUATEC, UCAM – with GGGI also reporting within this document, although not originally part of the task group). Each of these tool providers have developed solutions within the data governance, digital planning or design resources spheres, which will help cities implement their climate plans, as expressed in their city visions. As a component of Task 3.3 each tool provider was required to compile a document outlining their tool or tools, which equips readers with information concerning how to use each tool, what is required to use it and offer an example of the tool being used.

The technical and user elements of each tool have been built upon since the previous deliverable (D3.6 - Digital planning and design tools for climate neutral cities 1). Reporting in D3.6 was limited due to the tool’s development and implementation being a work-in-progress. D3.7 is more comprehensive, offering case study examples of each application of the tool. Given the variety of tools and tool providers contained within this task, the one-size-fits-all approach used in the previous deliverable is ill-suited to capture such diversity. Therefore, each tool provider has had the opportunity to guide the shape of the deliverable, as well as how the required information is collected and presented. What is contained within this document is the outcome of four online workshops and three rounds of review and refinement among the tool providers.

2.2 Purpose and Scope

This document serves as a guide to help cities select the right digital planning and design tools to support their progress towards carbon neutrality.

What follows is a detailed overview of the benefits of using the presented tools, technical (software and data) and expertise requirements, any potential tool limitations or barriers to implementation and an overview of each tool’s key underpinning principles and core terms. This is supported by a step-by-step guide on how to use the tool. Table 1 outlines the core areas that this report covers each tool, and the intention behind the content in each section.

Table 1: Key information covered in the reporting of each tool

Element	What is required
Software Requirements	<p>For a city to use your tool, they will have to utilise the relevant software - whilst some users may have prior access to and experience using it, others may find it completely novel. Therefore, it is important for each tool’s software components to be extensively detailed. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the forms of software required to use this tool? • For each item listed, please state if they are free to use or require purchase. Please provide any relevant weblinks to the providers (ideally to their price list)
Data Requirements	<p>This concerns which data is needed for your tool to function. Consider what the minimum data requirements are, as well as whether this can be expanded upon</p>

	<p>by adding more/different sources. Here clarity is of importance, so the more insight around the application of data the better. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are the data requirements to use this tool? • What forms of data are required as an input (carbon emissions, demographic, etc.)? • What format does the data need to be in? • How is data to be collected?
<p>Expertise Requirements</p>	<p>Whilst some tools are relatively simple and iterative to use, others require formal training and expertise. Therefore, it is essential that users are aware of the expertise required. To this end, this section requires information about the skills and knowledge needed to use your tool. If expertise is not required, please make it clear why this is the case. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is specific expertise required to use this tool? If so, please specify the requirements. • How does this expertise apply to the tool? • Which elements within the tool require this expertise?
<p>What are the Potential Barriers which Could Prevent this Tool Being Used?</p>	<p>Every tool is designed to be user friendly within its appropriate context, yet, despite how well-designed a tool is, there will be elements which prevent various potential users from applying it. This section is focused on these elements. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software, Data, Expertise • Cost • Time • Participants
<p>In What Context is the Tool Designed to be Used?</p>	<p>This section invites you to think about the specific elements of a city your tool is designed to work within, by considering the boundary of your tool. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope of your tool • The scale of your tool (is it sector specific, or is it intended to be used at the city level?) • Are there different organisations or elements of city governance which are covered by your tool? • Is your tool intended to be solely used by city authorities/government or is it to be used by different sets of users and stakeholders?
<p>What are the Limitations of this Tool?</p>	<p>Whilst a tool is designed to work within a designated context, from the specific to the relatively broad in scope and scale, no tool can comprehensively cover every element of a city. Therefore, this section requires you to consider the limits of your tool's capability and what elements fall beyond its intended scope. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How the scope of your tool may exclude certain elements

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How the intended scale within which your tool works could limit the development of different perspectives (such as granularity at the micro-scale or 'big picture' at the macro)?
<p>Where on a City's Journey Should the Tool be Used?</p>	<p>Different cities are at various stages of developing and implementing strategies to reduce their carbon emissions. Therefore, it is important for a potential user to know where in this process they would be applying your tool and how your tool would assist in each stage. Things to consider include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When the tool is intended for use and how it would support that stage: The start of a project (idea formulation) Through development cycles (prototyping, trials) The use/application stages throughout the entire project cycle

2.3 Step-by-Step Guide Key

Within each section there is a step-by-step guide which is supported by a process flow diagram to assist users in using each tool. Below is a key to describe each of the different elements of the diagrams.

Figure 1: Key for process flow diagrams

2.4 Document structure

The document is organised as follows:

Section 1 - Introduction

Section 2-12 - Summary of each tool, grouped according to lead developing organisation

Section 13 - Conclusion

References

3 Aquatec

Aquatec (Agbar group-Veolia) is a water and environmental technology company who provides services centred around consulting, design services, integral project management, installation and implementation of advanced solutions for optimization of integral water cycle processes and conservation of the environment. They focus primarily on smart and efficient management of urban drainage systems, water, climate change and resilience within cities, the reduction of combined sewer overflow impacts in receiving waters and sustainable urban drainage systems (SUDS) as a Nature-based Solution (NBS) or rainwater harvesting for urban uses. They possess experience of assessing the impact of extreme weather events on water quantity and the subsequent effects on urban drainage management, whilst providing adaptation measures, technologies and solutions to mitigate climate impacts on the water cycle.

Partner Website: <https://www.agbar.es/innovacion/>

3.1 Resilience Strategies Database and Tool

The RESCCUE database and tool is a direct result of the [H2020 RESCCUE project](#) focused on fostering **RESilience** to cope with **Climate Change** in **Urban arEas**. The project was coordinated by Aquatec from 2016-2020 and it provided different methodologies and tools to increase urban resilience to climate change based on a multisectoral approach whose main focus was to increase the resilience of urban services.

In the current context of fast innovation, it is becoming more challenging for decision-makers to identify and prioritise the most beneficial adaptation measures for their cities. Detailed assessment of multiple measures is resource-consuming and requires specific expertise, which is not always available. To tackle these issues, RESCCUE project developed a methodology to effectively prioritise adaptation measures against extreme climate hazards in urban areas. It follows a multi-phase structure to progressively narrow down the list of potential measures. This methodology is integrated into the RESCCUE database and Decision Support Tool developed by Aquatec and CETaqua (in collaboration with other RESCCUE partners) that can be freely accessed at: <https://adaptationstrategies.resccue.eu/>

The RESCCUE database presents a set of almost 200 adaptation measures that the user can select according to different filtering criteria. Once this preliminary selection is performed, the decision support tool guides the user to perform a cost-efficiency and multi-criteria analysis in order to select the most suitable adaptation measure or strategy according to the user-defined prioritisation criteria.

This tool facilitates the decision-making process by providing guidance to evaluate and compare the cost and benefit of different adaptation alternatives and to prioritise between different adaptation measures and strategies according to multiple criteria. It also includes an extensive catalogue of climate change adaptation measures that the user can filter according to its objectives, site characteristics, etc.

Costs: No funding required

3.1.1 Software Requirements

No specific software is required. The database and tool are web based and can be freely accessed at the following address: <https://adaptationstrategies.resccue.eu/>.

The only requirement to use the tool is that the user must register with an email and a password.

3.1.2 Data Requirements

1. The following data must be introduced by the user to obtain results. For the database:

- Selection criteria to filter available adaptation measures (from a drop-down menu)
- Complete description if new measures are added (including co-benefits).

For the Decision Support tool:

- The user must initially select (from a drop-down menu) the main objectives for the resilience strategy including:
 - The target climate hazard to be addressed by the strategy: flooding, combined sewer overflows, sea level rise, drought, heatwaves or compound events.
 - The key benefits targeted: citizen's engagement, climate hazard reduction, exposure reduction, capacity building, etc.
 - Type of measure: structural, non-structural, etc.
 - Spatial scale of the strategy: building, neighbourhood, city, etc.
 - Urban sector/service to address
 - Adaptation or mitigation target

2. The user selects the appropriate measures from the database

3. Finally, the user is requested to manually introduce a weight (from 0 to 100%) to each one of the economic, social or environmental co-benefits associated with each one of the measures, an implementation cost and an effectiveness indicator.

3.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Knowledge of the local climate hazards and the resilience objectives is necessary to filter the adaptation measures. Also, to perform a complete assessment and comparison of alternatives, detailed data on the implementation cost and the effectiveness indicator must be provided so certain expertise is required to use the tool.

3.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The potential barrier is data availability and lack of knowledge in the local climate context, given that a minimum set of data must be provided to allow the database and tool to perform the prioritisation of adaptation alternatives. This includes:

- Selection criteria to filter available adaptation measures.
- Complete description in case of new added measures (including co-benefits).
- Implementation of cost and effectiveness indicators (type and value) for each selected measure.
- Weights to prioritise criteria (from 0 to 100%). Default prioritisation criteria are set (cost-effectiveness and co-benefits for measures and cost strategies), but new criteria can be added to prioritise strategies.

In case the user does not provide this minimum set of data the tool cannot be used.

3.1.5 Tool Use Context

The database and tool are designed to be used at the starting decision-making processes concerning the development of a resilience action plan or strategy for a neighbourhood, city or region, when adaptation measures are selected and prioritised. These are the initial stages when developing a Resilience Action Plan.

3.1.6 Tool Limitations

Limitation in providing mitigation measures or strategies given that the database currently includes very few examples of those measures, although, as explained, mitigation measures can be included as long as the user enters all the required information.

On the other hand, if the user does not provide the minimum set of required data (implementation costs of selected measures and efficiency indicator), the assessment and prioritisation of measures and strategies cannot be completed.

3.1.7 City Journey

During the development of a Resilience Action Plan or Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan (SECAP) for a city or region.

3.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

RESCCUE database and tool

Figure 2: Resilience Strategies Database and Tool process flow diagram

3.1.9 Case Study

New urban developments resilient to climate change through cost-effective adaptation measures

Tool Name: RESCCUE database and tool

City and District/Neighbourhood: City of Granollers

Organisations

- Granollers city council
- AQUATEC (Tool provider and Granollers' liaison)

Case Study Context

According to the Granollers' vision page, Granollers wants to move forward in a healthy and sustainable city that puts people at the centre. The city council is committed to integrate green spaces, mobility and digital infrastructures to foster communities that are connected and respectful of nature and planetary boundaries. Through initiatives such as a citizen laboratory, mobility as a service (MaaS), and sustainable energy and circular economy solutions, it is proposed to improve the quality of life of Granollers, while continuing to reduce carbon emissions and adapt to Climate change's effects on an urban scale: floods and the increase in temperature.

This approach includes promoting mixed-use city developments, affordable housing and universal accessibility to ensure that all residents benefit from a culturally rich, equitable and adaptable urban environment. This vision integrates the objectives and actions necessary to create a prosperous city with opportunities for all.

Within the framework of the UP2030 project, the objective of Granollers pilot is to define technical guidelines for the development of future neighbourhoods or urbanistic sectors following 3 main pillar objectives: (1) climate neutral neighbourhoods (involving a systemic approach and coordination between plans and programs); (2) resilience to climate crisis (balance between grey/blue/green infrastructure and creative innovation) and (3) just transition (spatial justice and economic viability).

Specifically, to achieve the pillar on climate resilience, 3 main objectives were identified:

- To identify the balance between grey and blue/green infrastructure.
- To link urban green grids and related projects with the east mountain, agricultural, and river spaces through green infrastructure and open spaces of the new areas to be developed, as part of the Green City strategy development.
- To implement cross-cutting climate mitigation and spatial justice tools to assess future new developments of the municipality.

The RESCCUE database and tool has been implemented with the objective of giving support (UPskill) with the selection of cost-efficient and innovative alternatives to ensure or increase the resilience of the future neighbourhood to climate change, especially to flooding episodes.

Applying the Tool to the Case Study

The RESCCUE database and decision support tool was selected with the aim of contributing to the action phase of the pillar on resilience, specifically to support the development of new developments in:

- Resilience against floods. Integrating NBS.
- Connecting with existing green spaces.
- Contributing to the objectives of climate neutrality and spatial justice.

In order to accomplish the main objectives described above, an implementation exercise was designed, including the following tasks:

1. Selection of resilience measures from the RESCCUE database.
2. Data compilation for cost and efficiency of alternative measures. Including a modelling exercise on Infoworks ICM.
3. Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) of alternatives.
4. Multi-criteria analysis.

Outcomes of Tool’s Use

The tool was applied to a new neighbourhood in Granollers pending to be developed. First of all, a set of criteria were defined and used as filtering criteria for the database, these include:

- The main climate hazard for which it is necessary to increase resilience is pluvial flooding.
- The alternative measures to be compared must include both structural and NBS.
- Feasibility to be implemented at neighbourhood scale.

The use of the RESCCUE tool helped to prioritise the most cost-efficient alternative meeting the initial criteria. The following table summarizes the results.

Figure 3: Results of the cost-efficiency analysis using RESCCUE tool

Finally, a complementary multicriteria analysis was performed, including additional efficiency indicators and co-benefits. The results are shown in Figure 4.

Final multi-criteria ranking results

Order by: Criterion Scenario

[DOWNLOAD DATA](#)

SCENARIO	COSTS (ESTIMATED)	QPEAK REDUCTION	RUNOFF VOLUME REDUCTION
A La Bobila_green roofs	8,573,520 € 5	240 L/s 4	747 m3 3 5
B La Bobila_infiltration trenches	1,256,774 € 2	2,060 L/s 2	2,535 m3 1 1
C La Bobila_pervious pavement	6,976,462 € 4	1,440 L/s 3	2,438 m3 2 2
D La Bòbila_infiltration basins	105,750 € 1	190 L/s 5	562 m3 4 3
E La Bòbila_stormwater retention tank	3,425,000 € 3	2,740 L/s 1	m3 5 4

Figure 4: Results of the multicriteria analysis using RESCCUE tool

Results of the multicriteria assessment show that infiltration trenches are the most recommended option in terms of cost-efficiency and considering co-benefits. Then, pervious pavements are also a cost-efficient alternative, but they do not provide as many co-benefits as, for example, green roofs or infiltration basins do. Retention tanks are among the less recommended alternatives in terms of cost-efficiency and the measure that provide less co-benefits.

Alignment of results with pilot objectives

The RESCCUE database and tool implementation in Granollers pilot, supported by the scenario modelling, allowed to define a set of recommendations to find a balance between blue/green/grey infrastructure and creative innovation to achieve neighbourhoods resilient to climate change, with main focus in flooding episodes.

The main conclusions reached through this exercise can be summarised as follows:

- To achieve the current natural conditions of the example of developable neighbourhood used in this study and, considering the urbanization planned in the urban master plan as reference, it will be necessary to implement all the proposed NBS. The expected urbanisation of the neighbourhood includes typical sectors of green spaces, buildings, roads and parking lots so that all the selected NBS play a role in reducing the stormwater run-off generated in each sector and so the flooding risk of the neighbourhood.
- Through analysing the efficiency of each measure individually it can be concluded that:
 - Infiltration basins are a cost-efficient measure because they have a lower implementation cost than other measures and many associated co-benefits, but they cannot be implemented in all urban surfaces (mainly in green areas) and therefore they could never be proposed as the only resilience solution against floods.

- Infiltration trenches (in 1st place) and permeable pavements (2nd place) would be the most efficient solutions according to the multi-criteria analysis (considering both cost-efficiency and co-benefits). They are also the ones that reduce the most runoff volume in the urban grid.
- Green roofs are the most expensive alternative to implement but the significant co-benefits they bring make them a good alternative to be implemented in buildings.
- Retention tanks are efficient in reducing peak flow but not in reducing run-off volume. They also do not provide co-benefits (environmental or social) so that it is the less recommended alternative.

The outcomes of the RESCCUE database and tool implementation in Granollers should be interpreted as an example and an approach to prioritise resilience measures both for existing and developable sectors in the city. In the framework of the UP2030 project, these results were translated into a set of recommendations to be integrated into the “Guidelines for climate resilient and equitable urban environments”, corresponding to the Granollers prototype.

Lessons learned, challenges and implementation gaps

The lessons learnt from the RESCCUE tool implementation in Granollers can be summarized as follows:

- RESCCUE tool contributed to the sharing and agreement between different departments within the city council.
- Cost-efficiency assessment and multicriteria assessment are useful tools to illustrate and prioritise the costs and benefits of different alternatives, in this case resilient alternatives.
- The analysis of co-benefits also plays a key role when quantifying the benefits of an alternative and they need to be very well computed in order to prioritise between different measures or strategies.

Regarding the challenges and implementation gaps, it must be noted that the RESCCUE tool is not a stand-alone solution but a decision support tool. It needs data from the user to perform the CBA so that reference or local data is required on:

- Implementation and operational costs of measures (in €)
- Quantification of benefits (units depending on the efficiency indicator being used)
- Weights for prioritisation criteria (from 0 to 100%).

4 Buro Happold

Buro Happold, founded in 1976, is an international, integrated consultancy of engineers, designers, and advisors with a focus on delivering sustainable solutions from the building to the city and regional scale and across a wide range of sectors. Buro Happold combines technical expertise in engineering and design with strategic thinking to help cities navigate complex climate challenges, moving towards net-zero while ensuring communities can withstand future climate impacts. As part of UP2030, Buro Happold took on the role of a Technical Partner as well as a Tool Provider, supporting the cities in the integrated transformation towards climate neutrality and resilience.

Partner Website: <https://www.burohappold.com/>

4.1 Quick Checks on Climate Impacts (Climate Proofing)

Climate change poses high risks to cities and the urban environment, that are expected to increase in the near future. At the same time, cities play a crucial role in reducing global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The Climate Proofing methodology was developed to help cities and local authorities in identifying and minimizing the climate risks of urban development projects. Furthermore, the tool offers a proven methodology for the development of implementation focused strategies within the specific project.

The tool is innovative as it equally addresses climate mitigation and climate adaptation. It integrates synergies between mitigation and adaptation measures, aiming that measures on mitigation don't negatively affect adaptation and vice versa. Exploring opportunities for synergies and joint mitigation-adaptation actions can help create long-term and holistic impacts.

The climate proofing tool enables cities to address their emissions and set a foundation to build local capacities for tackling climate mitigation and adaptation. It has a methodology for integrating data on environmental impacts in early-stage decision-making processes, including the identification of which data is needed, and which reference data is valid. It also defines baseline scenarios from which adaptation and mitigation measures can be developed. Outcomes can be integrated into further development and the following decision-making process.

Costs: Funding required

4.1.1 Software Requirements

The Climate Proofing tool is a methodology. Therefore, no software is required. The content is developed through workshops, analysis and evaluation of existing information, and planning documents.

4.1.2 Data Requirements

The data requirements for the implementation of the solution require information on planned areas and uses in the project as well as information on building types and urban layouts. Furthermore, data on location specific surface conditions and climate risks are beneficial for the assessment of project specific climate vulnerability.

Depending on availability:

Local/Municipal policies, targets, frameworks, strategies, for example:

- Climate mitigation action plans.
- Climate resilience and adaptation action plans.

- Energy efficiency, renewable energy use legislation.
- Development strategies, local area masterplans.

Project specific, depending on the project's planning stage:

- development frameworks, masterplans
- Early-stage urban designs.
- Early-stage landscape/outdoor area concept.
- Site specific area indicators: total area, gross floor area, FAR, etc.
- Any other early design concepts and studies.
- Mobility strategy.
- Energy concepts.
- Material concepts (e.g., On structural designs, outdoor surfaces).

4.1.3 Expertise Requirements

A background in climate mitigation and adaptation and an understanding of environmental impacts and the drivers of carbon emissions in cities is of benefit in using the tool and in successfully translating scientific solutions into practice. A facilitator with the above background is required to successfully translate the scientific findings into practice/ implementation.

4.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The tool aims to support municipal stakeholders in early planning stages, as crucial decisions are already made at the competition stage, or even earlier. Only a very limited amount of data and project-specific information are required for a possible implementation of the climate proofing tool. Nevertheless, a lack of any project specific information might cause a potential barrier in the development of targeted and effective measures. Cost and participant engagement could represent potential barriers. While a municipality can adopt the methodology independently, they would require funding to hire an external facilitator, potentially the tool's developer, and to effectively engage stakeholders. Also, the lack of involvement/participation of key stakeholders can be a limitation for the success of the tool's implementation.

4.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is designed to be used at the pre-feasibility phase of a planned urban development project. It is designed to be integrated into the decision-making process of local authorities and can be used in an interdisciplinary context across fields of engineering, design and planning. The climate proofing structure serves as a methodological framework for integrating climate mitigation and adaptation measures into urban development. It supports the municipality in conducting a comprehensive analysis of existing climate action plans, identifying strengths, gaps, and opportunities for improvement.

Based on this assessment, it facilitates the development of a tailored climate mitigation and adaptation strategy that aligns with the municipality's specific environmental, social, and economic context, ensuring practical implementation and long-term resilience. The tool can be used both at district as well as city scale. The tool is designed for a diverse range of urban practitioners committed to implementing climate actions, including carbon neutrality strategies and adaptation initiatives. The actors encompass governments (national, regional and local authorities working on policies and

regulations to reduce carbon emissions and enhance climate resilience) as well as urban practitioners (urban planners, architects, engineers).

4.1.6 Tool Limitations

A quantification of the expected climate impacts that allows for a targeted development of mitigation and adaptation strategies requires technical and expert knowledge. A limitation of the tool is therefore currently the need for an expert/ guidance to be provided in the application of the climate proofing tool. The tool is designed to provide a 'big picture' overview of a municipality's climate mitigation and adaptation efforts, so scale is not considered a limiting factor.

4.1.7 City Journey

The tool is to be used in early planning phases of urban development projects on a city's path to achieve their climate goals. The tool helps to develop and implement strategies and measures within the urban planning realm that contribute to achieving climate ambitions (e.g. net-zero targets or climate resilience targets). Typically, the tool is used in very early planning phases of specific urban development projects but can also be used for a later review of developed strategies and in the translation of strategies into implementation measures.

4.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

Figure 5: Climate Proofing Methodology process flow diagram

4.1.9 Case Study

Climate Proofing – a tool for urban planners and adaptation and mitigation practitioners applied in Münster, Germany

Tool Name: Climate Proofing

City and District/Neighbourhood: Münster, Germany

Organizations: Actors involved

- City of Münster (Climate Department, additional municipal departments participating in workshops)
- Buro Happold (Tool Provider and Technical Partner in UP2030)
- Fraunhofer IAO (City Liaison in UP2030)

Case Study Context

The city of Münster, located in North Rhine-Westphalia, in Germany, has a population of 307,071 inhabitants. Münster has set the ambition to be climate neutral by 2030, a strategic goal reinforced through the signature of the Climate City Contract in 2024. While the city has acted in the fields of climate mitigation and adaptation for more than 30 years, the individual municipal departments oftentimes work in silos, limiting the development and implementation of a holistic approach to climate action.

Issues faced by the city

Münster's climate action efforts face several interconnected challenges:

- Administrative departments work in silos, leading to uncoordinated initiatives and inefficient resource use.
- Emission data is only available at the city level, limiting targeted district-level interventions due to privacy and technical constraints.
- Governance strategies focus on new construction, overlooking retrofitting opportunities in existing buildings.
- Climate data is fragmented and not easily accessible across departments, reducing transparency.
- Lastly, while the city aims for district-level action, current tools and standards like [BISKO](#) are misaligned with this goal, making localized planning difficult.

Why the city wanted to use the tool

The city aims to better align and coordinate between mitigation and adaptation actions, while also placing a stronger focus on social and spatial justice. The main limitation for implementing an

integrated approach to climate action is the lack of coordination, exchange and communication between different municipal units.

The city's objective to strongly align and integrate current and future climate efforts in the municipal departments was the initial reason for the application of the Climate Proofing tool.

Further, the implementation of the Climate Proofing methodology is selected for the development of a streamlined roadmap with a focus on climate-friendly development in existing districts.

The city aimed for a better understanding and communication of the resources and data available in the city for the development and implementation of climate action.

Application of the tool

The Climate Proofing methodology is a structured, iterative framework developed to support integrated climate action in the context of urban development. It consists of five parallel and complementary steps that guide practitioners through the planning, implementation, and evaluation of climate mitigation and adaptation strategies. These steps are:

1. **Identify / Comprehend**

This initial phase involves assessing the overarching climate goals and ambitions relevant to the project context. For mitigation, it focuses on identifying targets such as GHG reduction and resource conservation. For adaptation, it emphasizes understanding expected climate impacts and vulnerabilities. The aim is to align both ambitions and recognize potential synergies or conflicts.

2. **Evaluate**

In this step, specific fields of action are defined and prioritised. For mitigation, this includes areas with high potential for GHG reduction (e.g., building energy efficiency). For adaptation, it involves assessing climate risks through tools like hotspot analyses. The evaluation ensures that both dimensions are considered together to identify integrated intervention opportunities.

3. **Minimize / Adapt**

This phase involves developing targeted strategies within the prioritised fields of action. Mitigation strategies are categorized under "Minimize," while adaptation strategies fall under "Adapt." Each strategy is assessed for its impact on both climate dimensions to identify synergies and avoid trade-offs. For example, green infrastructure can simultaneously reduce emissions and mitigate heat stress.

4. **Implement**

The developed strategies are translated into spatial interventions and operational plans. This includes allocating resources, securing funding, and selecting implementation sites. Measures are designed to contribute to both climate neutrality and resilience, such as installing green roofs that provide insulation and stormwater management.

5. **Monitor and Document**

The final step focuses on tracking the effectiveness of implemented measures over time. This involves collecting data on GHG emissions, energy consumption, temperature changes, and other indicators. Monitoring ensures continuous learning and informs future planning cycles, reinforcing the iterative nature of the methodology.

Throughout all steps, **co-creation** is emphasized as a foundational principle. Stakeholder engagement, interdepartmental collaboration, and iterative feedback loops are integrated into each phase to ensure that strategies are context-sensitive, inclusive, and institutionally embedded.

To develop the envisioned **Transition Guideline**, which builds on the Climate Proofing approach and incorporates co-creation, an **Organizational Tracker** was created in the form of a comprehensive Excel worksheet. This tracker organized and consolidated available data, tools, project outcomes, and existing guidelines related to climate action and co-creation in the City of Münster. The collected resources were then systematically mapped to the individual process steps of Climate Proofing, based on their relevance and applicability to planning and implementation processes within the city. In close collaboration with representatives of the city’s Climate Staff Unit, detailed needs and demands for the later content and implementation of the Transition Guideline were collected to develop an initial structure of the document. The baseline analysis revealed the lack of a shared understanding and vision for climate mitigation and adaptation in urban development amongst the administrative staff. Formulating a shared vision for the integration of climate mitigation and adaptation in urban development processes in Münster and its implementation on the district level was hence crucial for the development of the Transition Guideline.

Figure 6: Climate Proofing Diagram

Figure 7: Workshops and engagement with authorities/governance

Throughout the process, three workshops were conducted (vision, action and upscaling workshop) to understand the status quo regarding roles and responsibilities, existing frameworks and concepts, and available data.

Challenges

The development process faced several challenges, including fragmented interdepartmental communication, limited access to granular district-level carbon emission data due to privacy and technical constraints. Despite these obstacles, the Climate Proofing tool was successfully integrated into Münster's administrative structure through a series of collaborative workshops. These engagements facilitated the localization of the tool, aligning it with Münster's strategic climate domains and existing policy frameworks.

Conclusion

The results of the action phase can be summarized in the following outcomes:

- **Münster guideline.** This guideline compiles existing knowledge, tools, and examples to offer an integrated perspective on climate protection and adaptation in established neighbourhoods. It facilitates knowledge exchange and collaboration among stakeholders at the neighbourhood level.
- **Publication:** *"Integrating climate mitigation and adaptation at the District level: co-creating a guideline for urban climate action in Münster"*, a scientific article published in *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*. ([Frontiers | Integrating climate mitigation and adaptation at the district level: co-creating a Transition Guideline for urban climate action in Munster](#))
- **Climate Proofing Handbook:** The handbook is intended to support municipalities more broadly in identifying and understanding relevant risks and vulnerabilities. Key learnings from the implementation in Münster are integrated in the Handbook. ([UP2030 - Buro Happold](#))

Lessons learned

The development of the Guideline in Münster yielded several important lessons that are broadly applicable to urban climate governance:

- First, the process demonstrated that co-creation is not merely a participatory method but a transformative practice capable of reshaping institutional routines and fostering cross-departmental collaboration. The success of the initiative hinged on the flexibility of the Climate Proofing framework, which allowed for its adaptation to Münster's specific administrative and strategic context. A thorough baseline analysis proved essential in identifying organizational barriers and aligning the tool with local needs.
- Moreover, the project highlighted the critical role of transparent and integrated data infrastructures in enabling evidence-based decision-making, while simultaneously exposing significant limitations. Attempts to extend co-creation to political actors revealed institutional boundaries that can constrain innovation and knowledge exchange. Ultimately, the Guideline should be viewed not as a final product but as a dynamic instrument for ongoing transformation, offering a replicable model for other cities seeking to align climate mitigation and adaptation through inclusive and context-sensitive approaches.

Future opportunities

While the current iteration of the Guideline primarily targets internal administrative use, future expansions are envisioned to include broader stakeholder engagement, such as citizens, community organizations, and local businesses. This would enhance the legitimacy and social foundation of climate transitions. The historical development of the Climate Proofing tool involved a comprehensive literature review and stakeholder engagement in Berlin, and its adaptation for Münster was facilitated through UP2030. The experience in Münster underscores the importance of flexible frameworks, collaborative processes, and robust data infrastructures in advancing integrated urban climate strategies.

Promotion and dissemination of tool/results from its use

The tool has also been included in further project proposals (although not yet funded), with the aim of continuing to use it as a valuable resource for clients and further municipalities.

5 Deltares

For more than a century, Deltares has worked towards answering a central question: how can we keep our deltas, and coastal and river areas, safe, sustainable, and habitable - both now and in the future? They are a not-for-profit, world-leading Dutch knowledge institute for water and the subsurface, who possess experience working throughout the world and are guided by major societal issues. Deltares possesses a workforce of over 900 people, which is comprised of over forty different nationalities. Using applied research, they develop in-depth knowledge that is necessary and useful for decision making. By ensuring this knowledge is accessible to everyone, Deltares works towards helping with innovative solutions. Through building on the continuity of their knowledge base, they serve as an important knowledge partner when working with a range of partners – be it government, the private sector or society at large.

Partner Website: <https://www.deltares.nl/en>

5.1 HydroFlows

HydroFlows is a Python-based modular workflow enabling to perform fast assessments in data-scarce cities, to understand and quantify risk in contexts where this normally takes a lot of time and resources. This allows decision makers to act faster (investments, planning, etc.).

Costs: Funding required

5.1.1 Software Requirements

HydroFlows is a library of Python-based modular workflows for conducting flood risk assessments in a standardized and reproducible manner. A *workflow* is defined here as a sequence of rules that are executed in a specific order. The workflows include automated setup of physics-based models, statistical analysis, and impact assessments. The package can be installed from a [GitHub](#) repository. To install HydroFlows, you can use either [pip](#), [pixi](#) or [conda](#). For more information, refer to the [Getting Started](#) page.

The workflows can be executed by a *workflow engine* to manage the execution of the workflows and to take advantage of the parallelization, scalability, and caching features of these engines. Apart from the HydroFlows engine, engines like [Snakemake](#) and the Common Workflow Language ([CWL](#)) are also supported.

The available *methods* (predefined steps in a workflow) for flood risk assessments include the automated setup of physics-based models such as Wflow for hydrology and [SFINCS](#) for flood inundation, statistical analysis, and flood impact assessments using [Delft-FIAT](#). Many methods build on HydroMT (Hydro Model Tools), which is an open-source Python package that facilitates the process of building and analysing spatial geoscientific models.

The final outcomes of the flood risk workflows are flood hazard and risk maps and statistics. All software is open source and compiled model kernels are distributed as free software.

5.1.2 Data Requirements

The flood risk assessments require data on topography, hydrography, land use, landcover, soil properties, building footprints and forcing data for rainfall, temperature, evapotranspiration, coastal water levels.

The first-order flood risk assessment can be based on a large stack of state-of-art global datasets to enable rapid assessments anywhere globally. The global datasets are taken from a data catalogue and

typically require no to only minimal preprocessing. As the workflows are fully automated, these can easily be replaced by local data where available in next iterations.

5.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Setting up workflows and model components requires hydrological and hydraulic modelling expertise. Some programming expertise is required to set up a Python environment.

5.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

An important barrier is the lack of required expertise as described above. The tool set is typically used by specialists with a professional background in hydrology and hydraulic engineering. Another barrier is the lack of reliable datasets.

5.1.5 Tool Use Context

HydroFlows is now initially typically used in data-scarce cities in low and middle-income countries which lack flood risk information. However, it is envisioned that this toolset eventually as part of a comprehensive and user-friendly suite of digital services and software, which can be used by Deltares, cities and other organizations at different project stages (from risk assessment to detailed design) to make cities more resilient to water-related weather extremes. The spatial scale can vary from the city district to the national scale.

5.1.6 Tool Limitations

The first-order flood risk assessment is based on global datasets. The advantage of this is that these datasets are available globally, but the limitation is the lack of granularity and limited accuracy.

In a second step local data is used, such as higher-resolution topography and meteorological observations, which will improve the output accuracy. A limitation is that these local datasets may not always be available in low and middle-income countries.

A local context with complex water management or other infrastructure in the area of interest (a catchment area or a city) that influence the natural flow of water (e.g. storm drainage systems, weirs, sluices, bridges, reservoirs) will require detailed and tailor-made assessments.

5.1.7 City Journey

The tool is now initially used at the start of a climate resilience project to understand the urban flood risks and potentially how the project can mitigate the flood risks.

Once a city has a flood risk management system in place, the toolset can be used as part of that system in consecutive project stages, ranging from System Understanding, Risk Analysis, Master Plan, Conceptual Design, Detailed Design.

5.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

[HydroFlows](#) has been developed within the UP2030 project. It is a library of modular workflows for conducting flood risk assessments in a standardized and reproduceable manner (Figure 8). The workflows include automated setup of physics-based models, statistical analysis, and impact assessments. The tool is backed up by a large stack of state-of-art global datasets to enable rapid assessments anywhere globally. As the workflows are fully automated these can easily be replaced by local data of better quality or updated data in a rapid changing urban environment. The final outcome of HydroFlows is not only the flood risk assessment results (flood maps and expected impacts for different climate and urbanisation scenarios), but also the automated workflow itself which can be

handed over to city professionals for the use in future studies to update the assessment as the city evolves and/or the climate projections change.

Figure 8: HydroFlows is a library of automated modular workflows for conducting flood risk assessments in a standardized and reproduceable manner.

5.1.9 Case Study

Rapid and Continuous Flood Risk Assessment and Adaptation Planning for Advancing Flood Resilience in Rio de Janeiro

Tool Name: HydroFlows

City and District/Neighbourhood: Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) — Acari Basin

Organisations: Actors involved

- Rio-Águas (Fundação Instituto das Águas do Município do Rio de Janeiro)
- Operational Control Centre of Rio de Janeiro (COR)
- City Hall
- Deltares (Technical Partner)
- Delft University of Technology (City Liaison)

Case Study Context

Floods in urban areas highlight the vulnerability of cities and the complex challenges they face in managing growth and development. As urbanization accelerates, the impact of floods on densely populated areas becomes more pronounced, with development often pushing into low-lying, flood-prone areas. Climate change exacerbates these issues through increased precipitation and sea level rise, leading to more severe and frequent flooding. While the city possesses high-quality data, there is currently a lack of flood models to assess and predict flood risks in specific areas.

Within the UP2030 project, Deltares has worked together with Rio-Águas, the municipal office for urban drainage, to combat these challenges. Rio-Águas is responsible for planning, implementing, and maintaining effective drainage systems. Another committed stakeholder has been Rio de Janeiro's COR. Staff from COR also attended the training workshop held in April 2025. The Delft University of Technology has served as the city liaison between stakeholders and technical partners.

The case study area is the Acari River Basin, for which Rio-Águas is in the process of developing a Drainage Masterplan that can guide future drainage interventions, optimize resources, and ensure the city's resilience to flood risks. The main practical aim of this study was therefore to assist Rio-Águas in developing the Drainage Masterplan. From the perspective of UP2030, a scientific aim was to investigate the usefulness of global data sets in enhancing local flood risk assessments, considering their advantages and limitations. This has provided insights into how such data can complement local knowledge and decision-making in flood management.

Description of case study area

The Acari River basin in Rio de Janeiro (Figure 9) is a highly populated and flood-prone region, and heavy floods have impacted it in the past. It is characterized by medium and low-income occupations and several non-planned urban developments. The area is particularly vulnerable to flooding due to its low-lying position, rapid urbanization, and inadequate drainage systems. In past floods, such as the significant event in 2010, tens of thousands of people were affected. During the most recent flood in

January 2024, 78,000 people were affected. These floods cause widespread damage to homes, infrastructure, and public services, with several neighbourhoods in the Acari River basin being submerged (see the series of pictures below). Damage estimates may range into the hundreds of millions of reais, though exact figures are unknown.

Figure 9: Location map of Rio de Janeiro and the Acari River Basin.

As one of UP2030’s pilot cities, Rio de Janeiro plays a central role in integrating climate adaptation strategies into urban planning. The city’s current focus is on strengthening its flood resilience through better risk assessment and sustainable design interventions. Through the efforts of Rio-Águas and COR, Rio is identifying opportunities for improved drainage infrastructure, potentially supported by NBS, in line with the city’s vision for a climate-resilient future. Ultimately, Rio-Águas aims to inform the city’s Drainage Masterplan with the outcomes of this study.

Issues facing the city

The frequency and severity of floods have led to ongoing efforts by the city of Rio de Janeiro to improve drainage, build protective infrastructure, and reduce the impact on communities living near the river. However, challenges such as rapid urbanization and climate-related heavy rains continue to make the region more vulnerable than before.

Application of the Tool to the Case Study

Approach to flood risk assessment

City planning must become risk-informed to protect citizens, homes and infrastructure from climate risks such as flooding. Conducting thorough flood risk assessments and keeping these up to date as the city changes, is crucial for developing effective flood protection strategies and ensuring a sustainable urban future. HydroFlows serves to repeatedly conduct rapid and continuous flood risk assessments for decision-support.

Application in the Acari Basin

Over the last two years of UP2030, a comprehensive catalogue of data and information was compiled, necessary for all phases of assessment of flood risk and developing strategies for adaptation measures. Hydraulic and damage models have been developed for the Acari River basin. Flood hazard and risk have been computed. Adaptation measures have been identified and simulated. Results have been discussed in detail in the April 2025 training workshop. During the workshop NBS has been explored that potentially improve flood resilience in addition to the grey infrastructural measures that are being prepared by Rio-Águas.

Building capacity through a training program

In addition to the modelling of flood risk, a second component of the case study consisted of a training program. Rio-Águas and Deltares jointly hosted an intensive training workshop for technical staff from the Rio City Hall, titled “*Advancing Flood Resilience in Rio de Janeiro*” in April 2025. The workshop included field excursions, discussions on green infrastructure, training in the use of the tools, and in which the tools will be transferred to Rio-Águas to ensure these can continue to support the city beyond the scope of the project.

Detailing the process of collaborating with the city

Co-development of HydroFlows over a period of 18 months

Throughout the development of the HydroFlows python code, Deltares has collaborated with Rio-Águas. Over a period of 2 years, Deltares jointly developed the prototype for the Acari Basin. Since the start of the prototype development, as of the second year of UP2030, there have been bi-weekly online meetings with Rio-Águas, discussing prototype setup, scope of work, tool development, alignment with master planning, data collection, training and capacity development needs, and workshop preparation.

A Week of Intensive Training

Deltares organized a week of intensive training in April 2025. The hands-on training focused on hydraulic flood modelling and adaptive strategies for enhancing urban flood resilience. Participants were introduced to HydroFlows and a second tool called FloodAdapt to be able to assess flood risks and explore a range of green, blue, and grey adaptation measures. [FloodAdapt](#) is a tool previously developed by Deltares to interactively explore different adaptation strategies to mitigate flood risk such as urban greening, water storage, but also elevating homes, buyouts and floodproofing. FloodAdapt can be easily used in combination with HydroFlows.

The training targeted the Acari River Basin. Using local datasets, combined with global public data, participants applied the new tools to develop more informed and effective flood risk management strategies for the basin, ultimately contributing to climate-resilient development.

The week began on Monday morning with an introductory session, bringing together staff from the City Hall, Rio-Águas, COR, and the Deltares team. The purpose was to align everyone on the background and objectives of the workshop. In the afternoon, a field excursion took participants to the Niterói Reservoir near Bandeira Square, where discussions focused on interventions and reservoir operations.

On Tuesday morning, the group visited the Acari River Basin, guided by a representative from the Civil Defence Department. This visit provided a direct understanding of the local challenges and allowed an exchange of ideas regarding Rio-Águas' ongoing efforts and future goals for improving flood resilience in the area. The afternoon was dedicated to a hands-on training with [SFINCS](#) (Super-Fast Inundation of

CoastS), a new reduced-complexity flood modelling engine developed by Deltares. Participants learned about the physics of compound flooding, how to efficiently simulate flood scenarios, and how to interpret model inputs and outputs for research and decision-support.

Wednesday morning featured a visit to the Operational Centre's Control Room, offering insights into how COR manages different types of hazards across the city. In the afternoon, participants engaged in a practical session using FloodAdapt. Participants explored future flood scenarios involving climate change, population growth, and extreme weather, and learned how to evaluate adaptation strategies such as levees, pumps, and building floodproofing.

Thursday's program focused on solution strategies. In the morning, participants discussed the benefits and trade-offs of grey, green, blue, and hybrid infrastructure solutions. The set of NBS was based on recently published catalogues from the [World Bank](#), [GIZ](#) and [Urban GreenBlue Grids](#). Using Multicriteria Analysis (MCA), they evaluated intervention packages based on factors such as economic impact (including expected annual damage (EAD) and effects on critical infrastructure), environmental outcomes (like water quality, drought resilience, and heat stress), social and health impacts (including the number of people affected by flooding and overall liveability), as well as costs and implementation feasibility. The discussions highlighted the complexity of selecting the most effective combination of measures for the Acari Basin. In the afternoon, the group shifted focus to HydroFlows. Participants practiced setting up workflows, updating datasets, and running impact assessments, learning how [HydroFlows](#) can easily integrate new or local data to support rapid assessments in changing urban environments.

The workshop concluded on Friday with a plenary session to reflect on lessons learned and discuss next steps. Participants evaluated how to sustain the new modelling experience, how the selected solutions align with Rio's Sustainable Development Plan (PDS) and drainage masterplan, and how to continue collaboration.

Outcomes of Tool's Use

Results and Insights

Figure 11 summarizes the subsequent steps of flood risk assessment for the Acari River Basin. Important inputs to the models are the digital elevation model (a) and time series of local rainfall (b). From the latter, rainfall statistics (hyetographs) are derived and turned into event sets for specific return periods (RPs) (c). Hazard maps are then computed for different return times. (d). The combination of hazard maps and spatial data on exposure and vulnerability then leads to flood risk, expressed in terms of EAD (in \$) (e).

Figure 10: Results of the flood risk assessment for the Acari River Basin in Rio de Janeiro. (a). digital elevation model; (b). time series of local rainfall; (c). rainfall statistics (hyetographs) turned into event sets for specific return periods (RPs); (d). hazard

The Acari River Basin study proved to be very valuable, as Rio de Janeiro has a wealth of high-quality local datasets. This enabled Deltares to compare results based on global data and results based on partly global and local data (Figure 12). By combining these local datasets with public global data, they were able to analyse how the HydroFlows approach can support urban drainage strategies and contribute to more informed, effective flood risk management.

Figure 11: Comparison between flood map derived with global (left) and local rainfall data (right). Dots indicate measurement locations where the difference between observed and simulated water levels is known. RMSE values show to what extent local datasets on rain

Figure 13 shows results for some of the adaptation strategies which have been evaluated: impact of flood hazard reduction resulting from reservoirs in the upstream parts of the catchment and dredging of the Acari River. The figures show that reservoirs substantially reduce flood depth for frequent (1-in-2 years) storms. For extreme events, however, hazard mitigation is limited. Dredging reduces the flood hazard in the downstream parts of the catchment for both frequent and extreme rainfall events.

Figure 12: Evaluation of the impact of measures on flood hazard reduction. Maps show depth differences of flood maps with and without reservoirs (top) and with and without dredging (bottom), for frequent (left) and extreme (right) rainfall events.

Deltares also evaluated the impact of adaptation measures on flood risk. Figure 12 shows the results for the same interventions of reservoirs and dredging, with the flood risk expressed as EAD. The figure compares simulation of the current situation with simulations including the measures, showing a reduction of damage following the implementation of reservoirs and dredging. However, the figure also shows that a temperature increase of 2 °C Celsius will lead to higher damages, which are not compensated by the envisioned measures.

Figure 13: Evaluation of the impact of measures on flood risk reduction. Top left map shows Expected Annual Damage (EAD) for the current state without measures. All other maps show differences in EAD with the current state, for dredging (mid) and reservoirs (right)

Lessons learned

Key Takeaways and Insights from the workshop with RioÁguas

The workshop was seen as highly productive, with participants enthusiastic about the hands-on approach that allowed immediate application of new skills. The tools introduced were appreciated for their potential in preliminary flood risk analysis and early warning systems, and the concept of translating flooding into tangible impacts such as economic damage and affected populations was particularly well-received. This new ability to communicate risk in accessible terms could support Rio-Águas in working more effectively with other city departments and the public.

The role of the tool in supporting improved decision making

Adopting a “Global-to-local” approach to accelerate flood risk management: It has been observed that turning around the joint process of flood risk assessment with modelling specialists and stakeholders, by starting from first-iteration rapid assessments based on global datasets as a starting point for initial discussion with local stakeholders, is very effective in bringing everyone involved around the table based on the same information. The process allows to continuously improve the model simulations and risk assessment by adding better local data once they become available.

This requires automated workflows, with standardized and reproducible methods, to be able to go through the risk assessment process in multiple iterations, every time evaluating improvement from adding new information. The tool developed here, HydroFlows, enables us to do exactly that.

Looking Towards the Future

Future outcomes/opportunities

Several areas for improvement and future action were also identified. On a governance level, Rio-Águas recognized the need for stronger collaboration with other departments, such as urban planning, to address exposure and vulnerability factors like floodproof building design. Implementing the new modelling tools on a broader scale will also require investing in new ways of working and building technical capacity within the organization.

On a technical level, workshop participants saw opportunities to refine the identification and prioritisation of critical flood locations by developing severity levels and specific evaluation criteria. Improving the resolution and quality of local data will be crucial for conducting more detailed local-scale analyses, a topic that was not addressed in depth during the training but will be important for future work.

Another avenue for further development on the toolset is integrating existing modelling tools like [HEC-RAS](#) into the HydroFlows workflows.

As a next step, Rio-Águas will experiment and apply the new tools in another river basin, supported by regular four-weekly progress meetings to maintain momentum. The workshop has laid a solid foundation for further collaboration, capacity-building, and climate-resilient urban development in Rio de Janeiro.

6 LINKS Foundation

Fondazione LINKS was created by *Fondazione Compagnia di San Paolo* – the biggest Italian bank foundation – and Politecnico di Torino as a bridge between research and market. To this end, LINKS has been working for almost 20 years at national and international level. Thanks to the cooperation of more than 160 researchers, the Foundation oversees technical-scientific disciplines in digital technology and regional development such as artificial intelligence (AI), connected systems and the internet of things, cybersecurity, advanced calculation systems and satellite systems. LINKS are currently operating across a range of contexts, including industry 4.0, intelligent mobility, AgriTech, the space economy and smart infrastructures.

Partner Website: <https://linksfoundation.com/en/>

6.1 Air quality monitoring and forecasting

Developed entirely within the UP2030 project, the tool is now available in its initial version. Ongoing efforts within the project will focus on enhancing its performance and addressing any specific requirements from cities opting to adopt it.

Air pollution poses a significant challenge in urban areas, adversely impacting public health and environmental quality. The concentration of pollutants such as particulate matter, nitrogen dioxide, and ozone often exceeds safe levels, leading to respiratory diseases, cardiovascular ailments, and environmental degradation.

To provide support in addressing these problems, the tool generates maps showing the forecasted concentration levels of five key pollutants (PM10, PM2.5, NO2, O3, SO2) for the upcoming seven days, along with the Air Quality Index as defined by the European Environmental Agency. These outputs provide critical insights into pressing urban issues related to air quality, allowing cities to make well-informed decisions and take proactive short-term measures to address air pollution effectively.

By adopting this tool, a city could register improvements in public health, as timely interventions can be implemented to mitigate air pollution-related health risks. By issuing targeted alerts and advisories based on the forecasts provided by the tool, cities can significantly reduce the incidence of respiratory illnesses and other health impacts associated with poor air quality. Moreover, the tool facilitates evidence-based policymaking by offering comprehensive insights into air quality trends and patterns, enabling the development and implementation of effective air quality management strategies.

Costs: Partial funding required

6.1.1 Software Requirements

The air quality forecasting tool is delivered as a docker (open-source software) web-based application accessible through standard web browsers. No additional client-side software is required. The tool can be hosted on cloud-based platforms or on-premises infrastructure depending on the city's preference.

Minimum Server Requirements for Hosting: two virtual machines with at least:

- CPU: 4 cores
- RAM: 16 GB
- Storage: 100 GB minimum

Licensing: The tool is freely accessible for participating cities during the project phase. Post-project support and advanced configurations may require a dedicated license agreed between parties. No proprietary software is required. All models and services used are based on open-source or freely available technologies.

6.1.2 Data Requirements

The tool integrates various types of environmental data to produce its forecasts. These include:

- Satellite Data: A dedicated account is needed to access data.
- Meteorological Data: Open access with free registration.
- Topographic Data: Accessible through the EU Copernicus platform with a free account.

The software will automatically download, process and use the above-mentioned data to produce forecast about air quality levels in the following days with no direct intervention of the user.

6.1.3 Expertise Requirements

The tool is designed for usability and accessibility by a wide range of municipal personal.

- At the user level, no specific expertise is required beyond basic web browsing skills. The interface is intuitive and user-friendly. The web dashboard provides a straightforward way to interact with the tool's outputs, allowing users to view and interpret the air quality data without the need for formal training or expertise.
- At Technical Level, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) staff is required to deploy the tool (especially for on-prem hosting).

Interpretation of pollutant data would benefit from basic environmental or public health knowledge, although not strictly necessary.

6.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Software and data requirements do not represent a potential barrier as the tool is provided as an open-source solution which manages the required data autonomously. From the expertise side, it might require ICT skills in the technical team of the cities in charge to deploy the solution, but then no specific expertise is required to use the tool as mentioned above. From an economic point of view, partial funding might be required for hosting or advanced support post-project.

6.1.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is intended for city-wide implementation, supporting a variety of municipal departments:

- Urban Planning
- Public Health
- Environmental Monitoring
- Mobility and Transport

While the core user group is within local government, the tool can also be configured to share forecasts with the public, enhancing citizen awareness and preparedness.

6.1.6 Tool Limitations

While the tool is designed to provide forecasts with a resolution of 500 meters within the city, the limited availability of historical data and spatial diversity may introduce errors in predictions at this

scale. As such, the tool is not intended to forecast air quality at every city block but rather to observe general trends at the city level, with the ability to inspect specific areas.

The inherent limitations in data availability and spatial diversity may lead to inaccuracies in predicting air quality variations at finer scales within the city. Therefore, users should interpret the tool's forecasts as indicative of broader trends rather than precise air quality assessments at a granular level. The tool's primary utility lies in providing a general understanding of air quality dynamics across the city, allowing users to identify areas of concern and prioritise interventions accordingly.

6.1.7 City Journey

The tool is not tied to a specific phase of a carbon reduction or urban transformation project. It can be used:

- To continuously support ongoing monitoring.
- At initial stages for identifying problem areas.
- During interventions to evaluate effectiveness.
- For awareness campaigns and citizen engagement.

It supports both standalone use and integration into broader smart city and sustainability strategies.

6.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

AIR QUALITY MONITORING AND FORECASTING

Figure 14: Air quality monitoring and forecasting process flow diagram

6.1.9 Case Study

Forecasting and Analysing Urban Air Quality in Lisbon through Satellite Data and AI-Based Modelling

Tool Name: AI-Based Air Quality Forecasting Tool

City and District/Neighbourhood: Lisbon, Portugal – Alvalade District

Organisations (Actors Involved):

- LINKS Foundation
- Lisbon City

Case Study Context

Lisbon faces the dual challenge of achieving climate neutrality while ensuring equitable adaptation across its diverse urban areas. The city's daily influx of commuters significantly increases traffic emissions and air pollution, particularly in central and mixed-use districts. Over the past decade, Lisbon has invested heavily in green and blue infrastructure to promote healthier lifestyles and climate resilience. Yet, a key challenge remains: quantifying the environmental and health benefits of these interventions to inform future planning and maximise impact.

Through the Air Quality Forecasting Tool, Lisbon enhances its digital decision-support platform with high-resolution environmental intelligence. The tool provides predictive and retrospective insights into air pollution dynamics, helping the city assess the effectiveness of green infrastructure, mobility policies, and spatial planning measures.

The pilot focuses on Alvalade, a parish of over 30,000 residents characterised by mixed land uses and notable climate and social vulnerabilities. Addressing issues such as urban heat, air pollution, and car dependency, the city aims to reclaim space for people and promote sustainable mobility.

Applying the Tool to the Case Study

The Air Quality Forecasting Tool, developed by LINKS Foundation was applied in close collaboration with the City of Lisbon to assess both current and historical air pollution dynamics. The joint effort focused on testing the predictive capabilities of the tool and delivering a retrospective, high-resolution analysis of air quality trends across the city.

The machine learning algorithm working behind the tool was trained using Lisbon-specific data like meteorological patterns, topographic characteristics and pollution trends (retrieved from the local network of monitoring stations) ensuring that forecasts and analyses accurately reflected the city's environmental and climatic conditions. Even though the stations network is not needed once the service is operational, its availability and eventually extension can support broader data collection. This new data could then be used to train again the machine learning model working behind the tool, potentially leading to better forecasting performance.

In this context, LINKS granted people from the municipality access to the web-based dashboard showing daily forecasts about air pollution produced by the tool. On the other hand, LINKS team

conducted a retrospective analysis on tool output to produce a set of maps and summary indicators about the above-mentioned pollutants concentrations over multiple years. These retrospective datasets offered valuable insights into long-term trends and pollution hotspots across Lisbon.

The Lisbon team used these outputs to compare satellite-based estimates with their in-situ measurements in the Alvalade parish, collected with local monitoring stations installed during several two weeks campaign conducted between 2023 and 2024.

Despite the overall success of the collaboration, several challenges were encountered. The limited availability of long-term, high-resolution in-situ data constrained both the training process, and the spatial resolution the tool can work at, resulting in coarse results for the applicability at a parish level.

Figure 15: NO2 2024 yearly hazard risk map produced with the high-resolution tool output

Figure 16: NO2 2024 yearly hazard risk map delta with respect to 2019 produced with the high-resolution tool output

Figure 17: Web-based application for the inspection of air quality tool output

Outcomes of Tool Use

The application of the Air Quality Forecasting Tool in Lisbon resulted in a comprehensive retrospective analysis of urban air pollution trends, revealing both spatial patterns and long-term dynamics across the city. The analysis highlighted areas with recurrently high pollutant concentrations while also evidencing gradual improvements in other neighbourhoods, likely reflecting the positive effects of recent mitigation measures and mobility policies.

However, several important lessons were learned during the process. While the tool demonstrated strong potential as a city-level decision-support system, its spatial resolution limited its applicability for detailed analysis at the neighbourhood or sub-urban scale. This constraint made it challenging to directly compare the tool's outputs with the results of the in-situ air quality measurement campaigns conducted in Alvalade. The experience underlined the need for further refinement of model granularity and the potential benefits of integrating additional local data sources to enhance resolution.

Overall, the tool has strengthened Lisbon's analytical capacity for evidence-based decision-making. It enables the city to anticipate pollution peaks, monitor the effectiveness of environmental and mobility policies, and communicate more effectively with citizens about air quality conditions and associated health risks, while highlighting avenues for continued model improvement and local adaptation.

Looking Towards the Future

The Lisbon case study represents an important first step toward integrating air quality forecasting into municipal planning. Future efforts will focus on enhancing model accuracy and spatial resolution through calibration with local monitoring data and the inclusion of additional layers such as traffic information.

Through these developments, the tool can evolve into a key element of Lisbon's digital decision-support infrastructure, supporting data-driven, sustainable, and climate-resilient urban management.

6.2 Ecosystem Services Assessment

Cities are trying to place nature at the centre of local policies, territorial government actions and planning that are sustainable and resilient to the challenges of climate change. The approach to design looks to the ecosystemic potential of urban transformations, in the technical urban planning and architectural fields it is to be considered fundamental in order to be able to fully exploit the conversion of spaces into environments that generate the greatest number of positive externalities understood as environmental, social and economic. Governments, non-profits, international lending institutions, corporations and all stakeholders that play a role for the future of the cities, all manage natural resources for multiple uses and inevitably must evaluate trade-offs among them.

The Tool enables decision makers to assess quantified trade-offs associated with alternative management choices and to identify areas where investment in natural capital can enhance human development and conservation. Balancing the environmental and economic goals of the cities, the multi-service, modular design of the tool provides an effective tool.

Costs: No funding required

6.2.1 Software Requirements

The InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs) tool is delivered as a standalone desktop application with a graphical user interface. It is compatible with Windows, macOS, and Linux operating systems. The tool is open-source and freely available for download and use by cities.

For spatial data preparation and visualization, open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) software such as QGIS is recommended. Users may alternatively opt for a commercial GIS platform like ArcGIS.

Licensing: All components of InVEST are free to use under an open-source license.

6.2.2 Data Requirements

The InVEST tool requires geospatial and biophysical data as inputs to run its models, but requirements vary by model. Core data requirements typically include:

- Land Use/Land Cover (LULC): raster format.
- Biophysical Table: tabular format (CSV) assigning values to each LULC class.
- Climate or Hydrological Data: raster format or CSV.
- Administrative Boundaries.

6.2.3 Expertise Requirements

Using the InVEST tool requires the basic ability to moderate GIS expertise, depending on the complexity of the model being used and the specificity of the data. The knowledge of GIS software includes handling raster and vector data, reprojecting layers, clipping and editing attribute tables. It is also useful for users to have a basic understanding of ecosystem services concepts, which can be explored in depth in the user guide.

6.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

While InVEST is open access and user-friendly, its application requires basic GIS expertise, particularly for preparing and formatting spatial data. A key barrier is the time needed to collect and process input

data. Although no software costs are involved, technical skills and time investment may limit use by non-specialists.

6.2.5 Tool Use Context

The tool is intended for assessing city-wide scenarios but could be used also to assess local interventions. It can support several aspects of urban planning activities as:

- Climate adaptation.
- Green infrastructures.
- Water management.

While cities' urban planners are key users, the tool is also suitable for researchers and consultants.

6.2.6 Tool Limitations

InVEST can be effective in assessing ecosystem services, but some limitations must be considered. For example, it does not address real-time dynamics and cannot replace detailed quantitative environmental monitoring. Its results depend largely on the quality, resolution, and availability of input data. If only coarse or generic data are available (e.g., global land cover), the results may lack the granularity needed for site-specific decision-making.

6.2.7 City Journey

InVEST can support cities at multiple stages of a climate or NBS project cycle:

- At the start (idea formulation), InVEST helps identify priority areas for intervention by mapping ecosystem services such as carbon storage, urban cooling, or flood risk reduction.
- During development and engagement phases, the tool can be used to support citizen engagement and stakeholder dialogues by visualizing the potential benefits of different scenarios.
- In the application and monitoring phase, InVEST allows for comparison of baseline and post-intervention conditions, supporting the monitoring and evaluation of implemented scenarios

6.2.8 Step-by-Step Guide

ECOSYSTEM SERVICES ASSESSMENT

Figure 18: Ecosystem Services Assessment process flow diagram

6.2.9 Case Study

Ecosystem Services Assessment – Application in Milan with InVEST

Tool Name: InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Trade-offs)

City and District/Neighbourhood: City of Milan

Organisations

- Urban Resilience Department, Città di Milano.
- LINKS Foundation (Tool provider).
- Learning Action Alliance (LAA): researchers from “Università di Milano” and “Politecnico di Milano.”

Case Study Context

The City of Milan aimed to apply InVEST tool to better integrate environmental values into urban planning and decision-making. The municipality pursued to evaluate the contribution of green infrastructure to climate mitigation and adaptation objectives, particularly focusing on two ecosystem services: Urban Cooling and Carbon Storage and Sequestration. The initiative supports Milan’s vision to create resilient, inclusive, and liveable districts by maximizing the environmental, social, and economic benefits of green spaces.

The study covers various spatial scales: the urban level, the neighbourhood level with a selected urban regeneration area (Caserma Mameli) and the plot scale with Piazza Sicilia. These scales were chosen to test the replicability and applicability of the methodology in different planning and design contexts.

Milan faces challenges such as the urban heat island effect, limited green covers and the need to achieve the objectives set by the Air and Climate Plan to contain the temperature increase below the 2 °C threshold by 2050.

Figure 19: Levels of ecosystem services assessment application

Applying the Tool to the Case Study

The InVEST open-source tool, developed by the Natural Capital Project at Stanford University, was applied by LINKS Foundation in collaboration with the Municipality of Milan. The tool provides a spatially explicit, quantitative assessment of the biophysical and economic value of ecosystem services. In this case, InVEST was used to model the Urban Cooling and Carbon Storage and Sequestration services, producing maps that represent both the current and future scenarios under climate and land-use change conditions.

The methodology was co-developed with the Urban Resilience Department of Milan to ensure its alignment with municipal needs and its future integration into internal planning processes. Input data included LULC maps, canopy cover data, and local climate datasets. The outputs were used to inform planning decisions and to support the monitoring of Milan's "Piano Aria e Clima".

The process involved collaboration between municipal departments (Green Department, Urban Resilience) and the LAA formed by researchers of the field, which contributed expertise, data, and feedback on methodological refinements. The main challenges included data availability and harmonization and ensuring methodological consistency across scales.

Outcomes of Tool Use

The application of InVEST provided Milan with detailed maps on ecosystem service values at multiple scales. The tool enabled the identification of priority areas for green infrastructure enhancement and quantified the contribution of existing and planned green areas to carbon sequestration and urban cooling.

Beyond the technical results, the process fostered a new methodology for assessing ecosystem services in Milan, which can be replicated by municipal staff thanks to the development of a dedicated handbook. The handbook is intended for use by municipal staff and is not currently shared with users outside the municipality. The tool has been integrated into the city's monitoring framework for the Air and Climate Plan.

Among the key lessons learned is the critical importance of standardized data management and capacity building for effective tool utilization. Furthermore, it has been highlighted that the accuracy and level of detail of input data significantly influence the precision and reliability of the output results.

Overall, InVEST supported more informed, evidence-based decision-making and strengthened Milan's ability to quantify and communicate the environmental value of urban transformations.

Looking Towards the Future

Future work will focus on refining the methodology, addressing data gaps, and validating the economic assessment of the Urban Cooling service. The Municipality of Milan and LINKS Foundation plan to expand the application of InVEST to additional districts and integrate it with other existing municipal tools. Capacity building activities and the finalization of a user handbook will ensure the tool's long-term adoption and replicability within municipal processes.

Figure 20: Example of carbon storage assessment output

Figure 21: Example of urban cooling assessment output

The collaboration has also opened pathways for integrating ecosystem services assessments into broader urban planning strategies, contributing to Milan's long-term objectives of climate neutrality and resilience by 2050.

7 LNEC

LNEC, the National Laboratory for Civil Engineering in Portugal, undertakes, coordinates and promotes scientific research and technological development, aiming at continuous improvement and good Civil Engineering practice and providing services of Science and Technology to public and private, national and foreign entities. They also assist the Government in the development of public policies, providing technical support to the entities that constitute the Authority in the various sectors of Public Administration, in particular with regard to quality and safety of works, persons and assets, protection and requalification of the natural and built heritage and modernisation and technological innovation, particularly in the building sector. Since its early days, LNEC has been establishing networks and partnerships with national and international entities, giving it the ability to promote and foster the globalization of Science and Knowledge; positioning LNEC as an important partner in its area of expertise.

Partner Website: <https://www.lnec.pt/en/>

7.1 Resilience Assessment Framework

The Resilience Assessment Framework (RAF) is a tool that helps a city to undertake a structured urban resilience assessment to climate change, with focus on the urban water cycle and interdependencies, providing easy visualization of results through graphical representation.

The tool enables the user to assess the development level of city resilience, also considering the contribution of strategic services and their inter-dependencies to city resilience. The services included are water supply, wastewater, storm water and waste management, electrical energy distribution and mobility. It also supports these service providers to assess the respective resilience development level of the service.

This allows the city to identify what are the main strengths and weaknesses in the city and services resilience; to support decisions on the measures needed to enhance resilience and to develop strategies considering the long-term. Its main purposes are to support strategic decision-making, development of resilience action plans, communication among different stakeholders and assess resilience progress.

The methodology and web-tool constitute an assessment tool itself with a consistent portfolio of indicators for supporting the development and the monitoring of a resilience plan for a territory or a service. The tool is objective driven. The assessment allows to identify development levels, ranging from the whole city to a more detailed assessment regarding a specific service.

Costs: No funding required

7.1.1 Software Requirements

It is a user-friendly web-based application (<https://icaria.lnec.pt>). To have access to the tool, users need credentials for logging in; new users can get these upon request. A users' manual was developed and is accessible from the web platform. The access to the application should be made from anywhere using a large range of devices. Relying on a web framework, the app usage does not require any local installation on the user device. The only requirement is a web browser (e.g., Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox) and an internet connection.

7.1.2 Data Requirements

The use of the tool is simple and is included in the tool description. The user goes through the tool filling in the information required to calculate the resilience indicators by answering the predefined

questions. The assessment is based on forms to be filled in, to provide the answer or select from a list of predefined answers, of which: (i) only one may be selected; (ii) multiple answers may be selected.

Regarding this aspect, no specific data requirements are needed. Nevertheless, depending on the assessment to be carried out, city and services managers need to provide the information required to set the answer related to the resilience dimensions assessed. Depending on the level of maturity, it is possible to consider a less or a more detailed assessment, as well as qualitative (knowledge-based) or quantitative information (e.g. information from GIS, mathematical modelling, work orders), which may be used.

The categories include information regarding organizational planning and management; relation and communication with citizens and stakeholders; risk management; management, operation and performance of services; interdependencies between services; infrastructure and assets, historical records of climate-related events, consequences, and a description of city services and infrastructures.

7.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Urban resilience knowledge and data-based decision competences are advantageous but not mandatory. The output is addressed to city or services managers, considering a senior level of responsibility and decision. Depending on the scope of the assessment (city, service) it may involve several organizations (requiring consultation with stakeholders within the city administration to inform the assessment) or different departments of an organization.

7.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources competences. Namely, expertise in urban resilience, as it facilitates the use and results interpretation. Once the tool is flexible and provides the facility to be used in a simplified and progressive way, these barriers will be overcome. Despite the availability of the tool after UP2030 end, LNEC mentoring is only available during UP2030.

7.1.5 Tool Use Context

This tool will be utilised to assess the urban resilience of a city or strategic service.

The approach is primarily designed to be used by city authorities and managers, strategic services operators, particularly those responsible for managing urban resilience. It can also be used by metropolitan areas, consultancy services, multilateral organizations or researchers.

7.1.6 Tool Limitations

The solution addresses urban resilience to climate change, which involves multiple hazards and sectors. In this tool the focus is on water for the dimensions presented.

7.1.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating urban resilience assessment, it is intended for use to provide a resilience diagnosis (current status), facilitate the development of resilience action plans, and assess the progress of the plan implementation. The recognition of the relevance to enhance resilience is fundamental.

7.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

The step-by-step guide is represented in a flowchart in Figure 22.

Figure 22: Resilience Assessment Framework step-by-step

7.1.9 Case Study

Assessing climate resilience using the RAF | contributions of a Lisbon neighbourhood and facility for the city resilience enhancement

Tool Name: Resilience Assessment Framework

City and District/Neighbourhood: Lisbon, Alvalade Parish

Organisations:

- LNEC
- City of Lisbon

Case Study Context

Lisbon, capital of Portugal, has a population slightly above half million inhabitants, doubled daily by commuters residing in the metropolitan region. With an area of approximately 100 km², Lisbon is divided into 24 civil parishes. Alvalade is a neighbourhood of Lisbon (Figure 23), which construction was considered as one of the most important urban projects in Portugal, in the last century.

The parish of Alvalade is an area of more than 30,000 inhabitants, characterized by significant climate vulnerabilities and social inequalities. Alvalade land use characteristics are quite diverse, including housing, commercial activities, sport infrastructures, multiple green areas, health infrastructures, universities, research facilities, religious sites and schools. The planned interventions focused on the various social facilities located within the parish, such as schools, sport complexes and libraries. Lisbon intended to assess the needs and define a set of solutions (including fit for purpose NBS, water reuse) to promote climate neutrality and adaptation, considering multiple impacts (social, economic, political, environmental, technological and heritage) at the same time.

The São Miguel Rugby Club (CRSM) is a local sports organisation that promotes rugby and other sports since 1970. Since its creation it has been a reference in the training and development of Portuguese rugby, focusing on younger groups and low-income communities. The club encourages the participation of young athletes, many from local primary schools having regular weekly practice of the sport. The club has a role as an active agent in the community, with partnerships with various types of organizations. In this sports club facility, at the outdoor, there are sport fields with artificial turfgrass, namely a rugby field (official dimensions) and two football fields aside, flowerbeds, unpaved grounds, spectator stands, tree beds and other vegetation. The buildings' purpose includes changing rooms, physiotherapy rooms, weight rooms, one guest house, one restaurant, and one laundry. As mentioned, Lisbon case study addresses the Alvalade parish and the CRSM facility (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Alvalade parish and the São Miguel Rugby Club sports facility

Vision and Objectives

Lisbon has the vision and ambition to become a sustainable, resilient, inclusive and climate-neutral city by 2030, reinforcing its climate leadership position at European and global level. Lisbon's climate transition vision is based on the following goals and pillars: i) reduce GHG emissions by 80% (2030), compared to 2002; ii) increase city resilience to extreme weather events; iii) increase sink areas and carbon sequestration capacity; iv) invest in compensation programs (for residual emissions); v) ensure a fair and inclusive transition, reducing inequalities and alleviating energy poverty; vi) value the participation in the “Mission 100 cities with a neutral impact on the climate by 2030”, as a strategy to enhance investment.

The vision of Alvalade parish is based on the concept of a climate neutral future envisioned to the whole city in alignment with UP2030 pillars (carbon neutrality, climate resilience, and spatial justice).

Therefore, the RAF application in Lisbon contributes to the pilot vision by: i) providing objective information on the current resilience; ii) reinforcing the support to a decision system already used by the city; iii) improving analysis of the contributions of the existing or planned NBS; iv) improving knowledge of the effects on resilience of the identified measures; v) moving forward towards a more climate resilient and adaptive city; facilitating communication among stakeholders.

Applying the RAF in Lisbon

In Lisbon, the RAF was applied to the Alvalade Parish and São Miguel Rugby Club, to assess the resilience to climate change with focus on the water-related aspects. The application is innovative, as it considers the parish and facility's scales and aligns the assessment metrics with the UP2030 pillars (carbon neutrality, climate resilience and just transition).

The process of collaboration with the city actors included workshops, meetings, site visits, work sessions, and data and results sharing and discussions.

Meetings were organised with the Lisbon Municipality, Lisboa E-Nova, LNEC and responsible teams of the Alvalade Parish and the CRSM. The RAF was presented, including identification of application and data requirements.

The main steps carried out during the process were:

1. From all the assessment framework metrics, those applicable at parish and facility scales were identified and mapped in the UP2030 pillars, with contributions from the city.
2. The information needed to calculate the metrics, both to the Alvalade Parish and to the CRSM, was collected, receiving the contributions from the responsible managers of the parish and facility, and the Lisbon municipality.

3. The resilience assessment for the current situation, both in the parish and in the CRSM, was carried out by calculating the metrics.
4. Results were analysed with interaction with the Lisbon Municipality. Adjustments and corrections were implemented whenever needed.
5. The improvement measures that contribute to the UP2030 pillars – already implemented or being considered – were identified, with collaboration of the Lisbon Municipality, Lisboa E-Nova, and responsible teams of the Alvalade Parish and the CRSM.
6. Updates of the information were collected regarding the implemented and planned measures. An urban drainage mathematical model was developed to provide information to assess the effects of the redesign of the urban space, implementing some Nature Base Solutions and water reuse in the CRSM facility.
7. The resilience assessment for the improved situation was carried out, by calculating the metrics, both in the parish and in the CRSM.

Results were analysed and compared with the assessment for the current situation, evaluating the improvements results, with interaction with the Lisbon Municipality.

Integrating the RAF into local context

The RAF tool can be applied to diverse contexts. The framework had already been previously applied at cities' scales (see the examples next). It is currently being applied at a regional scale in the ICARIA project.

Within UP2030, in Lisbon, the RAF was applied to the Alvalade Parish and CRSM facility. The application in the UP2030 Lisbon prototype is innovative, as it considers the parish and facility' scales and aligns the assessment metrics with the UP2030 pillars (carbon neutrality, climate resilience and just transition).

A selection of the assessment framework metrics applicable at parish and facility scales was required and they were mapped according to the UP2030 pillars, in collaboration with the city, following the process already presented (see above "Applying the RAF in Lisbon").

Examples of RAF application

The examples of the RAF application at city scale are presented for Barcelona, Bristol and Lisbon in Figures 24 to 26 (Cardoso et al., 2020a, b, c), where the coloured darker tones correspond to a more advanced level of resilience.

Figure 24: RAF application in Barcelona (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c)

Figure 25: RAF application in Bristol (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c)

Figure 26: RAF application in Lisbon (Cardoso et al., 2020b, c)

Main challenges

The main challenges faced during the RAF application process in Lisbon are related with: i) the identification of metrics considering their applicability for the new scales of application (parish and facility); ii) data collection from different sectors and stakeholders, namely Lisbon Municipality, Lisbon Energy and Environment Agency, Alvalade Parish, São Miguel Rugby Club, and Portuguese National Laboratory for Civil Engineering; iii) the characterization of the improvement solutions, including the mathematical modelling of the drainage system in the São Miguel Rugby Club facility, to assess impacts of NBS implementation.

Outcomes of the RAF use

Scales of application

The resilience assessment metrics applicable at parish and facility scales were identified and applied at the Alvalade parish and São Miguel Rugby Club (CRSM). Some examples are: i) “the percentage of drinking water being used for irrigation, street cleaning, firefighting (%)”; ii) “type of energy sources used in the location (-)”; iii) “type of mobility solutions available used in the location (-)”; iv) “frequency of occurrence of major rainfall related flooding incidents (n.º/year)”; v) “estimated water retention due to the implementation of natural areas (%)”; vi) “carbon sequestration and storage increase expected due to the implementation of natural areas (tC/ha)”.

The metrics were mapped for the three UP2030 pillars, Carbon Neutrality (C), Resilience (R), Spatial Justice (S). As examples, from the abovementioned metrics, i) contributes to (R), ii) contributes to (C and R), iii) contributes to (C, R and S), iv) and v) contribute to (R), vi) contributes to (C).

Alvalade Parish

The resilience assessment results for Alvalade parish, regarding the initial situation, are presented in Figure 27, including the overall results (a) and the assessment per UP2030 pillar (b). Depending on the answers, the results present the percentage of metrics *Unanswered* (Un), *Not applicable* (NA), and those in the development levels *Advanced*, *Progressing* or *Incipient*, identifying those where any action exists yet (*Incipient_{not}*).

Overall, the Alvalade parish is developing its vision, as previously presented (see “Vision and Objectives”), as about 38% of the assessed metrics are advanced and 28% progressing, totalizing 66%. However, there is significant room for improvement, regarding the 34% of incipient metrics, and, particularly, the 11% of metrics where there is no action yet. Looking at the UP2030 pillars, it is evident that, globally, the carbon neutrality and social justice are more advanced or have higher progress, as compared with climate resilience, where a higher percentage of incipient metrics is observed, including aspects not yet covered.

A set of actions was carried out at Alvalade parish level focusing on improving knowledge and information, as well as in the areas of energy and water efficiency, mobility, circularity and waste, NBS, the environment, and social inclusion and justice. At the Alvalade Parish, methodological, digital or physical actions were identified or implemented, some at parish level while others at sub-pilots’ level. They are described in the Lisbon prototype report, and some examples are:

1. To raise awareness and engage citizens in climate neutrality initiatives
2. To increase knowledge about the parish of Alvalade and the selected pilot projects
3. Monitor and assess air quality

4. Promote sustainable events
5. Retrofitting of lighting systems to LED
6. Installation of photovoltaic system
7. Installation of an electric charging station
8. Installation of water saving devices on showers and taps
9. Use of alternative water sources for field irrigation (water reuse and rainwater use)
10. Naturalization of the water cycle to enhance hydrological functions (e.g. Infiltration, retention), storage of rainwater for local uses, and reduce peak outflows to public drainage system, using NBS
11. Reinforcing green infrastructure

The resilience assessment results for Alvalade parish, regarding the improved situation by focusing on the metrics affected by the improvement measures, are presented in Figure 28, including the overall results (a) and the assessment per UP2030 pillar (b). After considering the measures planned or implemented, overall, the Alvalade parish is following a path coherent with its vision, as it is observed now an increase of 5% of advanced metrics and all relevant aspects are having now action. However, there is significant room for improvement, particularly, regarding the 32% of incipient metrics. Looking at the UP2030 pillars, globally, the carbon neutrality and spatial justice have improved and keep more advanced or with higher progress, as compared with climate resilience. Notably, the main improvements are climate resilience related, with all relevant aspects having now action.

It is possible to foresee that, if similar measures could be adequately replicated in the parish, including other facilities, a significant resilience enhancement could be achieved.

São Miguel Rugby Club facility

The resilience assessment results for the CRSM, regarding the initial situation, are presented Figure 29, including the overall results (a) and the assessment per UP2030 pillar (b).

Overall, the CRSM has about 13% of the assessed metrics in an advanced level and 13% progressing, totaling 26%. There is significant room for improvement, regarding the 46% of incipient metrics, and, particularly, the 38% of with no action yet. Looking at the UP2030 pillars, the carbon neutrality and spatial justice are slightly more advanced, as compared with climate resilience, where a higher percentage of incipient metrics is observed, including aspects not yet covered. However, a significant room for improvement in all pillars exists.

A set of actions was carried out or planned at the CRSM facility level focusing on improving knowledge and information, as well as in the areas of energy and water efficiency, mobility, circularity and waste, NBS, the environment, and spatial inclusion and justice. At the CRSM methodological, digital or physical actions were identified or implemented at sub-pilots’ level. They are described in the Lisbon prototype report, and some examples are:

1. To raise awareness and engage the users in climate neutrality and sustainable initiatives
2. To increase knowledge about the pilot projects
3. Promote sustainable events
4. Retrofitting of lighting systems to LED
5. Installation of photovoltaic system in the roof
6. Continuous monitoring of electricity and water consumption
7. Installation of an electric charging station
8. Installation of water saving devices on showers and taps

- 9. Use of alternative water sources for field irrigation (water reuse and rainwater use)
- 10. Naturalization of the water cycle to enhance hydrological functions (e.g. infiltration, retention), storage of rainwater for local uses, and reduce peak outflows to public drainage system, using NBS
- 11. Reinforcing green infrastructure
- 12. Circularity and reuse of sports equipment

Figure 29: RAF application in CRSM for the initial situation

To analyse the effects of considering the redesign of the urban space, implementing some NBS (measures 10 and 11) and water reuse in the facility (9), a stormwater drainage mathematical model was developed. A potential solution to redesign the urban space, considering NBS and reinforcing the green infrastructure is presented in Figure 30.

The resilience assessment results for CRSM, regarding the improved situation by focusing on the metrics affected by the improvement measures, are presented in Figure 31, including the overall results (a) and the assessment per UP2030 pillar (b).

Club Rugby São Miguel – improvement solution of redesign of the urban space considering NBS

Figure 31: Initial situation

Figure 32: Improvement solution

Club Rugby São Miguel – improvement situation

Figure 33: Overall assessment

Figure 34: Assessment per UP2030 pillar

After considering the measures planned or implemented, overall, the CRMS is following a robust path, aligned with the Alvalade parish and Lisbon vision. In fact, a boost is now observed in the advanced metrics, which tripled to 34%, in the progressing metrics, which doubled to 28%, and in the evidence that all relevant aspects are having now action. This is reflected in all the UP2030 pillars, that have significantly improved.

It may be anticipated that, through the adequate replication of similar measures in other facilities within the parish, the overall resilience would present a significant improvement.

Findings and conclusions

Lessons learned

The main lessons learnt from applying the RAF tool in Lisbon are outlined below.

It is fundamental to work closely with the city, parish and facilities' managers, to:

- Bring in their background work, experience and knowledge of the city, which are essential to provide aligned and reliable information, strengthen the validation of the assessments, and ensure effective discussions and insights.
- Involve them in the identification of key aspects, assessments, data provision and verification of results.
- The tool contributed to share and discuss relevant aspects of climate resilience at different scales and how they can be aligned.
- The RAF is a useful tool to make evident and communicate among stakeholders the climate resilience strengths, weaknesses and opportunities for improvement at different cities' scales, facilitating the identification of improvement solutions and progress of improvement solutions.

The role of the RAF in supporting improved decision making

The main role of the RAF in supporting improved decision making is to help a city, parish, or facility to undertake a structured urban resilience assessment to climate change, providing easy visualization of results through graphical representation, and informing on the main strengths, weaknesses and opportunities for improvement. This information supports decisions on the measures needed to enhance resilience and to develop strategies considering the long-term, development of resilience action plans, communication among different stakeholders and assess resilience progress. It also supports visualizing the impact of the planned measures on resilience.

7.2 B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources

The Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources was developed under the H2020 B-WaterSmart project (Accelerating Water Smartness in Coastal Europe and beyond). Designed as proprietary software, the Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources implements a novel matchmaking framework for formulating and assessing candidate combinations of two or more supplies, including reclaimed water, in satisfying non-potable water demands in urban or regional contexts, to enable planning options. Its mission is to support urban management authorities and water utilities in making smart decisions for an efficient water-energy-nutrient balance in the city to leverage circular economy (water reuse) and water resiliency (climate change impacts).

The B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources implements a matchmaking framework entirely conceived for enabling a smart combination of the water sources and water demand points existing or planned in a city or region. The basic idea of the water supply/demand matchmaking is simple – use fit-for-purpose water source whenever justifiable in terms of performance (volume availability, water quality, energy demand, phosphorus reclamation), cost, and risk. Local entities, such as green area owners, which manage non-potable water demand provide their requirements (in terms of water quality and water needs throughout the year) to this matchmaking environment. The water supply/demand alternative combinations are then assessed using quantitative metrics of performance, characterising the resource recovery and efficiency towards water, energy, and phosphorus (W-E-P) and cost along a pre-defined time scale.

Costs: Partial funding required

7.2.1 Software Requirements

This tool requires payment of a fee and can run on any computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access requiring an updated internet browser in any operating environment. At an early stage for testing the adequacy/applicability of the tool to the city, its application by LNEC and the UP2030 city will not require the fee payment. The software provider can be assessed at <https://baseform.com/>.

7.2.2 Data Requirements

The data categories include the following.

Water demand/supply matchmaking:

- Input data: water descriptors; volumes (availability/supply and consumption/demand), water price (supply); related energy descriptors: energy content water (supply); related phosphorus descriptors: P concentration in reclaimed water (supply); alternatives' specific costs: CAPEX and OPEX, energy; water carbon footprint.
- Background data: municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.

Alternative combinations' selection:

- Input data: metrics employed to qualify the different water demand/supply alternatives (e.g., volume availability, cost, energy content, carbon footprint, nutrient content, geolocation); risk metric.
- Background data: municipal policy/plans, e.g., on water reuse and climate action.

7.2.3 Expertise Requirements

Strategic planning and data-based decision competences are advantageous but not mandatory. It is a flexible tool adjustable to different types of organizations, scale, and contexts. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability as well as human resources skills and competences. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.2.5 Tool Use Context

This tool is deployable at any spatial scale as it applies to any supply/demand context. It can be used from neighbourhood level to the city level. Its main objective is to promote water reuse as a safe urban resilience strategy. This is a product of the B-WaterSmart H2020 project (2020-2024) and it may be used individually or in a set of B-WaterSmart complementary and interoperable tools, namely with “Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Non-potable Water Reuse” and “Reclaimed water quality model in distribution systems”.

7.2.6 Tool Limitations

The beta-version developed (requiring a payment fee) allows a very comprehensive visualization and user-friendly customization. It has no limitations.

Compiling information with temporal and spatial granularity for Water demand/supply matchmaking may be difficult and time consuming, but once collected the tool works as repository.

7.2.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating the selection of the best water source combinations to satisfy specific non-potable uses, and to enable prioritisation of strategic and tactical planning options on the governance of water sources and water uses in an urban setting, it is intended for use throughout the entire project cycle, from the planning to the application stages.

7.2.8 Step-by-Step Guide

The step-by-step guide is represented in a flowchart in Figure 35.

Figure 35: : B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources step-by-step

7.2.9 Case Study

Circularity in the urban water cycle | B-WaterSmart tools applied in a Lisbon sports facility

Tool Name: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse

City and District/Neighbourhood: Lisbon, Alvalade Parish

Organisations:

- LNEC
- City of Lisbon

Case Study Context

See case study context in section 7.1.9.

At the São Miguel Rugby Club, the general characteristics of the facility relevant for the tool application, as well as the non-potable water uses, and main benefits and disadvantages of the artificial turfgrass are presented in Table 2. The Rugby field is presented in Figure 33, the artificial turfgrass is presented in Figure 34.

Table 2: Main characteristics of the São Miguel Rugby Club

Name	São Miguel Rugby Club Bulldogs Rugby Field - Parque Desportivo Municipal
General description	Municipal sports park (home of the Clube de Rugby de São Miguel - RSM) inaugurated in 2019, address: Av. do Brasil, 1700-067 Lisboa Sport fields, artificial turfgrass: 1 rugby field (official dimensions) and 2 football fields 5 a side Building: 12 changing rooms, 2 physiotherapy rooms, 2 weight rooms, 1 guest house, 1 restaurant, 1 laundry
Non-potable water uses	<u>Restricted access irrigation with sprinklers</u> a. watering for grass cooling on hot days, to improve the playing conditions b. washing the grass fibre blades, to increase the durability of the artificial turfgrass
Artificial turfgrass	Benefits: increased field carrying capacity, reduced water use, mechanical resistance Disadvantages: increased absorption of solar radiation (<i>i.e.</i> , 'hot spot')

Figure 36: São Miguel Rugby Club | Rugby Field with Artificial Grass

Vision and Objectives

See vision and objectives in section 7.1.9.

The B-WaterSmart tools applied in a Lisbon sports facility for promoting circularity in the urban water cycle, contribute to the prototype vision by: i) enabling smart water allocation in non-potable uses; ii) assisting city authorities in overcoming barriers related to the incipient experience on water reuse projects, namely, design, licensing, and long-term planning needed to support the required investments in municipal infrastructures; iii) contributing for water supply-demand management to specific goals, such as energy neutrality and climate action; iv) improve knowledge of application of water reuse in a sports club and inform how it could be upscaled to other similar facilities; v) moving forward towards a more climate resilient and adaptive city; vi) facilitating communication among stakeholders.

Outcomes of the B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources

The results of the B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources in the São Miguel Rugby Club - Bulldogs Rugby Field are presented in the next figures, Figure 35 to Figure 41. In detail, they address:

- General view of the initial menu (Figure 37)
- Supply (Figure 38 and Figure 39), attributes of the available water sources.
- Demand (Figure 39 and Figure 40), requirements of the non-potable water use.
- Alternatives (Figure 41 and Figure 42) designed solutions for the demand problem at stake and, in parallel, to contribute for the implementation of the city/region’s water management strategy (e.g., promotion of water reuse, decrease of drinking water consumption and of freshwater abstraction).

Figure 37: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: initial menu

Figure 38: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Supply, available or planned water supplies for satisfying non-potable water uses on the Bulldogs Rugby Field

Figure 39: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Supply, general characteristics (inc. water quality and production), water losses (distribution network), geographical position (supply point).

Figure 40: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Demand, planned water demand related to non-potable water uses on the Bulldogs Rugby Field

Figure 41: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Demand, time series data: water and fertiliser need

Figure 42: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Alternatives, defined matchmaking solutions

Figure 43: B-WaterSmart Matchmaking tool screenshot: Alternatives, water demand satisfaction within the Water Reuse alternative

Findings and conclusions

The role of the B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources in supporting improved decision making

In Lisbon, the B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources was implemented to facilitate smart water allocation in non-potable uses, namely the irrigation of sport fields. Key contributions include assisting city authorities in overcoming barriers related to the incipient experience on water reuse projects, namely, design, licensing, and long-term planning needed to support the required investments in municipal infrastructures; informing how pilot actions contribute to citywide scaling efforts; and strengthening stakeholder communication.

The main role of the B-WaterSmart Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources is supporting a city, parish, or facility with informed and improved decision making for promoting circularity in the urban water cycle.

7.3 B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse

The Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse was developed under the H2020 B-WaterSmart project (*Accelerating Water Smartness in Coastal Europe and beyond*, <https://b-watersmart.eu/living-lab/lisbon-portugal/>). Designed as proprietary software, the B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool implements a user-friendly risk assessment framework for water reuse in non-potable purposes. The human health and environmental (groundwater and surface water) risk assessment methodology is based on the relevant ISO standards (especially, ISO 31000:2018, ISO 20426:2018, and ISO 16075-2:2020) and the Regulation (EU) 2020/741 on minimum requirements for water reuse. Its mission is to assist city authorities responsible for non-potable water uses by guiding the user through the inherently complex context of health and environmental risk guidelines.

The B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse includes two main elements:

1. Configuration: Components (referring to Hazards, Exposure Routes, Exposure Sites, Activities, Population and Environment at Risk); Hazardous Events; Barriers; and Prevention Measures.
2. Analysis: Risk Identification for building the risk scenarios and Baseline Risk Analysis for assessing the risk referring to the risk control measures in place. If this risk level is not acceptable (i.e. if it is moderate or high), then additional or improved risk control measures need to be considered (Risk Treatment) to ensure a safe water reuse. The Final Risk Analysis delivers the assessment of the residual risk, resulting from the enhanced risk control. The conditions for water safe reuse are defined only when all scenarios present a low level of risk.

Costs: Partial funding required

7.3.1 Software Requirements

This tool requires payment of a fee and can run on any computer, tablet or smartphone with internet access requiring an updated internet browser in any operating environment. At an early stage for testing the adequacy/applicability of the tool to the city, its application by LNEC and the UP2030 city will not require the fee payment. The software provider can be assessed at <https://baseform.com/>.

7.3.2 Data Requirements

The data categories include: Input data: descriptors of the main features of the urban facility (e.g., public park) that may impact the human and environmental exposure to the hazards present in the reclaimed water, water descriptors relevant for risk assessment (water demand and reclaimed water quality); Background data: municipal policy/plans, national and European regulations, relevant standards on water reuse and risk assessment; Additional data: on risk treatment measures.

7.3.3 Expertise Requirements

Human health and environmental risk assessment requires basic knowledge of risk management and of the legislation applicable to water reuse. Risk management skills are advantageous but not mandatory since LNEC mentoring/support/capacity building is available within UP2030.

7.3.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Potential barriers include data availability and human resources skills and competences. Namely, expertise in risk assessment. LNEC mentoring/support is available within UP2030.

7.3.5 Tool Use Context

The tool can be used by planners and designers to integrate reclaimed water in urban planning as a water management solution to improve circularity and resilience (e.g. to drought). It is to be used at

non-potable water use specific level: a location (e.g., a garden or a park) or an activity (e.g., street cleaning).

Its main objective is to promote water reuse as a safe urban resilience strategy. This is a product of the B-WaterSmart H2020 project (2020-2024) and it may be used individually or in a set of B-WaterSmart complementary and interoperable tools, namely with “Decision Support Tool for Alternative Water Sources’ allocation in urban non-potable uses” and “Reclaimed Water Quality Model in Distribution Systems”.

7.3.6 Tool Limitations

The beta-version developed (requiring a payment fee) allows a very comprehensive visualization and user-friendly customization. It has no limitations.

7.3.7 City Journey

As a tool aiming at facilitating safe water reuse through qualifying risk in water reuse locations or activities, it is intended for use throughout the entire project cycle, from the planning to the application stages.

7.3.8 Step-by-Step Guide

The step-by-step guide is represented in a flowchart in Figure 42.

Figure 44: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for urban water reuse step-by-step

7.3.9 Case Study

Circularity in the urban water cycle | B-WaterSmart tools applied in a Lisbon sports facility

Tool Name: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse

City and District/Neighbourhood: Lisbon, Alvalade Parish

Organisations:

- LNEC
- City of Lisbon

Case Study Context

See case study context in section 7.2.9

Vision and Objectives

See vision and objectives in section 7.2.9.

Outcomes of the B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse

The results of risk assessment associated with water reuse for the São Miguel Rugby Club Field are presented below: configuration of risk management framework for urban non-potable water reuse (Figure 45 to Figure 53); analysis of the risk assessment process itself (Figure 54 to Figure 55).

Figure 45: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: initial menu

Figure 46: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, potential biological and chemical hazards

Figure 47: B-WaterSmart WS Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, potential exposure routes with an impact on human health and the environment

Figure 48: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, identified hazardous events likely to have an impact on the achievement of the objective (safe water reuse)

Figure 49: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, locations where exposure to hazards may occur

Figure 50: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, exposure to hazards on activities in the field

Figure 51: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, people and environmental receptors (vulnerability-based classification) that may be exposed to hazards

Figure 52: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, selected barriers (i.e., risk mitigation measures to reduce hazards concentration in water or likelihood of exposure to hazards) to control risk associated with water reuse

B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment		Analysis	Configuration	boceform Rita Ribeiro
Components Barriers Preventive measures Hazardous Events	PREVENTIVE MEASURES			CREATE PM
Code	Category	Name	Reference	
PM1.1)	Awareness	Signage (e.g. "Reclaimed water is being used in this area for irrigation", "Water not suitable for drinking")	ISO 20469:2018	
PM1.2)	Awareness	Identification of pipes and accessories (reclaimed water network, non-potable)	N/A	
PM2.1)	Involvement	Risk communication to teams: self-protection measures against contact with reclaimed water, information on RW quality, information on environmental benefits	N/A	
PM2.2)	Involvement	Risk communication to public (sports and festivals): self-protection measures against contact with reclaimed water, information on RW quality, information on environmental benefits	N/A	
PM2.3)	Involvement	Risk communication to staff (irrigation system and club): self-protection measures against contact with reclaimed water, information on RW quality, information on environmental benefits	N/A	
PM3.1)	Operational procedures	Training on good practices: reclaimed water use (artificial turfgrass watering and flower bed irrigation)	N/A	
PM3.2)	Operational procedures	Training on good practices: check for eventual cross-connections between drinking and non-potablewater distribution networks	N/A	
PM3.3)	Operational procedures	Irrigation scheduling	N/A	

Figure 53: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: Configuration, selected and defined preventive measures to support risk mitigation and the management of the water reuse system

← Demand Risk Assessment - Bulldogs Rugby Field - Parque Desportivo Municipal

CREATE SCENARIO

1. RISK IDENTIFICATION

HAZARDS

POPULATION OR ENVIRONMENT AT RISK

EXPOSURE ROUTES

EXPOSURE SITES

ACTIVITY

HAZARDOUS EVENTS

- Failure of reclaimed water treatment system
- Development of biofilm (RW distribution network and sprinklers/drippers)
- Cross-connection between drinking water and reclaimed distribution networks
- Contact with wet surfaces (e.g. vegetation, equipment, balls)
- Contact with reclaimed water (e.g. puddles/irrigation, lakes)
- Excessive water supply
- Watering for cooling with players on the field

NOTES

2. BASELINE RISK ANALYSIS

RISK TYPE

CLASSIFICATION OF THE LIKELIHOOD OF EXPOSURE TO HAZARDS, WITHOUT HAZARDOUS EVENTS

Figure 54: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: analysis, menu to build the risk scenarios

EXPOSURE SCENARIO	HAZARD	POPULATION OR ENVIRONMENT AT RISK	RISK EVALUATION	RISK EVALUATION
Scn20	Pathogenic bacteria - Legionella	People - Immature immune system	LOW	LOW
Scn21	Pathogenic bacteria - Legionella	People - Competent immune system	LOW	LOW
Scn22	Pathogenic bacteria - Legionella	People - Weakened immune system	LOW	LOW
Scn23	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn24	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn25	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn26	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn27	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Immature immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn28	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn29	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn30	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Immature immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn31	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn32	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn33	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Immature immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn34	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn35	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn36	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn37	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn38	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Competent immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn39	Pathogenic bacteria (indicator) - ...	People - Weakened immune system	MODERATE	LOW
Scn40	Chemical standards - Total nitrog...	Surface water - Low to moderate vulnerability	LOW	LOW
Scn41	Chemical standards - Total phosph...	Surface water - Low to moderate vulnerability	LOW	LOW
Scn42	Chemical standards - PFAS	Surface water - Low to moderate vulnerability	LOW	LOW

Figure 55: B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment tool screenshot: analysis, results of the risk assessment process (2 stages) regarding non-potable water reuse on the Bulldogs Rugby Field (conclusion)

Findings and conclusions

The role of the B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse in supporting improved decision making

In Lisbon, the B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse was implemented to assess and manage risk regarding water reuse in irrigation of sports fields with artificial turfgrass. Key contributions included assisting Lisbon Municipality in overcoming barriers related to circular economy practice already in place; supporting the development of risk management plans for the safe use of reclaimed water as an alternative water source; informing how pilot actions contribute to citywide scaling efforts; and strengthening stakeholder communication.

The main role of the B-WaterSmart Risk Assessment Tool for Urban Water Reuse is supporting a city, parish, or facility with informed and improved decision making for promoting circularity in the urban water cycle.

8 Maggioli SpA

For more than 100 years, Maggioli SpA was run as a family company which, for four generations, has made Corporate Social Responsibility a way of doing business. They have a track record of working with a range of diverse institutions (schools, universities, research centres, local and national administrations) whilst planning and supporting initiatives that place them as part of the innovation process. Additionally, Maggioli have experience supporting local and central public administrations, freelancers and companies through a range of technological services, from ‘applications for mobile devices’ and ‘computerised document storage services’ to offering consultancy and organisational support for public management. They are now expanding into the leading-edge fields of the internet of things, AI and smart urbanism.

Partner Website: <https://www.maggioli.com/en-us>

8.1 MIRA Digital Twins Platform

MIRA as a digital twin (DT) tool provides cities with the ability to create virtual replicas of urban environments. These replicas allow city planners and officials to simulate various scenarios, optimize infrastructure, and enhance decision-making processes. DTs enable efficient urban planning, helping to design better transportation systems, allocate resources effectively, and prepare for emergencies. By integrating real-time data from sensors, they facilitate proactive maintenance of critical infrastructures, extending their lifespan and reducing costs. Furthermore, MIRA fosters citizen engagement by providing interactive platforms for residents to explore and contribute to urban development projects. They also support sustainability efforts by analysing environmental data and contributing to the design of eco-friendly policies. Overall, DT tools offer cities a powerful means to improve efficiency, resilience, and citizen satisfaction in the face of complex urban challenges.

The following innovative aspects can be associated with MIRA:

- Advanced Data Integration and Analytics
- Data ingestion from different sources and owners (not only city authorities but also other third parties)
- Real-time Predictive Capabilities
- Cross-domain Applications: DTs can bridge the gap between traditionally isolated domains, such as manufacturing, supply chain, and maintenance, representing a significant innovation. This seamless integration would lead to a holistic view of operations and enable better decision-making across the organization.
- Virtual Simulation and Scenario Planning
- User-friendly Interface and Accessibility
- Security and Privacy Measures

Costs: No funding required

8.1.1 Software Requirements

MIRA is a cloud-based platform, directly accessible through a web browser. No extra software is required for the end user. Integration with various third-party data sources may require documented APIs or predefined files for import (json, csv, etc.). These data sources could be either open source,

already client-owned or should be acquired by the client. Pricing for commercial use of MIRA will depend on the type of buyer, number of assets, etc.

8.1.2 Data Requirements

In principle MIRA integrates two types of data:

- Sensor data: Any type of sensor, camera or devices that send information about a particular issue.
- Service data: All third-party data, alerts and notifications processed in the context of another service, which are aggregated and reused in dashboards for monitoring purposes).

The types of files/services that could be used with MIRA include:

- CSV, TXT files
- JSON
- XML
- RESTful APIs
- Databases (SQL and NoSQL databases). This requires the development of a database connector

MIRA is also capable of hosting geographical information through the use of shapefiles or other static information from media files (JPG, PNG, BMP, TIFF, MP4, AVI, MOV).

Depending on the context, different information be integrated. For instance, in a mobility case users can integrate data from:

- Cameras (to identify mobility congestion rates or patterns of congestion)
- Street lighting
- Mobility service operator solutions
- Energy demand and other related info/services
- Other

For energy purposes (buildings) MIRA can integrate also various data:

- Sensors (temperature, occupancy, Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) operation, etc.)
- Building Information Modelling (BIM) Models
- Energy management solution data

If a city wants to keep track of a sustainability index in different areas, then MIRA can aggregate information from:

- Sensors (Noise, CO₂, etc.)
- Possible data about occupancy and other operations of the area
- MIRA can be used to monitor the performance of those sensors and create a module for sustainability where users can associate sustainability metrics with urban operations, thus identifying needs for improvements and interventions.

In all the above case, MIRA aggregates the data and on top of the modelled DT can run different services (or integrate third party services) such as:

- Simulation (forecasting of energy demand, predict mobility, what-if scenarios for green interventions)
- Any other applicable service developed by UP2030 or service used by the pilots. The main advantage of MIRA is the aggregation of different information sources to different topologies and execute what-if scenarios for area interventions.

8.1.3 Expertise Requirements

No specific need from local authorities, just some training about the use of the tool, either online or in-person. Hands-on training on the use of the platform is the preferred method of training. These training courses on the use of the tool vary from 2 to 10 hours, depending on the number of different modules/sensors ingesting data in the system.

8.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Interoperability issues may arise due to the need to integrate diverse data sources and systems. Resistance to change within organizations and bureaucratic hurdles can slow down the adoption process. Lastly, lack of awareness or understanding of the benefits of DTs may lead to scepticism among stakeholders. Overcoming these barriers requires addressing interoperability issues early in the process, promoting awareness and education, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.

8.1.5 Tool Use Context

MIRA allows for creating virtual replicas of urban environments, either at city-wide scale or in a smaller area (neighbourhood/district), including buildings, infrastructure, and services. Furthermore, the use of data from live sensors enriches the digital model, allowing for real-time awareness, context and actionable intelligence. The exploitation of this real-time, accurate and actionable information leads to improved informed decision-making.

MIRA can be employed to optimize urban planning, infrastructure management, and citizen engagement. City planners utilize DTs to simulate various development scenarios, analyse transportation systems, and optimize resource allocation. These tools aid in the proactive maintenance of critical infrastructure, monitoring energy consumption, water usage, and waste management. Moreover, digital twins enhance emergency preparedness by simulating disaster scenarios and testing response strategies. Additionally, digital twins support sustainability efforts by analysing environmental data and facilitating the implementation of eco-friendly policies. Overall, in the context of a city, DT tools are invaluable for data-driven decision-making, improving efficiency, resilience, and citizen satisfaction in urban development and management.

8.1.6 Tool Limitations

For the scope of the pilots and the current state of the tool, MIRA can be used as a visualization and integration platform to monitor, aggregate and analyse information received from sensors or integrated from existing data sources a city may possess. Simulation of what-if scenarios requires modelling of each use case scenario separately (i.e. inputs-algorithm-outputs) which can be generalized but in some cases are pilot-specific and would be difficult to replicate them. Integration of available data and services requires the sources of information to be fully documented.

DTs face challenges such as data accuracy, scalability, and integration complexity. Real-time updates, data accuracy, privacy concerns, financial barriers and usability can also pose as limitations (depending

on the case in a smart city DT); however, MIRA considers data governance principles on how and to whom data is shared among stakeholders.

8.1.7 City Journey

MIRA can be used at various stages of a city's journey, from initial planning to ongoing management. It's crucial during urban development for simulating different scenarios, optimizing infrastructure, and engaging citizens. In operation, it aids in monitoring and managing resources efficiently, predicting maintenance needs, and enhancing emergency preparedness. Continuously, it helps in adapting to evolving needs and challenges, ensuring sustainability and resilience.

Overall, DT tools are most effective when integrated throughout the urban planning lifecycle, supporting data-driven decision-making, efficiency, and citizen satisfaction from planning to ongoing management. The only prerequisite is that the city must already have the required data available, either through deploying sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices, conducting studies, strategic plans, etc.

8.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

Figure 56: MIRA Digital Twins Platform process flow diagram

8.1.9 Case Study

MIRA Digital Twin – Energy and GHG Emissions Reduction in Istanbul

Tool Name: MIRA Digital Twin

City and District/Neighbourhood: Istanbul, Turkey – Kadıköy District

Organisations: Actors Involved:

- Maggioli - MIRA Digital Twin developer
- METU/GÜNAM (Middle East Technical University / Center for Solar Energy Research and Applications) – data and insight provider
- CIRCE (Research Centre for Energy Resources and Consumption) – simulations and scenario modelling
- Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality – city-level engagement
- Kadıköy District Municipality – local implementation area
- European Union (Horizon Innovation Actions, UP2030 Program) – funder
- Local stakeholders including energy planners, urban policymakers, building managers, and community organisations

Case Study Context

Cities today face urgent challenges — from climate action to urban inclusion. MIRA helps cities navigate these challenges:

- For **climate neutrality, resilience** and **sustainability**, it can simulate the impact of green interventions, mobility, it can model energy consumption and CO₂ emissions on given use case scenarios and therefore help plan low-carbon strategies.
- For **inclusion**, it visualizes data that highlights social disparities, enabling fairer spatial policies and citizen participation.
- For **digital transition**, it bridges data silos and integrates data and technologies into everyday urban governance.

Istanbul, a metropolis of over 16 million inhabitants, is experiencing one of the fastest rates of urbanisation in Europe. The city faces critical challenges tied to its heavy reliance on fossil fuels, rising energy demand from an ageing building stock, and vulnerability to climate change. Residential and commercial buildings are responsible for nearly 40% of energy use, and most of them were constructed before modern energy-efficiency standards were implemented.

Figure 57: Map of Istanbul

The city's climate commitments under both Turkish national strategies and the UP2030 project demand substantial reductions in GHG emissions. Istanbul therefore sought an evidence-based planning tool to assess potential retrofit impacts, guide climate action prioritisation, and facilitate communication between experts, decision makers, and the public. The MIRA DT was chosen for its ability to integrate diverse data streams into an interactive platform.

Description of Case Study Area

The Kadıköy district on Istanbul's Asian side was selected as the pilot area. Kadıköy is known for its vibrant cultural life, mixed land use, and diverse building stock. It is home to approximately half a million people and functions as both a residential hub and commercial centre. Key characteristics include high density, an ageing housing stock, significant commercial activity, and strong solar rooftop potential.

Figure 58: Map of Kadıköy district

Issues Facing the City

Istanbul, and subsequently the district of Kadıköy, faces a series of interconnected challenges in the transition toward a low-carbon and energy-efficient future. The district's **energy consumption remains high**, largely due to an **ageing and inefficient building stock**. A substantial share of Kadıköy's residential and commercial buildings were constructed before the introduction of modern energy-efficiency regulations. As a result, inadequate insulation, outdated heating and cooling systems, and limited use of renewable energy technologies contribute to elevated energy demand and greenhouse gas emissions. Many of these older buildings also fall short of earthquake resilience standards, making their renovation both an energy and a safety priority.

Another significant issue is the **dependence on imported fossil fuels**, a challenge that affects Istanbul and Türkiye more broadly. Kadıköy's electricity and heating needs are still primarily met through the national grid, which relies heavily on natural gas and other imported energy sources. This dependency not only increases energy costs and exposure to global market fluctuations but also undermines local sustainability efforts. Despite its high potential for rooftop solar generation, adoption of renewable energy solutions in Kadıköy remains relatively limited, constrained by regulatory, financial, and technical barriers.

Addressing these energy challenges is further complicated by the **fragmented data systems and the absence of comprehensive, reliable datasets**. Information on building energy performance, retrofitting activities, and real-time consumption patterns is scattered across different institutions and formats. This lack of integrated and interoperable data makes it difficult for municipal authorities to design targeted policies, monitor progress, or engage in evidence-based decision-making. Data standardization and sharing remain limited compared to the scale of the district's energy challenges.

Citizen engagement in building retrofitting efforts also remains limited. Although awareness of energy savings and climate impacts is growing, many residents face economic and procedural barriers that discourage participation in renovation programs. The perception that retrofitting is costly or

disruptive, combined with a lack of financial incentives and technical guidance, slows down the uptake of energy efficiency measures among homeowners and small businesses.

Finally, **institutional silos within and across municipal departments** pose a major obstacle to coordinated climate and energy action. Responsibilities for energy management, urban planning, environment, and public engagement are often distributed among different units with limited cross-departmental communication. This fragmentation can lead to overlapping efforts or policy gaps that hinder the implementation of integrated solutions such as district-level renewable energy systems or holistic building retrofiting programs.

Description of the tool

A Digital Twin Platform provides a real-time digital representation of the city, integrating urban data to monitor assets, infrastructures, and performance. It supports evidence-based decision-making by enabling cities to analyse current conditions and plan strategically for the future.

City DT vision and functions

It can be considered that a City DT is a network of interconnected DTs, each one representing different assets (e.g. buildings, parking slots) or networks (e.g. neighbourhoods, public spaces, etc.) (Figure 59).

In city DTs, data from multiple digital twins can be aggregated for a composite view across a number of real-world entities, such as a power plant or a city, and their related processes.

Figure 59: City Digital Twin aggregating different hierarchical DT levels

The main functions of a city DT are the following:

- **Monitoring** different metrics/ key performance indicators (KPIs) of the city DT and its belonging DTs at different hierarchies: From individual assets (e.g. buildings) to networks of assets (e.g. neighbours) up to the whole city context.
- **Different visualizations** at asset or network level.
- **Data aggregations** of various smart city services (e.g. parking, mobility, energy demand, etc.). Some of those services can apply to the asset DT level or even aggregated to the network DT.
- **What-if scenarios** for different city cases (e.g. green interventions, building renovation, restructuring neighbours).

- **New services on top of the city DT**, making use of the aggregated data. Such services could be measurement of sustainability metrics (CO₂ emissions, etc.) global (at city level) or local (asset/neighbour) energy demand and others.

From the technological perspective, the implementation of a City DT solution takes into consideration different enablers, as depicted below.

Figure 60: Technological enablers for City Digital Twins solutions

MIRA digital twin platform

MIRA is an intuitive DT platform that creates a dynamic, real-time digital replica of urban environments, infrastructure and assets. It integrates spatial data, IoT sensor data, static or dynamic sets of information, simulation results and planning tools within a single interface.

Its core objective is to support evidence-based decision-making and empower cities on their journey toward climate neutrality, resilience, sustainability, inclusion, and digital transition - major objectives of the UP2030 project.

Figure 61: MIRA digital twin platform

MIRA is designed to be accessible by different types of users. Whether you're an urban planner, a GIS professional, or a policy decision-maker, the platform supports various levels of technical expertise. While advanced features can be leveraged by users familiar with tools like GIS, the interface remains friendly and adaptable — making collaboration across departments and disciplines seamless.

Applying the Tool to the Case Study

The MIRA pilot in Istanbul was developed through a collaborative process involving local, national, and European partners. Engagement followed three major phases:

Phase 1: Data Integration – METU/GÜNAM datasets covering 2,460 buildings were standardised and ingested into MIRA.

The first stage focused on collecting, standardizing, and integrating building-level data into the MIRA platform. METU, in collaboration with GÜNAM and the city of Istanbul, provided detailed datasets covering 2,460 buildings within the Kadıköy district. These datasets included parameters such as building footprints, height, construction period, usage type, and estimated energy performance indicators. This phase also involved verifying data quality and completeness, addressing challenges related to inconsistent local records and missing attributes. The standardized dataset formed the foundation for subsequent simulation and visualization work.

Phase 2: Simulation and Scenario Design – CIRCE developed simulations for four retrofit scenarios for 2030 and 2050: photovoltaic (PV), insulation, heat pumps, and combined interventions.

In the second phase, the **CIRCE Foundation** led the development of energy simulations and scenario analyses to assess potential decarbonization pathways for Kadıköy's building stock. Four distinct retrofit scenarios were designed for the **2030 and 2050 time horizons**, focusing on combination of key technological interventions:

- **Building insulation upgrades** to reduce heating and cooling demand;
- **Deployment of heat pumps** for efficient electrified heating;

Scenario 1: Thermal Shell Improvement based on the TS825 standard followed in Turkey.

This scenario improves the building envelope – walls, windows, and roofs. The results depicted for this scenario are split into heating and cooling estimations. The baseline heating consumption is depicted in kWh as well as kWh per square meter, for the specific building. The projected consumption is also shown both in kWh and kWh/m².

Scenario 2: Passivhaus Improvement

Similarly to the previous scenario, simulations are run for a retrofit to meet Passivhaus standards [an internationally recognized ultra-low-energy building standard focused on exceptional comfort and very low heating/cooling demand]. Again, the results depicted for this scenario are split into heating and cooling estimations.

Scenario 3: TS Improvement + Heat Pump

In this scenario, MIRA combined thermal improvements indicated by the TS825 standard [a **Turkish national standard** that sets the requirements for **thermal insulation in buildings**] with a new heat pump system. MIRA visualizes how this reduces heating energy demand.

Scenario 4: Passivhaus + Heat Pump

Finally, the most ambitious scenario – combining full Passivhaus retrofit with a heat pump. This typically is expected to show the highest emissions reduction and cost savings over time.

Each scenario was simulated using CIRCE modelling framework, allowing the estimation of energy savings, CO₂ emission reductions, and long-term cost implications at both building and district level. The results provided a quantitative foundation for discussing realistic, phased pathways to achieve local and national energy transition targets.

Phase 3: Visualization and Engagement - MIRA's interactive interface visualized building and district-level simulation outcomes.

The final phase translated the analytical outcomes into an accessible, interactive form through the **MIRA digital twin interface**. The platform visualized the simulation results across Kadıköy's urban map, enabling users to explore **building-level energy performance** and aggregated **district-scale impacts** for each scenario. This visualization facilitated more intuitive understanding among city planners, policymakers, and stakeholders by connecting technical data to spatial and social contexts. The platform also serves as a communication and engagement tool, illustrating the tangible benefits of energy retrofitting and renewable energy adoption to both municipal departments and citizens.

Through these three phases, the Istanbul pilot demonstrated how integrating technical expertise, digital tools, and local collaboration can enhance the city's capacity to plan, monitor, and communicate its pathway toward a low-carbon urban future. The process underscored the value of shared data standards, transparent modelling, and participatory visualization in supporting sustainable city transitions.

Integrating the Tool into the Local Context

The MIRA platform was transformed to **tailor Istanbul's governance structures and needs and available data**, ensuring that its outputs could directly inform local decision-making and contribute to ongoing sustainability strategies. From the outset, the pilot team worked to align MIRA's analytical and visualization capabilities with the priorities of the **Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality** and the **Kadıköy District Municipality**, both of which play key roles in implementing the city's SECAP.

The project translated technical simulation results into **policy-relevant indicators**, such as potential CO₂ reductions, energy savings, and renewable generation potential under different retrofit scenarios. These indicators were designed to be compatible with the reporting requirements and monitoring tools already used within the city's SECAP framework.

Furthermore, MIRA's spatial and building-level insights could be easily **embedded into neighbourhood-scale planning processes** in Kadıköy. The platform's ability to visualize local energy performance and retrofit potential supported municipal planners in identifying priority zones for action, such as areas with older housing stock or high energy demand. These insights complemented existing local programs on energy efficiency, urban renewal, and climate resilience, helping bridge the gap between strategic objectives and on-the-ground implementation.

By adapting to the city's institutional context and data practices, MIRA not only demonstrated technical feasibility but also strengthened the link between **digital innovation and local governance capacity**, paving the way for more informed, data-driven, and participatory urban energy planning in Istanbul.

Examples of the Tool Being Used

City officials can use MIRA to compare retrofit effects under 2030 vs. 2050 scenarios, prioritise where to invest in insulation or PVs, and design pilot subsidy schemes. MIRA's maps can also be shown to the public in order to demonstrate benefits of retrofitting to citizens.

Figure 62: MIRA map and numeric output

Figure 63: MIRA map and visualizations

Challenges

Challenges included limited datasets, difficulty scaling analysis across Istanbul, need for consistent municipal engagement, and technical complexities in merging datasets, simulations, and visualisation.

Several **technical and institutional challenges** influenced both the pace and scope of development but can also be of concern when deploying the solution at full scale, or when replicating to another city. One of the most significant issues was the **limited availability and completeness of datasets**. While high-quality information was obtained for a sample of 2,460 buildings in Kadıköy, comprehensive data covering the wider Istanbul metropolitan area were difficult to access. Gaps in attributes such as energy performance, construction materials, and usage types require additional processing and assumptions, and therefore can reduce the precision of some simulations.

A related challenge involved the **difficulty of scaling the analysis beyond the pilot district**. Istanbul's size, administrative complexity, and heterogeneity of urban fabric made it challenging to apply the same data-driven approach across all districts. Expanding the digital twin to a citywide level would require greater data harmonization, institutional coordination, and computational capacity.

The process also highlighted the **need for consistent and sustained municipal engagement**. Ongoing involvement of technical staff and planners is essential to ensure that local knowledge, policy priorities, and planning data are accurately reflected within the MIRA framework. Establishing regular communication channels and capacity-building activities are vital for aligning technical outputs with practical urban needs.

Finally, it must be mentioned that the **technical complexities in merging datasets, simulation models, and visualization tools** within a unified platform. Integrating geospatial data, energy performance simulations, and interactive mapping require close coordination among partners and iterative testing to ensure interoperability. Despite these challenges, the process provided valuable insights into the requirements for scaling up digital twin approaches and strengthening data governance for sustainable urban energy planning in Istanbul.

Outcomes of Tool Use

The primary deliverable of the Istanbul pilot is the **MIRA platform**, fully integrated with analytical tools and datasets, provided by **CIRCE** and **METU/GÜNAM** respectively. This integration enables the platform to combine detailed building-level information with advanced simulation models, creating a powerful environment for evaluating energy efficiency and decarbonization strategies.

A total of **2,460 buildings** were included in the pilot use case. Their datasets – covering characteristics such as building type, age, and energy performance – have been carefully ingested and standardized within MIRA, forming the basis for simulation and visualization activities.

Using this data, **four retrofit scenarios** have been simulated, combining actions like rooftop photovoltaic systems, building insulation upgrades, deployment of heat pumps. Each scenario has been modelled for **2030 and 2050**, enabling assessment of both short- and long-term impacts on energy consumption and GHG emissions.

The platform produces **detailed building-level and aggregated district-level visualizations**, showing the energy savings and CO₂ reductions achievable under each scenario. These visualizations provide an intuitive way to compare interventions, support municipal planning, and guide decision-making toward more sustainable urban energy pathways.

Lessons Learned

- Data quality drives outcomes
- Visualisation builds trust between experts and policymakers.
- Citizen engagement is critical for uptake.
- Scaling from district to metropolitan level requires significant resources and political will.

MIRA translated complex data into accessible visuals, supporting evidence-based decision-making. Officials used results to justify subsidies, prioritise investments, and integrate energy retrofitting scenarios into Istanbul's climate planning.

MIRA platform played a significant role in transforming **complex building and energy data** into accessible, user-friendly visualizations that could be readily interpreted by municipal officials and stakeholders. By integrating simulation outputs with geospatial mapping and district-level indicators, MIRA enabled decision-makers to **see the potential impacts of various retrofit scenarios** on energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions across Kadıköy.

This capability allows city planners and municipal staff to make **evidence-based decisions**, rather than relying on assumptions or partial data. For example, the insights generated through MIRA can be used to **justify the allocation of subsidies** for energy-efficient retrofitting programs, ensuring that financial incentives are targeted toward interventions with the greatest impact. The platform also supports the **prioritisation of investments**, helping officials identify which buildings or neighbourhoods would benefit most from PV installations, insulation upgrades, or heat pump deployment.

Furthermore, MIRA's outputs can be **directly integrated into Istanbul's climate and energy planning processes**, providing a tangible link between technical analysis and policy implementation. By translating detailed simulations into clear, actionable information, the tool strengthens the city's capacity to plan, communicate, and implement retrofitting strategies that contribute to both short-term goals for 2030 and long-term decarbonization targets for 2050.

Looking Towards the Future

Next steps for MIRA after the completion of the UP2030 project include:

- Scaling up from Kadıköy to metropolitan Istanbul.
- Integrating real-time IoT data (smart meters, climate sensors).
- Expanding citizen participation through public-facing platforms (i.e., directly accessible by citizens).
- Replication in other UP2030 cities.
- Extending use beyond buildings to transport, water, and waste systems.

Conclusion

The Istanbul MIRA DT platform as used for the Istanbul pilot demonstrates how DTs can transform climate action planning. By combining building data, advanced simulations, and visualisation, MIRA created actionable insights for reducing GHG emissions in Kadıköy. While challenges remain in scaling and data integration, the tool has proven its ability to make climate action visible, accessible, and evidence-based, supporting a just and resilient urban transition.

9 Mapping for Change

Mapping for Change works to provide benefit to individuals and communities from disadvantaged or marginalised groups, along with the organisations and networks that support those communities, where the goal is to create positive sustainable transformations in their environment. They are experts in the use of GIS, applying it to meet client needs. They also support individuals from the aforementioned groups to gain access to higher education at University College London, to study fields connected with our work.

Partner Website: <https://mappingforchange.org.uk/>

9.1 Community Maps and GeoKey

Community Maps and GeoKey are integrated, web-based platforms designed to support participatory mapping and stakeholder engagement in urban planning, policy development, and local decision-making. Together, they offer a scalable, flexible, and user-friendly solution for collecting, managing, and visualising spatial data contributed by citizens, stakeholders, and local authorities.

Community Maps serves as the public-facing, interactive interface, while GeoKey operates in the background as an open-source backend system for storing and managing geospatial data. These tools have been successfully deployed across a range of contexts—from local neighbourhood projects to city-wide and national initiatives—over the past twelve years.

Mapping for Change offers these platforms as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) solution, including deployment support, training, and ongoing technical maintenance.

Costs: No funding required

9.1.1 Software Requirements

Community Maps and GeoKey function together as a modular, web-based system designed for participatory and community-driven mapping projects.

System Architecture

GeoKey (Backend Infrastructure – Open Source):

A Python/Django-based server-side application that stores and manages geographic data through an open web API. It supports user access management, structured data storage, and integration with external systems. GeoKey requires no specialist knowledge for administration and can be deployed on cloud or local servers.

Community Maps (Frontend Interface – Proprietary):

A user-friendly, browser-based application built on top of GeoKey, designed for data collection, visualisation, and analysis. It enables public engagement and internal data management via a graphic user interface optimised for desktop and mobile access.

Hosting and Deployment

Cloud-hosted (by Mapping for Change) with technical support and SLAs

Technical Specifications

Client Side:

- Browser-based (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Edge)

- Responsive design for desktop, tablet, and mobile use

Server Side:

- Python/Django application
- PostgreSQL/PostGIS database support
- RESTful API for integration
- Security Features
- HTTPS data encryption
- Role-based access control
- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)-compliant configuration
- Licensing

GeoKey: Open-source (GNU GPL v3)

Community Maps: SaaS licensing with optional bespoke development

9.1.2 Data Requirements

Data requirements vary depending on the use case. Some projects may only require quantitative datasets (e.g., air quality readings), while others focus on qualitative inputs such as community feedback on proposed urban interventions.

The platform supports a wide range of data types:

- Text
- Numeric values
- Single lookup fields (dropdown with one selection)
- Multiple lookup fields (dropdown with multiple selections)
- Date and time fields

Supported uploads:

- Images: PNG, JPEG
- Video: MP4, MKV
- Audio: MP3
- Documents: PDF

Supported data imports:

- CSV
- GeoJSON
- KML

These formats allow for the creation of new data categories or the augmentation of existing datasets. Data can also be exported for reporting or further analysis

9.1.3 Expertise Requirements

No technical expertise or GIS skills are required to use or manage the platform. Users need only basic digital literacy and familiarity with the relevant thematic area or organisational context – such as planning, community engagement, or environmental policy.

The system has been designed to be intuitive, with minimal training required (typically 2 hours). Its ease of use supports cross-departmental adoption without the need for IT or specialist staff.

9.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

For the tool to be used effectively, municipalities must recognise its potential early in the planning or engagement process. This includes:

- Identifying when to initiate a mapping project
- Determining what data to collect and share
- Developing communication strategies to engage stakeholders effectively

A key current limitation is the lack of direct integration with external platforms. While data can be imported via supported formats (e.g., CSV, GeoJSON), this is a manual process and may pose a barrier for more advanced integration needs.

Additionally, successful use requires a designated person or department to take ownership of the platform. While the system is administratively light-touch and automates many tasks, limited human resources could impact uptake and consistent use.

9.1.5 Tool Use Context

Community Maps is intended to support participatory mapping and spatially enabled stakeholder engagement across a range of urban planning and policy contexts. It allows stakeholders to create digital representations of their environment, visualise current conditions, document aspirations, and contribute to the design of interventions.

Typical use cases include:

- Identifying local challenges, assets, and development opportunities
- Facilitating transparent public participation and consultations
- Mapping barriers and opportunities for climate action and social equity
- Connecting neighbourhoods and mapping social infrastructure
- Supporting thematic initiatives (e.g., green infrastructure, flood risk, active travel)
- Promoting cross-departmental collaboration through shared visual tools

The platform helps reduce siloed working by offering a unified spatial interface to highlight overlaps, identify gaps, and foster joined-up decision-making.

A platform introduction and user guide are available at:

<https://www.youtube.com/@MappingForChange>

9.1.6 Tool Limitations

The key limitation of the platform is its reliance on internet connectivity. As a web-based application, it cannot currently be used offline. This may limit its accessibility for user groups or areas with

inadequate digital infrastructure or where digital exclusion is a concern. Offline use and integration with legacy or proprietary systems are not currently supported.

9.1.7 City Journey

Community Maps and GeoKey are suited for use throughout most stages of a city’s planning or project cycle, as seen in Table 3. Using the TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle (Rocco et al., 2024), the platform has been shown to support eight out of ten planning phases—excluding Phase 5 (Strategy Evaluation) and Phase 10 (Upscaling).

Table 3: Application of the Community Maps/ GeoKey tools in the different planning phases

Planning Phase	Description	Applicable
1. Contextualisation	Identify contextual needs and priorities	✓
2. Engagement	Engage key stakeholders	✓
3. Visioning	Design a vision and strategic goals	✓
4. Strategy Design	Design alternative strategies	✓
5. Strategy Evaluation	Evaluate the impact and feasibility of alternative strategies	+
6. Policy Design	Design policies aligned with strategy and vision	✓
7. Intervention/Spatial Design	Design (spatial) interventions based on the strategy and vision	✓
8. Piloting	Pilot proposed policies and interventions	✓
9. Pilot Evaluation	Evaluate pilot results and adapt if necessary	✓
10. Upscaling	Scale up policies and interventions based on evaluation outcomes	+

The platform is most effective during the early to mid-stages of the planning process, where collaborative data collection, visioning, and stakeholder engagement are critical to informing and shaping effective urban strategies.

9.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

Figure 64: Community Maps process flow diagram

9.1.9 Case Study

Budapest - Empowering Citizens for Greener Cities

Tool Name: Community Maps (with GeoKey)

City and District/Neighbourhood: Budapest, Hungary – the initial implementation was citywide. Further implementation will be centred on specific districts implementing the Healthy Streets programme.

Organisations: Actors involved:

- Municipality of Budapest
- GGGI Hungry
- Mapping for Change
- Local citizens and community groups

Case Study Context

Budapest City Council aimed to create a more liveable, people-centred urban environment by integrating sustainability, climate resilience, and active mobility into city planning. The city faced challenges around green infrastructure planning, limited citizen engagement, and transparency in municipal decision-making. The City of Budapest adopted Community Maps as one of its key tools for stakeholder involvement. The platform helps urban planning practitioners build stronger connections by engaging local residents and encouraging meaningful participation in planning and decision-making. It also provides a practical way to collect feedback and gather insights directly from the community.

The initial case study focused on a city-wide implementation of the platform in which issues such as heat island effects, limited green spaces, and high car dependency sought to be addressed. In addition to adopting the platform to support Budapest's new Green Infrastructure Strategy it has also been developed to support the Healthy Streets programme. The Healthy Streets methodology – adapted from London – emphasises active travel, play areas, and climate adaptation as core components of healthier, more inclusive streets. Multiple districts across the city are implementing Healthy Streets and will be engaging local stakeholders in the re-design of streetscapes through Community Maps.

Budapest faced several interconnected urban challenges. The city had insufficient green infrastructure and limited space for pedestrians, contributing to reduced urban liveability and environmental resilience. Citizen participation in planning processes was relatively low, making it difficult to incorporate community perspectives into urban development. Additionally, there was a pressing need to balance accessibility for people with disabilities with broader climate and active travel goals. These issues were compounded by challenges in cross-sector coordination and public communication, which often hindered the effective implementation of integrated, people-centred urban strategies.

Applying the Tool to the Case Study

Detailing the Process of Collaborating with the City

Working with the municipality’s Green Infrastructure Development Unit and Department of Climate and Environment, Mapping for Change developed a tailored version of the platform to serve two main goals:

- To collect proposals from citizens on where to plant new trees; create new green areas on hard surfaces and identify poor green areas in need of renovation.
- To visualise and share information on existing city plans for green spaces, whether planned or already implemented.

Part of the initial development stage involved working closely to discuss options on data management (user registration, access settings, and moderation), user engagement, and the technical configuration of the admin dashboard (GeoKey). Training and capacity building sessions were held to ensure the knowledge to maintain, update and edit that map structure were held within the municipality.

Integrating the Tool into the Local Context

A localised Hungarian version of the platform was developed to ensure accessibility and usability for local residents. The tool was embedded within Budapest’s Green Infrastructure Strategy and the broader Healthy Streets initiative, aligning it with the city’s sustainability and urban liveability goals. To encourage public participation and raise awareness, the mayor actively promoted the platform through social media campaigns, highlighting its role in supporting citizen engagement and collaborative urban planning.

Examples of the Tool Being Used

Over a two-month period, residents submitted 898 proposals through the platform, focusing on initiatives such as tree planting, the creation of new green areas, and the renovation of existing public spaces. The tool facilitated participatory mapping, enabling citizens to identify issues and propose tangible improvements within their neighbourhoods. Data exported via GeoKey was integrated into existing city planning workflows, supporting evidence-based decision-making and enhancing collaboration between citizens and municipal departments.

Figure 65: Community Maps interface highlighting citizens' contributions

Implementation and Capacity Building

The project's implementation was marked by strong cooperation between partners which enabled a smooth and collaborative workflow. To ensure that all participants could effectively engage with the platform and contribute meaningfully, training and capacity building were envisioned as core components of the process.

To support this, a suite of introductory and user-focused materials were developed, including:

- [Community Maps Platform Introduction](#)
- [Community Mapping Platform User Guide](#)
- [GeoKey admin dashboard tutorial](#)

These resources were designed to equip users with the necessary skills to navigate the platform, understand its functionalities, and actively participate in community mapping activities, strengthening both engagement and the quality of contributions.

Challenges

The project encountered several challenges during implementation. There was a lack of 3D visualization for certain elements within the urban realm, such as tree height, which limited the ability to fully represent people's connection within spaces being described. However, many opted to include images of streetscapes and Google Street View to overcome this. The mapping interface had limited granularity in terms of the extent in which users can zoom into micro-scale localities, such as a dropped kerb, making it difficult to capture issues at that scale. Additionally, maintaining momentum required active moderation and consistent promotion to sustain citizen engagement over time.

Outcomes of Tool Use

The initiative generated a rich dataset of over 800 citizen proposals, including 300 located within city-managed areas. These insights directly informed the development of the 2025–2031 “Concrete and Asphalt for Green Surfaces” programme, guiding future investments in sustainable urban infrastructure. The data and community input also supported the approval of a pilot sponge city project, enhancing transparency in urban planning and strengthening the connection between citizen participation and municipal decision-making.

Platform Engagement Statistics (Google Analytics):

- Sessions: 2,324
- Active Users: 1,846
- New Users: 1,830
- Average Engagement Time per Session: 1 minute 53 seconds

These metrics reflect strong public interest and engagement with the Community Maps platform, demonstrating its effectiveness in reaching and activating a broad user base within a short timeframe.

Lessons Learned

Participatory tools have proven effective in generating high-quality, actionable data to inform urban planning processes. Their visual and interactive interfaces significantly enhance citizen engagement, fostering greater transparency and trust between residents and local authorities. To ensure lasting impact and meaningful participation, clear strategies for moderation, communication, and data management are essential components of successful implementation.

The tool enabled data-driven urban planning by directly integrating citizen input into municipal decision-making processes. It strengthened transparency and accountability between citizens and government, fostering a more collaborative approach to urban development. Additionally, the data collected provided valuable, evidence-based support for advancing climate resilience initiatives and shaping policies related to public spaces and sustainable city planning.

Looking Towards the Future

The city plans to continue using Community Maps through the Healthy Streets Knowledge Centre, ensuring the tool remains a core component of participatory urban planning. There are plans to expand its implementation to nine districts across Budapest, broadening citizen involvement and data collection efforts. The platform also has potential for integration into participatory budgeting frameworks, allowing residents to play a more active role in allocating resources for local

improvements. These efforts align closely with the UP2030 goals of enhancing citizen engagement, promoting climate resilience, and driving sustainable urban transformation.

Figure 66: Screenshot of Budapest project used in Presentation of Community Maps at Budapest’s Healthy Streets Conference

10 TSPA

TSPA (Thomas Stellmach Planning and Architecture) is an international urban planning and design firm that develops sustainable urban systems for a changing world. They have delivered projects ranging from regional development to urban planning - from neighbourhood design to place-making. Their team is composed of planners, designers, urbanists, data, and communication experts. Besides their work with German cities, TSPA have realised projects on four continents, drawing upon global experience to find innovative solutions for each context, be it abroad or at home.

Partner Website: <https://tspa.eu/en>

10.1 City Scan

City Scan is a workflow built around a parametric design and creative explorations that enables the generation and evaluation of urban design scenarios. By integrating computational methods with urban planning and design expertise, the tool provides a holistic approach to shaping and understanding urban spaces. It facilitates consideration of a wide range of factors by systematically analysing their interdependencies to create data-driven insights. This integrated approach ensures that urban design solutions are both visionary and practical, addressing environmental and social challenges while being tailored to the unique needs and opportunities of each specific context.

The City Scan employs a step-by-step approach to create and assess urban environments, focusing on indicators such as walkability, density, solar energy potential, and carbon sequestration, among others. These indicators can be customized based on the requirements of each project. The tool allows for the iterative exploration of different scenarios, making it possible to assess and compare their potential impacts in a systematic way.

Due to its data analysis and visualization capabilities, City Scan can visualize complex urban systems and their interrelations. For instance, it can show how building typologies and spatial layout influence energy efficiency and solar exposure. These analyses help to balance different priorities, such as green space allocation versus building height or land use efficiency versus social inclusivity.

A key feature of the City Scan is the possibility to involve stakeholders in the design process through rapid scenario iterations. This feature enables near-real-time exploration of trade-offs, such as the impact of building density on land occupancy. By visualizing these trade-offs clearly and early, the tool facilitates informed discussions and collaborative decision-making and supports the creation of urban design solutions that reflect the needs of residents and stakeholders. It provides a structured framework for evaluating urban design scenarios, helping to identify solutions that are well-informed, context-sensitive, and balanced across environmental, social, and spatial factors.

City Scan does not offer a standardized solution. It is adapted for each specific context. For example, in the Granollers pilot project within the UP2030 initiative, the tool has been customized to address the specific challenges and opportunities of the La Bòbila district, but its outcomes are aimed at informing city wide processes for new development areas. This customization ensures that its outputs are relevant and practical for the local context and is further described in Section 2.

Costs: Funding required

10.1.1 Software Requirements

City Scan is built in the Grasshopper environment within Rhinoceros 3D, which requires:

- A licensed copy of Rhinoceros 3D (commercial, approx. €1000), available at <https://www.rhino3d.com/buy/>

- Grasshopper (comes with Rhino, no additional cost)
- A suite of free, open-source plugins: Ladybug Tools (Ladybug, Honeybee, Dragonfly), Decoding Spaces, Pufferfish, Kangaroo, Human, Clipper, Fennec.

10.1.2 Data Requirements

City Scan requires two types of data. For analysis of the area: spatial data inputs typically in vector formats (e.g., .shp, .geojson) and tabular data (.csv, Excel) for parameter inputs. Core datasets include:

- Urban form: building footprints, heights, street network, protected (preservation) areas
- Demographics: population density, socio-economic indicators
- Climate data: solar irradiation, temperature, carbon emissions (ideally spatialized), climate risk hazard areas, such as flooding zones, etc.
- Land use and zoning
- Optional: energy demand and consumption, vegetation cover.

Data can be collected via GIS platforms, municipal databases, or remote sensing.

10.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Using City Scan requires intermediate to advanced knowledge in:

- Parametric modelling with Grasshopper
- Urban planning and spatial analysis
- Understanding of climate and sustainability indicators
- Basic GIS and data preprocessing skills.

Training may be required for new users – the training might take from 1-3 days.

Otherwise, TSPA offers a service to operate the tool. These services are paid, offered as a package, for using the tool. The pricing depends on the complexity of the site, thus it is flexible. The support is provided throughout the entire period of contract, until the final delivery of the outputs.

10.1.4 9.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

Several barriers might prevent the use of the software:

- Software Costs: Rhinoceros license is not free
- Technical complexity: requires specific skills in Grasshopper and urban analysis
- Data availability: limited or poor-quality spatial or climate data can hinder usage
- Time: understanding the logic behind the script, set up and data preparation can be time-intensive
- Interface: it is built within Grasshopper and Rhino 3D interface, which interface is not new-user friendly, therefore operating the tool might be complex (to mitigate this TSPA offers their expertise operating the tool, until the further funding can be secured to develop more user-friendly interface)
- Stakeholder engagement: live co-creation sessions may need facilitation and preparation.

10.1.5 Tool Use Context

City Scan is designed to support small, medium- to large-sized cities (focusing on neighbourhoods).

- Scale: neighbourhood, district, or city-wide scale
- Sectors: urban planning, energy, climate adaptation, mobility
- Users: municipal planning departments, developers, NGOs, researchers, urban planning practitioners
- Purpose: building urban design scenarios and their testing, stakeholder engagement, visualizing environmental impact of different urban forms, optimizing urban layouts.

10.1.6 Tool Limitations

Not plug-and-play:

- Requires some setup and contextualisation for each new application

Data-driven but not real-time:

- Insights are generated based on static input datasets
- Interpretation and application of outputs still depend on expert review and contextual knowledge

Technical:

- No possibility to integrate topography of the area
- Limited number of available building typologies
- Can only generate flat roofs – which might have different effects on solar radiation, cooling.

10.1.7 City Journey

City Scan is suitable for use throughout the urban transformation journey:

- At start of the project: Developing urban design concept/scenarios for empty lots within city
- Through development cycles: Urban design scenario exploration, urban form and its environmental performance exploration
- Stakeholder engagement to involve key stakeholders in design process, discuss and present trade-offs (such as urban density, green areas, mobility infrastructure etc.)
- Guiding planning decisions based on quantified trade-offs
- To align urban design concepts and plans with city climate goals

10.1.8 Step-by-Step guide

Figure 67: City Scan process flow diagram

10.1.9 Case Study

Data-driven urban design scenarios and their assessment for climate-neutral neighbourhood design guidelines

Tool Name: City Scan — Parametric urban design & assessment tool

City and District/Neighbourhood: Granollers (Spain) — La Bòbila sector

Organisations: Actors involved

- City of Granollers (Ajuntament de Granollers)
- Aquatec (city liaison in UP2030)
- Community/institutional stakeholders participating in workshops: political representatives, citizen associations, vulnerable community groups representatives

Case Study Context

Granollers is a medium-sized city, with population of around 61 000 inhabitants, located in northeast of Barcelona. Within UP2030 project, for its pilot area, the city chose the undeveloped area, located east to the railway and main train station – Sector 129 La Bòbila. The city is focusing to turning new urban developments into low-carbon neighbourhoods via drafting new urban planning guidelines.

Granollers focuses on developing a set of urban design guidelines for low-carbon, resilient, and inclusive districts. As a first step, the city aimed to prototype in La Bòbila district and replicate the approach across other areas by 2030 by drafting the guidelines. To achieve this, Granollers needed a way to test different spatial strategies, quantify trade-offs, and base decisions on measurable data.

City Scan offered an opportunity to generate different urban design scenarios and assessing them through comparable indicators such as density, energy use, solar potential, carbon sequestration, and walkability. This process allowed to quantify trade-offs and to assess different design choices to inform planning guidelines.

Issues facing the city

Granollers identified several challenges in its transition toward becoming a more inclusive, resilient, and climate-neutral city. At the governance level, the city faced fragmentation across departments and a lack of a systemic approach to planning and implementation. The need for stronger and more inclusive engagement was another key issue. Technical challenges also emerged, particularly around data management, sharing, and cross-analysis. Finally, the needs analysis conducted at the beginning of the project highlighted several spatial and sectoral challenges: insufficient multi-functional green spaces, mobility patterns dominated by private vehicles, limited accessibility due to topography, and increasing pressure on housing affordability.

Applying your Tool to the Case Study

The desk research, which incorporated stakeholders' inputs gathered through various workshops held between 2023 and 2024, provided a deeper understanding of priorities and was instrumental in

defining the parameters for the project. The key documents shared by the city administration which have been considered in this process included:

- Urban Master Plan of Granollers.
- Master Plan Information Sheet for the Urban Planning Sector.
- Granollers Housing Plan.
- Land Regulation of the Urban Master Plan: detailing zoning for Sector 129 La Bòbila.
- Pla Mobilitat Urbana Sostenible SUMP.
- Green Urban Master Plan.
- SECAP.

These documents offered essential insights into local priorities, regulations, and urban dynamics. This information was integrated with best practices in urban design to directly shape the development of key project parameters, which were organized into six thematic categories:

- Mobility Network
- Green & Blue Infrastructure
- Functions & Services
- Building Typologies
- Socio-Economic Factors
- Urban Morphology & Regulations

In parallel, **geospatial analysis** was conducted to evaluate the current conditions and identify emerging spatial synergies. This analysis connected the pilot area with the broader city context and provided foundational data for the parametric design tool. Key aspects examined during this stage included:

- The distribution of services
- Mobility connectivity
- Surrounding green areas
- Land surface temperature

Detailing the process of collaborating with the city

Figure 68: Diagram presenting the process steps

Analysis and digital environment

The City Scan application in Granollers followed a structured, iterative process combining insights gained during the vision co-creation process, spatial data modelling and participation.

After initial assessment of relevant documents and pilot objectives, the detailed 3D digital environment was created, incorporating:

- Existing street networks, buildings, and land uses
- Environmental elements such as water bodies and topography
- Relevant spatial constraints (heritage, flood zones, green corridors)

This base model was connected to analysis scripts in Grasshopper, enabling parametric control over densities, typologies, and land-use distributions.

Define Scenario Axes and Key Priorities

In collaboration with the city and selected stakeholders, TSPA defined a scenario matrix structured around two main axes:

- Nature ↔ People, and
- Moderate ↔ Transformative levels of intervention.

The findings from the analysis phase guided the development of urban design scenarios, each representing a distinct set of development priorities. These conceptual schemes were crafted to explore how high-level ideas could be integrated with design options, allowing for a comparative evaluation of their performance, advantages and disadvantages. By testing different urban design configurations, the scenarios provided a framework for understanding the trade-offs between competing priorities and their implications for the project's objectives.

Figure 69: Scenario matrix diagram, representing how axis were defined

Diagrams represent the grouping of pilot project objectives and how they informed scenario matrix. On the left is the cluster of objectives, that represents 'nature' axis and priorities related to environmental protection. On the right – a cluster of objectives representing 'people' axis and priorities related to social inclusion and economic development.

Design Charrette and Scenario Generation

One of the key steps in the process was a design charrette (a workshop format, where expert workshop in planning ideas and solutions. The goal is to bring together various perspectives to find solutions and create initial spatial layouts), which allowed for the creative exploration of options and the development of visionary ideas. These options are then submitted to critical rational judgment, assessing which of these can provide a feasible way forward within the project requirements.

During this phase, several internal sessions – within the TSPA team – were conducted to brainstorm and sketch potential spatial configurations for each scenario. By breaking the area into thematic layers (such as mobility, density, green and blue infrastructure and more) and creating conceptual diagrams, the workshops helped translate the overarching scenario concepts into spatial options.

Throughout multiple sessions, the spatial scenarios were refined, identifying critical spatial relationships between building typologies, mobility networks, green spaces, density, and the specific priorities of each scenario. This process enabled a comprehensive understanding of how each scenario could be represented spatially.

The outcomes of the charrette formed a foundational step for moving forward. The refined sketches and diagrams were digitized, serving as the basis for the following development of a detailed digital model.

Each alternative configuration included:

- Street networks, urban blocks, parcels, sidewalks, bike lines, public and green spaces
- Building volumes with different typologies and heights
- Building functions
- NBS: bio-swales, green-roofs, solar panels
- Final step: refining and optimising spatial forms (removing unrealistic geometries, adjusting building sizes, etc)

Figure 70: Example of axonometric view of building heights distribution of NM scenario

Integrate Environmental and Geographical Data

Environmental datasets (e.g. solar radiation, sun hours per year, average temperature) were linked to the 3D model. These inputs enabled City Scan to simulate solar gain, shading, and sky-view factors, supporting passive design and comfort analysis.

Run Spatial and Environmental Assessments

Each scenario was quantitatively evaluated through two parallel assessments:

- Spatial statistics: site density, street length, bicycle paths, green-space ratios, and trees per person, permeable surfaces ratio, etc.
- Environmental statistics: carbon sequestration, energy demand, and solar-energy production, etc.

Outputs were exported into spreadsheets and visualised through dashboards and diagrams for comparison.

Figure 71: Cooling analysis example

Figure 72: Electric Equipment analysis example

Figure 73: Heating analysis example

Figure 74: Lighting analysis example

Visualisation and Output

The process concluded with the production of spatial models, 2D plans, 3D diagrams, and quantitative statistics, providing a consistent and comparable evidence base.

These results formed the basis for Granollers' Urban Climate Planning Guide – A Greener City with Opportunities for Everyone, translating scenario insights into recommendations for low-carbon, inclusive neighbourhoods.

Development/changes to the tool

The development of the tool began with a highly specified codebase that proved to be unstable. This led to a complete rewrite of the algorithm from the ground up. During this process, an entire suite of new design features was developed, for adaptable future use, but tailored to the context of Granollers. These features were informed by parameters derived from the vision and adaptive pathways workshops conducted with representatives from Granollers.

The development process involved rigorous testing of new components and regular presentations to the Granollers team to gather feedback and establish priorities. This iterative cycle of feedback and refinement ensured that the tool met client expectations and addressed real-world needs. Additionally, a comprehensive suite of analytical components was developed to enhance the tool's capabilities and provide actionable insights for urban design.

Outcomes of Tool Use

City Scan delivered a report with a detail explanation of each scenario, and comparisons across four scenarios, revealing trade-offs between density, public/green space, street allocation, energy demand, solar generation, and sequestration (with dashboards/plots and side-by-side scenario charts). Each scenario is presented with 3D and 2D diagrams and plans, and data sheets.

Some examples from the comparative analysis are:

- Built-up area spans from ~160,000 m² (NM) to 331,000 m² (PT), showing the capacity and energy implications to different land coverage scenarios.
- Energy demand and solar production charts clarify how higher density and green roofs can shift the balance toward on-site generation but increase cooling loads if shading/orientation aren't managed.
- Public-space comfort insights from direct sun and sky-view factor analyses fed design moves like shading and tree planting in more exposed and larger public spaces/streets.

Statistical Measures	People Oriented - Moderate Scenario	People Oriented - Transformative Scenario	Nature Oriented - Transformative Scenario	Nature Oriented - Moderate Scenario
Site Area (m ²)	463,903.80	463,903.80	463,903.80	463,903.80
Site Floor Area Ratio (FAR)	0.79	0.88	0.57	0.41
Average Block Floor Area Ratio (FAR)	2.50	1.99	2.25	2.07
Built-up Area (m ²)	255,405.30	331,088.60	212,780.60	160,133.40
Total Building Footprint (m ²)	70,892.20	85,222.60	69,941.10	37,887.80
Green Roof Ratio	n/a	0.00	0.60	0.75
Green Roof Area (m ²)	0.00	0.00	41,964.66	28,415.85
Solar Panel Area (m ²)	0.00	46,345.23	13,221.09	6,116.85
Total Built Floor Area (m ²)	367,694.70	407,930.80	263,008.70	190,398.20
Average Building Height (m)	13.00	12.20	12.60	11.00
Tallest Building (m)	28.00	19.00	25.00	16.00
Approx. no. Residential Units	1,794.00	2,684.00	1,668.00	1,082.00
Approx. no. Residents	4,484.00	6,711.00	4,169.00	2,705.00
Total Saleable Residential Floor Area (m ²)	177,754.60	266,012.00	165,274.10	107,225.50
Total Residential Floor Area (m ²)	209,123.10	312,955.30	194,440.20	126,147.60
% Residential Space	56.90	76.90	73.90	66.30
Total Social/Public Floor Area (m ²)	7,020.70	1,588.40	2,017.80	2,048.80
Social/Public Space Per Capita	1.57	0.24	0.48	0.76
% Social/Public Space	1.90	0.40	0.80	1.10
Total Retail Floor Area (m ²)	70,832.50	61,320.60	50,874.70	41,649.00
Retail Space Per Capita	15.80	9.14	12.20	15.40
% Retail Space	19.30	15.10	19.30	21.90
Total Office Floor Area (m ²)	80,718.50	31,066.60	15,676.00	20,552.80
% Office Space	22.00	7.60	6.00	10.80
Approx. no. of Office Workspaces	5,381.00	2,071.00	1,045.00	1,370.00
Office Space per Capita	18.00	4.63	3.76	7.60
Total Street Surface Area (m ²)	52,713.20	64,429.90	38,958.80	39,526.30
Total Bike Lane Area (m ²)	22,555.00	27,480.10	30,618.50	12,190.70

Figure 75: Section of the data sheet for each scenario metrics

Figure 76: Comparison of energy demand (in kWh) among all four scenarios. The diagram represents difference of energy demands related to different urban form (e.g. density, spatial configuration), revealing which urban design choice might be more suitable in the

Lessons learned

- Rapid iteration as a part of the design process: City Scan provides a structured way to explore and concurrently analyse different design scenarios by adjusting variables such as density, land use, and green space allocation. It enables stakeholders to understand the impacts of these changes on metrics like energy demand, mobility efficiency, and environmental performance. The tool supports iterative design processes by allowing quick adjustments and evaluations, offering a robust foundation for exploring urban transformation pathways.
- Visually compelling qualitative and quantitative data: The City Scan tool provides rapid visualizations for comparing scenarios, enabling stakeholders to make informed decisions based on clear, evidence-driven insights. The visualizations also spatialize the data in a way that is difficult to understand in tabular or aggregated graph formats.
- Co-design as a part of technical development: The process of developing a tool for urban design requires a deep understanding of what stakeholders involved in the process need. This is difficult to do in a vacuum. In line with the UP2030 principles of co-design, City Scan’s development was greatly enriched by the co-creative process with the City of Granollers. The direction for development was largely steered by the needs of the city within the framework of their objectives within the project. This gave us the opportunity to hear what the priorities

and needs were and allowed us to test new developments of the tool with a specific case and receive feedback and validation from the city's representatives.

- **Adaptability to diverse contexts:** During the process of the development, the tool was developed in a modular structure, what makes easy to adapt it to other urban contexts and scales. This adaptability enhances its utility as a resource for cities facing varied challenges and planning objectives or for continuing to work with Granollers pilot and detail the conceptual design even further.
- **Metrics and Trade-off between them to Evaluate Urban Form Performance:** One of the main focuses of the tool development was the ability to provide quantitative metrics to assess resilience, carbon neutrality, connectivity, and density parameters of each urban design. However, each of these parameters presents certain theoretical and practical trade-offs between them and interrelates in ways that were not possible to analyse in depth due to the tool's ongoing development and the project's timeline constraints. This limitation prevented a more comprehensive evaluation of how these factors interact and influence one another in the context of net-zero neighbourhood design.
- **Integration of qualitative and socially oriented goals:** While City Scan has been built around integration of parameters and the production of data as a core aspect of the design process, integrating goals which are more intangible proved to be more difficult. Correlating objectives such as affordable housing, socio-economic and cultural diversity, and prevention of gentrification with spatial and built-form parameters was difficult to do. Going forward, there is a need for greater study of the correlation of such social indicators with their respective implications on the environment.
- **Technical Development Time:** Significant technical development was required to refine the City Scan tool, which posed challenges given the concurrent need to develop content and meet tight project timelines. Balancing these demands required careful coordination and prioritisation.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** One of the biggest tool's potentials lies in its ability to generate the scenarios in real time during stakeholder meetings allowing for the live visualization of needs and trade-offs between different design options. However, due to the tool's ongoing technical development and the timeline of the UP2030 project, this feature was not directly implemented in Granollers. Instead, the scenarios were presented and evaluated with key stakeholders through the Adaptive Pathway meeting (April 2024), interviews with technical representatives from the City Council (May 2024), and the Action Workshop (October 2024).

The role of the tool in supporting improved decision making

City Scan supported improved decision-making by providing a data-driven, spatially explicit framework for testing and comparing urban design scenarios. It allowed Granollers to visualize how different design choices would impact KPIs such as density, energy demand, solar potential, carbon sequestration, walkability, and green space distribution.

By quantifying trade-offs between environmental and spatial goals, the tool enabled the city to move from intuition-based planning toward evidence-based, transparent, and comparable decision-making. It helped align design strategies with carbon neutrality, resilience, and inclusion objectives, ensuring that future guidelines and policies are grounded in measurable outcomes rather than assumptions.

Looking Towards the Future

The current version of City Scan delivered a complete and consistent evaluation package for Granollers - a defined set of spatial, environmental, and energy indicators that informed the design of the Urban Design Guidelines for Low-Carbon Neighbourhoods. These guidelines, now finalised, translate the tool's analytical outputs to inform spatial principles and targets.

In the future, City Scan could be applied to assess new urban plans in Granollers, testing their alignment with the guidelines and broader climate-neutrality goals.

Beyond UP2030, there is an opportunity to conduct additional pilot studies to refine the workflow based on real-world use and user feedback. Further development could focus on expanding data-visualisation dashboards, adding new analytical scripts (e.g., environmental comfort, integration with topography), and enhancing the front-end interface to enable live operation and clearer communication of results. Strengthening the link between 3D modelling, statistical outputs, and environmental analysis will further improve the tool's accuracy and usability for municipalities and designers alike.

11 UCCRN

The Urban Climate Change Research Network (UCCRN) is a global consortium of over 1,200 individuals from over 150 cities dedicated to the analysis of climate change mitigation and adaptation from an urban perspective. UCCRN members are scholars and experts from universities and research organizations around the world. They span a broad range of expertise including climate scientists; urban heat island and air quality experts; climate change impact scientists; social scientists, including economists, political scientists, and sociologists; and urban designers and planners.

Partner Website: <https://uccrn.ei.columbia.edu/about-us>

11.1 UDCW Methodology

UCCRN Urban Design Climate Workshops (UDCWs) aim to integrate and scale-up climate change mitigation and adaptation in cities through knowledge sharing, collaboration, and action planning. Innovative aspects of the UDCW methodology can be recognized in:

1. Provision of a set of designer/planner friendly interoperable tools that are able to assess the climate benefits of different planning and design strategies at different scales both in terms of comfort quantitative indicators and quanti/qualitative co-benefits indicators starting from few input parameters (urban morphology, climate data, land uses, etc.).
2. Understanding of the relation between socio-spatial justice and climate justice providing tools that can spatialize community needs that are often not directly climate related, matching them with climate-resilient design opportunities.
3. Integration of quantitative and qualitative analysis. The management of different types of data in the same working environment is a value proposition related to the potentiality of streamlining the design and planning process basing on the assessment of social, economic, and environmental co-benefits associated with climate-resilient development strategies and on the survey of community-based assets.

The methodology is oriented to foster processes of co-design and co-production generating a collaborative environment in which the dialogue between different stakeholders can facilitate the adoption of design and planning solutions desirable for the multiple actors engaged.

Cost: No funding required

11.1.1 Software Requirements

The tool is a guideline, it can be implemented by using UDCW simulation and facilitation toolkits.

11.1.2 Data Requirements

The tool is a guideline, it can be implemented by using UDCW simulation and facilitation toolkits.

11.1.3 Expertise Requirements

The UDCW methodology can be applied by professionals with a background in architecture, urban planning, or design. It involves the use of UDCW simulation and facilitation toolkits, which require specific expertise.

11.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

A key barrier is that the UDCW methodology can only be implemented by specialized experts. While it can serve as guidance for public officials and practitioners, expertise in architecture and planning is essential.

11.1.5 Tool Use Context

The UDCW was first formalized in the Urban Planning and Urban Design chapter of the Second Assessment Report on Climate Change and Cities (ARC3.2) (Raven et al., 2018), and further advanced in the forthcoming Third Assessment Report (ARC3.3) (Raven et al., 2025). ARC3.3 expands on this foundation by presenting applied research, pilot projects, and tested models that demonstrate how urban systems and the built environment can be reimagined to support integrated mitigation and adaptation strategies and local community needs. Grounded in urban climate science and community engagement, from 2015 the UDCW methodology has been tested through case studies in cities on a global scale such as Napoli, Paris, Durban, New York, Barcelona within several research, educational and institutional initiatives.

11.1.6 Tool Limitations

The implementation of the methodology has been evaluated only under UCCRN expert guidance.

11.1.7 City Journey

The scope of the tool is to provide multi-scale and urban planning and design guidance from strategic/conceptual level to master planning and neighbourhood scale design.

The methodology helps to align climate goals with local stakeholders and community needs and priorities, connecting carbon neutrality, adaptation, and environmental justice goals. The UDCW methodology includes a 4-step iterative process supported by specify tools (see UDCW Simulation toolkit and UDCW Facilitation toolkit), providing a fully quantitative and spatialized analysis of climate benefits of co-designed planning/design scenarios in relation to climate projections downscaled to the urban climate and other socio-economic and environmental co-benefits.

The tool is intended to be used by technical planning department in cities and planning/design practitioners.

11.2 UDCW Simulation Toolkit

Climate resilient development in cities requires integration of mitigation and adaptation measures across spatial scales. The UDCW simulation toolkit consists in set of IT tools (GIS and 3D Modelling Algorithm Aided Design tools) for heat waves and flood hazard/impact modelling considering urban microclimate effect (morphology, land use and cover, building features, etc.), including user guidance. It allows the user to perform analyses at city (2D) and neighbourhood (3D) scales based on climate projection information.

Testing of the effectiveness of alternative strategies at a conceptual stage of the plan/project - through a set of interoperable tools embedded into common planning and design software (GIS and 3D modelling tools) which are integrated with simulation modules supporting the assessment of climate benefits from different planning and design strategies at different scales through few input parameters (climate data, urban morphology, land cover, construction typologies, etc.) - is also possible.

Cost: No funding required

11.2.1 Software Requirements

The UDCW Simulation Toolkit is an on-demand service-based tool, and users can deliver city plans and architectural drawing through any kind of software. The recommended software are Q-GIS for the 2D city plans and Rhinoceros (McNeel) for 3D models. Detailed user guides providing tips to provide simple drawings and models based on data requirement taxonomy are provided, including video tutorials.

Any GIS software tool (only for input data collection to be transferred as .shp or .gpkg files). The designs and models that are produced in GIS and 3D environments will be used as input for simulation tools. These tools will generate maps for the assessment of climate and energy drivers at different scales.

GIS tools:

- CPU: Intel Core i7/AMD Ryzen 7 (recommended)
- CPU Memory: 2.7 Ghz or more (recommended)
- RAM: 2 Gb (min); 8 Gb or More (recommended)
- Hard Disk: SSD 128 Gb or 500 Gb SATA (recommended)
- GPU memory: 1 Gb RAM (min)
- Operating System: Windows 8 64Bit or more macOS High Sierra (10.13) or more, Linux, BSD

3D modelling/ Algorithm Aided Design (AAD) tools:

- CPU: intel Core i7/AMD Ryzen 7 (recommended)
- CPU Memory: 2.7 Ghz or more (recommended)
- RAM: 16 GB or more (recommended)
- GPU: NVIDIA/AMD Radeon; Open GL4.1 capable (recommended)
- GPU memory: 4 GB or more (recommended)
- HDD/SSD memory required: 1 GB minimum

Operating System: Windows 8 64Bit or more

Hardware requirements: Several computers with high operating power and memory

11.2.2 Data Requirements

End users are required to transfer to UCCRN experts a series of GIS files (shp, geopackage) including all the input data needed to run the simulation model, according to the taxonomy and attributes listed in UCCRN's data table (See: Appendix 2; D3.6).

With regard to the Input data, UDCW simulation toolkit require different information according to the scale and the tool to be used.

- GIS tools
- Data Types: 2D drawing of the area (.shp, gpkg format), climate data (air temperature, solar radiation and position, rain amount in CSV or Excel format); land use (building, open spaces, vegetation features in raster format: .tiff, .asc, etc); population distribution (number of people, age of people in ESRI Shapefile format)
- 3D modelling/AAD tools

- Data Types: district scale 3D models (in .3dm format), land use, building features (construction, Window to Wall Ratio, Hvac, etc in .csv, excel, .shp format or as Rhino attributes), open space features (trees, surfaces thermal properties, etc in .csv, excel, .shp format or as Rhino attributes); climate data (in.epw format)

The tools allow to introduce as input specific climate change projections, based on IPCC RCPs/SSPs (Representative Concentration Pathways/ Shared Socioeconomic Pathways) for different future timeframes. The data include both annual averages (targeting e.g. building energy consumption) and extreme events (heat waves and extreme precipitation). The toolkit allows to manage different types of data in the same working environment, streamlining both the design process and the assessment of climate-resilient development strategies, delivering the following output based on specific planning and design solutions:

Thermal comfort analysis

- Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT) [°C]
- Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) [°C]
- Indoor Predicted Mean Vote (PMV)
- Hospitalization costs due to heatwaves [€]
- Mortality rate increase [%] (beta)

Flood analysis

- Run-off [-]
- Flood probability index [-]
- Building damage (structure/content) [€]
- Road infrastructure damage (cleaning/repairing) [€]

Energy analysis

- Building Energy Use Intensity [kWh/m²y]
- Renewable energy production potential [kWh/y]

Carbon analysis

- Carbon Footprint of Building Materials [tCO₂/y]
- Carbon storage potential from vegetation [tCO₂/y]

As for the GIS Tools, all the output data are provided through .shp, .gpkg, .geoTIFF, geoJSON and raster .png formats.

In the case of 3D AAD tools, the output data consists in 3D maps and graphs provided in .png format and in projected climate data in .epw format.

11.2.3 Expertise Requirements

UDCW simulation tools are particularly specialised computational tools. For this reason, their standalone use requires an adequate technical and IT background to be used correctly. Basic knowledge of GIS software to handle the data collection and transfer is also required.

11.2.4 Potential Barriers to Use

To reduce barriers that could prevent this tool from being used, the tools are offered as a service, only requiring users to prepare the files within GIS software environment, based on a guide provided by UCCRN. UDCW simulations are generally provided as a service by UCCRN EU team, based on specific end-user requirements and user-tailored workflows. However, a lack of the above expertise could prevent the tools from being correctly utilised.

11.2.5 Tool Use Context

The scope of the tool is to provide multi-scale and urban planning and design guidance from strategic/conceptual level to master planning and neighbourhood scale design. Supported by specific IT tools, GIS and 3D AAD, the UDCW Simulation Toolkit provides a fully quantitative and spatialized analysis of climate benefits of planning/design scenario in relation to climate projections downscaled to the urban climate.

The tool provides support for decision-making processes to consider urban climate design principles in city planning, urban and building/open space design and perform robust climate hazard/impact and mitigation/adaptation assessments based on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) AR6 and EU Taxonomy/DNSH approaches.

GIS and 3D modelling tools are widely used by designers and planners. Moreover, the implementation of AAD tools allows for an effective and rapid interaction among the software environments, fostering the multi-scale approach proposed. For this reason, the tool is specifically intended to be used by technical planning departments in cities and planning/design practitioners.

11.2.6 Tool Limitations

The toolkit includes a set of climate projections, information and data about temperature and precipitation, including annual averages (through Energy Plus Weather - EPW files, globally) and extreme events (only for EU cities). Limitations might be related to the availability of EPW files for the city. Both annual averages and extreme events data can be provided by users if available.

11.2.7 City Journey

The models included in the UDCW Simulation Toolkit are based on the elaboration of climate projections downscaled to include urban microclimate conditions and simulate the impacts of heat waves on population (mortality rate increase, hospitalization, including economic direct and indirect impacts) and the effect of seasonal temperature trends variation on energy demand for building heating/cooling, and impacts of floods on buildings and open spaces (direct and indirect damage to structure and content).

The tools can measure the climate benefits in terms of adaptation and mitigation measures through fully quantitative indicators, also including assessments of social, economic and environmental co-benefits associated to climate resilient development strategies.

The UDCW Simulation Toolkit can be used throughout the entire project cycle, but it is particularly recommended at the strategic city planning level and the early conceptual stages of an urban/building design project, to make sure that targeted decarbonization and climate adaptation goals are measured through robust quantitative indicators.

11.3 UDCW Facilitation Toolkit

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools that allow to engage different typologies of city actors (experts: decision makers, city officials, planning/design practitioners; and non-experts: third sector and citizens) in a co-created climate resilient design process.

Cities can benefit from the toolkit to trigger knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context. The tools facilitate communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridge complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge.

The tools are conceived to foster the dialogue between experts and non-expert and to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens and as well with capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers.

The main objective is to create structured interactions with institutions, practitioners and civil society, leveraging a collective learning about climate-related issues and possible solutions.

The toolkit helps in contextualizing design solutions by establishing local priorities according to real needs and opportunities of a specific territory. When used in synergy with the UDCW Simulation toolkit, bottom-up data can be integrated to quantitative modelling of climate change impacts (heat and flood) and the assessment of mitigation/adaptation benefits and social, economic and environmental co-benefits of climate-resilient planning/design solutions.

The toolkit includes:

- Collaborative mapping through analogic (boards/stickers) or digital (P-GIS Participatory Geographic Information System) tools (Collaborative mapping with experts and non-experts)
- City visions and local needs matching (Priority mapping/co-design exercise with non-experts)
- A Day in the life (Visioning exercise with experts and non-experts)
- 3D neighbourhood configurator tool (co-design exercise with experts)

Cost: No funding required

11.3.1 Software Requirements

No specific software is required for the tools 2 and 3 of the toolkit (2. City visions and local needs matching; 3. A Day in the life).

For tool 1 (Collaborative mapping) if there is a need to offer digitalizing results a digital software for mapping is required (e.g. Open Street Maps, Google Maps) and additionally QGIS to deliver P-GIS outcomes.

For tool 4 (3D neighbourhood configurator tool) the recommended software is Rhinoceros (McNeel, Version 6 or higher) for the configurator usage.

All the tools need to be used through workshops.

11.3.2 Data Requirements

Tool 1: Data are required for Collaborative Mapping to create baseline maps. Different kinds of information can be included in the baseline maps such as public services and facilities; transports; urban functions; historical and cultural landmarks; population; land use; building typologies; other typologies depending on data produced by researchers or cities.

These data are optional, as the mapping can be done as well just using satellite imagery data sources. Data Format for baseline maps: KML/KMZ; txt.; ESRI Shapefile; DBF or CSV; raster images (.tiff; .jpeg; .png).

Tool 2: City visions and local needs matching)

Tool 3: A Day in the life can be tailored according to case objectives. They need thick data regarding the characteristics of the urban and social fabric of the neighbourhood, daily life experiences and knowledge about social groups or use of urban spaces. Often, they are surveyed through collaborative mapping or in specific focus groups.

Tool 4: 3D Building Configurator: all the input data needed to run the simulation model, according to the taxonomy and attributes listed in UCCRN's data table (See: Appendix 2; D3.6; cfr. UDCW Simulation Toolkit).

11.3.3 Expertise Requirements

Facilitation skills are required to guide the interactions between a diversity of participants to the co-design and co-production activities in a workshop environment. Previous engagement with city actors or local communities would be an advantage to structure the use of tools and tailor them appropriately to the context. Preparatory meetings with local key contacts are also advised. The toolkit is flexible as it contains different typologies of exercises, and it can be customized by the expertise of the facilitators and typology of target audience.

Knowledge about climate risks in urban areas and planning/architectural knowledge is highly recommended. Specifically for the 4 components of the toolkit experts' skills can be detailed as follows:

- Collaborative mapping: basic knowledge on usage of online tools for mapping recommendable and GIS expertise optional.
- City visions and local needs matching: basic knowledge on city models and design solutions (e.g. circular city, green and blue city, zero carbon city, 15 minutes city), visualization and graphic expertise advisable.
- A Day in the life: none.
- 3D Neighbourhood configurator tool: architectural 3D modelling recommendable (basic Grasshopper knowledge).

11.3.4 Potential Barriers to Use

A UCCRN expert (facilitator) to lead the activities is advisable or specific training for local experts should be developed for capacity building.

Engagement of a consistent number of participants for the workshops could be demanding for city administrative offices.

For the management of the outcomes from the collaborative mapping, a GIS background is required to integrate data from different sources (bottom-up information from communities or scientific data).

11.3.5 Tool Use Context

The toolkit has been developed to complement quantitative analysis for climate assessments with qualitative information and to better contextualize planning and design solutions according to the specificity of local issues and potentialities. The tools serve to survey thick data and no expert knowledge often overlooked in design and planning for urban resilience. The UDCW facilitation toolkit

can be used at city level in planning departments or by private firms for engagement processes, co-design and public consultations. In terms of city governance, it can contribute to participatory planning, inclusive spatial decision-making and collective learning. It can contribute to drive spatial justice outcomes at procedural and recognitional level.

11.3.6 Tool Limitations

The tool requires a preparatory phase aimed at engaging relevant stakeholders and community representatives that will be involved in the workshop activities. A limited number of engaged participants results in a limited quality of final outcomes. Inclusiveness and representativeness of different population groups need to be ensured during the whole process of the toolkit use.

11.3.7 City Journey

The UDCW facilitation toolkit can be used at different stages of a City's Journey as the variety of tools can be flexible depending on the purpose of their use. They are particularly effective for mapping priorities at start of a project and at the stage of the idea formulation (Tool 1,2,3,4). Collaborative mapping (1) can be also useful in the follow up of a project implementation to verify effects of the interventions or urban policies. A Day in the life (3) can support effectively the up-taking of everyday practices of sustainability through visioning and engagement.

11.3.9 Case Study 1

Downscaling the Sustainable Corridors

Tool Name: Urban Design Climate Workshop

City and District/Neighbourhood: Rio de Janeiro, São Cristóvão District

Organisations:

- UCCRN European Hub, UCCRN Latin American Hub, Pontificia Universidad Catolica de Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio), Fiocruz, New York Institute of Technology, Columbia University,
- Delft University of Technology
- City of Rio: (Prefeitura da Cidade do Rio de Janeiro, Rio Águas, Instituto Municipal de Urbanismo Pereira Passos, Relações Internacionais (International Relations Office), Escritório de Planejamento (Planning Office), Centro de Operações Rio-COR (Rio de Janeiro's Operational Control Centre, Secretaria Municipal de Meio Ambiente da Cidade-SMAC (Municipal Secretariat for the Environment).

Why a city wanted to use the tool:

Rio de Janeiro adopted the UDCW methodology to develop a climate-resilient 2050 urban scenario for the São Cristóvão district, employing advanced simulations to downscale its Sustainable Development and Climate Action Plan to the neighbourhood level and to detail Sustainable Corridors through climate-oriented design solutions. The city's choice was driven by established collaborations: UCCRN's Latin American Hub had already built strong partnerships with local authorities, universities, and research institutes, creating trust and readiness for joint experimentation. Additionally, the UDCW offered opportunities for strategic synergies, aligning with ongoing UCCRN initiatives in Rio, such as UCCRN_edu and expert meetings linked to the G20, enabling the city to connect local priorities with international networks and enhance its global resilience profile.

Description of case study area:

São Cristóvão is undergoing rapid urban transformation and was recently incorporated into the Porto Maravilha expansion area, making it a strategic site for testing climate-responsive design solutions. The neighbourhood combines dense urban development with recurrent climatic hazards, particularly flooding and extreme heat. Its vulnerability is heightened by its historical wetland origins and the progressive loss of ecological systems through centuries of drainage, landfilling, and infrastructure-driven urbanisation. The result is a densely built environment with limited green spaces and high surface temperatures. The neighbourhood's socio-spatial profile reflects these transformations. Formerly a royal seat and later an industrial hub, São Cristóvão now contains deindustrialised and underused spaces, uneven access to services, and several favelas that coexist with emerging redevelopment pressures. Major road corridors and transport infrastructures strengthen its role as a mobility node but also create physical barriers and urban voids that reduce cohesion and exacerbate exposure to heat.

Issues facing the city:

São Cristóvão reflects the broader structural challenges of Rio de Janeiro, shaped by governance limitations, environmental vulnerabilities, and development pressures. The district is regulated by overlapping planning instruments, including the City Masterplan and the Urban Structuring Project, which designate Areas of Special Interest for social inclusion, tourism, institutional use, and targeted urban restructuring. Despite this framework, speculative redevelopment—intensified by the 2024 expansion of the Porto Maravilha Urban Operation—places pressure on local economies, housing, and cultural traditions, highlighting gaps in integrated and implementable governance.

The district is also exposed to significant climate and environmental risks. Its dense urbanization over former wetlands has resulted in heat stress due to limited vegetation and extensive impervious surfaces, recurrent flooding exacerbated by an overburdened Canal do Mangue and loss of natural retention areas, and declining air and water quality from traffic congestion, aging infrastructure, and rising population density. While São Cristóvão contains important green and cultural assets such as Quinta da Boa Vista and the National Observatory, its ecological infrastructure is fragmented and insufficiently aligned with climate adaptation needs.

Collaborating with Rio de Janeiro

Phase 1 (2023 – early 2024): Knowledge Exchange and Capacity Building

The collaboration between UCCRN (technical partner), TU Delft (city liaison), and Rio's municipal departments began in May 2023 with the aim of offering technical support for climate-resilient urban development. Over time, this initial support evolved into a process of co-developing knowledge with the municipality, local partners. This shift enabled the adaptation of the UDCW to the city's priorities and laid the foundation for developing a climate-responsive prototype for São Cristóvão. The activities of this phase have been:

- Initial engagements between Rio City Hall, UCCRN European Hub and Latin American Hub, and TU Delft established synergies and defined how the UDCW could support municipal planning processes.
- An initial exploratory UDCW test in São Cristóvão, have been made through research and educational activities (Design Studio) by New York Institute of Technology and University of Naples Federico II (UCCRN partners) functioning as a *proof of concept* rather than a full prototype.
- In March–April 2024, two weeks of intensive activities brought together:
 - Round tables and expert sessions with UCCRN Regional Hubs (G20 side event)
 - A student urban design studio (PUC-Rio + New York Institute of Technology)
 - Meetings with municipal departments and community representatives
 - These sessions generated an early proposal for Sao Cristovao incorporating feedback from local authorities, community organisations (e.g., NOSSAS), and external experts (e.g., Deltares on flood risk).

In this phase the test of the UDCW methodology provided the following outcomes:

- Consolidation of a **science–policy–society interface** to address climate risks, socio-spatial inequalities, and environmental justice challenges.

- Validation of the **UDCW toolkit** as a suitable method to integrate climate data, GIS-based analysis, and co-design processes in a Global South context.
- Establishment of São Cristóvão as the **entry case** for more detailed design and prototyping in Phase 2.

Phase 2 (mid-2024 onwards): Prototype development

Building on Phase 1, Phase 2 applied the UDCW toolkit to produce a climate-responsive prototype for São Cristóvão. Using multi-scenario modelling (current state, business-as-usual, and best practice), the UCCRN team assessed heat risks and analysed socio-spatial vulnerabilities, service accessibility, mobility systems, and green-blue infrastructure gaps.

This process supported the downscaling of the city's Sustainability Corridors (Green, Blue, Brown, Orange) into actionable neighbourhood-level strategies. Three pilot areas were selected—Porto/Ex-Gasômetro, Rio Trapicheiros/Canal do Mangue, and a mixed-use redevelopment zone—where integrated interventions could address resilience, mobility, ecological restoration, and social inclusion. The resulting prototype outlines evidence-based spatial strategies that connect climate modelling with design interventions, supporting Rio's PDS through neighbourhood-scale actions. A set of policy recommendations complements the prototype, guiding reforms in governance, housing, ecological connectivity, and inclusive development. The activities of this phase have been:

- Bilateral meetings with city officers for data sharing and refinement in tool application (Instituto Municipal de Urbanismo Pereira Passos, Relações Internacionais (International Relations Office), Escritório de Planejamento (Planning Office), Centro de Operações Rio (Rio de Janeiro's Operational Control Centre, Secretaria Municipal de Meio Ambiente da Cidade (Municipal Secretariat for the Environment).
- Oct.2024-May 2025 synergies were established with the *Rio Climate Resilience* project and Climate Hub Rio (Columbia Global Centre, NASA-GISS, Columbia Climate School) for the full implementation of the UDCW in the Rio de Janeiro Prototype.
- Final Review of the prototype report by local stakeholders (on-going) and final round table about upscale opportunity foreseen for Dec. 2025.
- Nov. 2025 Presentation of the prototype results at COP30, IBAM Side Event "Cities Adaptation and Justice in Climate Emergency - Launch of the UCCRN Scientific Assessment Reports, ARC3.3 series: Justice for Resilient Cities and Urban Planning and Design for Climate Action", organized by PUC-RIO and UCCRN Latin America Hub.

Figure 78: Phasing of Prototype development and collaboration with the City

Integrating tool into local context:

The São Cristóvão district in Rio de Janeiro, currently undergoing extensive redevelopment—including the new Flamengo stadium, Porto Maravilha waterfront regeneration, a multimodal transport hub, and the transformation of Leopoldina station—provides an ideal testing ground for the Sustainable Corridors initiative. In response to stakeholder requests, scenario-based approaches have been adopted to ensure corridor designs align with local priorities and planned urban projects.

The UDCW addresses these needs by identifying climate risks and impacts specific to São Cristóvão, assessing design interventions that balance adaptation, mitigation, and socio-spatial justice, and prototyping solutions through simulations of heatwaves and energy demand. By facilitating co-design processes with stakeholders, the UDCW ensures that equity and accessibility are embedded in the downscaling of PDS corridors. Linking PDS objectives with locally grounded design strategies, the São Cristóvão pilot demonstrates the practical translation of a strategic urban instrument such as the Sustainable Corridors from vision to implementation, enhancing Rio’s capacity for climate-resilient urban transformation and providing a model for other cities in Brazil, Latin America, and beyond.

Examples of tool being used

The UDCW simulation tool has been used in particular for Multi-scale Scenario comparison (Current, Business as usual and Best Practice) through 3D parametric modelling. The following samples illustrate a focus area (Canal do Mangue) of the district in which microclimate assessment were performed: Current state; Business as usual; Best Practices with the simulation of climate-resilient interventions related to re-naturalisation of a former industrial site, creation of new public spaces pocket parks, social housing and community services.

More specifically, the UDCW simulation tools were used to calculate two KPIs related to outdoor thermal comfort: MRT and UTCI.

Area 2: Canal do Mangue

SCENARIO 1:
CURRENT STATE

- Canal do Mangue**
Waterway acting as a boundary between the districts of São Cristóvão and Santo Cristo.
- Ex industrial area**
Currently disused.
- Planned residential growth area**
Area related to Porto Maravilha project.

0m 100m 200m

COMFORT OUTDOOR SIMULATION

Epw: Copacabana_RJ_Brazil_2020
Simulation period: 16 November 2020
Time: 12:00 - 18:00

Air T: 32,8°C
Max T: 35,7°C
Wind speed: 1,58 m/s
Relative humidity: 55%
Mean T MRT: 45,1°C
Mean T UTCI: 36,9°C

Universal thermal comfort index (UTCI)

Mean radiant temperature (MRT)

Area 2: Canal do Mangue

SCENARIO 2:
BUSINESS AS USUAL

- New administrative area**
New administrative buildings for offices and services.
- New Flamengo stadium**
Development of new stadium and open spaces.
- Green corridor**

0m 100m 200m

COMFORT OUTDOOR SIMULATION

Epw: Copacabana_RJ_Brazil_SSP585_2050
Simulation period: 16 November 2050
Time: 12:00 - 18:00

Air T: 36,0°C
Max T: 42,8°C
Wind speed: 2,84 m/s
Relative humidity: 30%
Mean T UTCI: 41,5°C

Universal thermal comfort index (UTCI)

Mean radiant temperature (MRT)

Figure 79: Comfort outdoor simulations 3D Modelling: Current State and Business as Usual

Scenario comparison

Area 2: Canal do Mangue

Scenario comparison

Area 2: Canal do Mangue

Figure 80: Comfort outdoor simulations 3D Modelling: Best Practice

Challenges

The application of the UDCW tool to São Cristóvão faced multiple, interrelated challenges linked to the complexity of the area. A key difficulty was the comprehensive analysis of the site, encompassing climate risks, land use patterns, urban form, and the intricate policy framework governing the neighbourhood. Understanding recurrent flooding, heat stress, fragmented green spaces, and environmental pressures required detailed climate modelling and simulations to accurately capture local vulnerabilities (e.g. informal settlements). At the same time, mapping land use and assessing the implications of overlapping planning instruments—such as the City Masterplan (Plan Diretor), the

Urban Structuring Project (Projeto de Estruturação Urbana São Cristóvão PEU), and various Areas of Special Interest (Áreas de Especial Interesse Social - AEIs)—was essential to identify opportunities and constraints, helping to distinguish what strategies to prioritise and what interventions to avoid.

Operational challenges also arose in coordinating stakeholders, municipal authorities, and academic partners, requiring iterative sessions. Despite these difficulties, the systematic analysis of the area enabled the effective application of the tools, data collection and the translation of complex analyses into actionable scenarios.

Outcomes of Tool Use

The UDCW application in São Cristóvão delivered a comprehensive analytical package enabling scenario-based comparison and evidence-based design recommendations. The tool produced outputs across three development scenarios: Current State, Business-as-Usual (BAU), and Best Practice, providing a consistent and comparable evidence base for climate-resilient planning.

Scenario Modelling and Thermal Comfort Assessment

Microclimate simulations were performed at neighbourhood scale through 3D modelling AAD tools using two KPIs: Mean Radiant Temperature (MRT) and UTCI. The simulations were conducted over three pilot areas using a 5m × 5m resolution grid.

Current State simulation parameters:

- Air temperature: 38 °C (frequent/occasional heatwave events)
- Wind velocity: 1.5 m/s (minimal ventilation conditions)
- Relative humidity: 55%
- Simulation period: 16 November, 12:00–18:00 (minimal shading conditions)

BAU scenario parameters (RCP 8.5, 2050 projection):

- Projected air temperature: 39 °C (typical heatwaves), up to 42 °C (extreme events)
- Critical UTCI threshold exceedance: >46 °C observed in densified zones (Area 1, Leopoldina)

Current State analysis:

- High Tmrt and UTCI values in densely urbanised areas due to limited greenery and extensive soil sealing
- No substantial cooling effect adjacent to Canal do Mangue despite water body proximity
- Favourable microclimate conditions only in Quinta da Boa Vista park (vegetation effect) and coastal areas (sea breeze)
- Elevated thermal stress in Area 2 (Canal do Mangue) due to high heat absorption capacity of asphalt surfaces

BAU scenario (2050) analysis:

- Worsening heat stress in northern São Cristóvão due to urban densification strategy
- UTCI exceeding 46 °C threshold in Area 1 (Leopoldina) despite increased vegetation—indicating extreme heat stress conditions
- Localized Tmrt/UTCI mitigation along Canal do Mangue corridor where tree planting was incorporated
- Critical thermal stress levels in Area 3 (Porto) despite sea proximity, due to lack of heat reduction measures

Best Practice scenario analysis:

- General cooling effect in newly developed areas, particularly near northern port and Canal do Mangue
- Measurable reduction in Tmrt and UTCI values in Area 1 through modified building layout and increased vegetation
- Significant thermal stress reduction around Flamengo stadium and coastline through greening strategies
- Confirmation that adaptive measures alone are insufficient to fully mitigate extreme heatwave impacts under RCP 8.5

Flood Hazard Assessment

Unsteady flow analysis was conducted using HEC-RAS software to simulate dynamic water movement behaviour. The modelling captured variations in flow rates and water surface elevations during transient flooding events, providing insights into rainfall-runoff-drainage system interactions. The April 2010 extreme rainfall event served as validation reference for flood vulnerability mapping along Canal do Mangue and adjacent areas.

Masterplan Outputs

The Best Practice scenario resulted in a masterplan operationalizing the Sustainability Corridors (Green, Blue, Brown, Orange) at neighbourhood scale. Six meta-design configurations were developed, each addressing specific urban design themes to provide planners with effective mitigation and adaptation solutions. The main strategies adopted include:

- **Area 1 - Leopoldina Station:** new social housing district with emphasis on public open space design, blue infrastructure for flood mitigation, and enhanced urban connections
- **Area 2 - Canal do Mangue:** sustainable corridor integration with tree-lined streets, reduced vehicular space, dedicated public transport/cycling lanes, social housing development, and ecological restoration of neglected residual space as urban park
- **Area 3 - Porto/Ex-Gasômetro:** stadium integration with green infrastructure network, Porto Maravilha waterfront revitalization, building stock retrofit with renewable energy systems

Lessons learned

The São Cristóvão case shows that climate-informed policies become effective when metropolitan strategies are translated into concrete actions anchored to specific neighbourhood priorities.

The development of this pilot provided key insights for refining the UDCW methodology within UP2030's mission of supporting cities toward climate resilience, carbon neutrality, and just transition.

- **Downscaling metropolitan strategies requires governance literacy:** Translating high-level visions into neighbourhood-scale interventions demands detailed understanding of local policy frameworks. The overlapping planning instruments in São Cristóvão (Plano Diretor, Projeto de Estruturação Urbana, AEIS, APAC (Áreas de Proteção do Ambiente Cultural), Operação Urbana Consorciada Porto Maravilha (OUC) expansion) required careful navigation to identify implementation opportunities while avoiding conflicts and safeguarding social equity objectives.
- **Multi-scenario comparison supports trade-off visualization:** The three-scenario framework enabled stakeholders to visualize how different development trajectories affect thermal comfort, flood exposure, and land-use efficiency. Comparison between BAU (densification-

focused) and Best Practice (greening-focused) scenarios demonstrated measurable differences in MRT and UTCI outcomes, facilitating communication of climate risks and adaptation benefits to municipal decision-makers.

- **Adaptive measures have limits under extreme climate projections:** Simulations under RCP 8.5 showed that even comprehensive greening strategies cannot fully mitigate extreme heatwave impacts. UTCI values exceeding 46 °C were observed in BAU scenario despite vegetation increases, confirming that urban design interventions must be combined with broader mitigation policies to address future climate conditions.
- **Co-design strengthens tool relevance and uptake:** Iterative collaboration with Rio's municipal departments (IPP, COR, SMAC, Rio Águas) and academic partners ensured UDCW outputs aligned with actual planning needs. However, budget constraints prevented full deployment of the Facilitation Toolkit for real-time scenario generation during stakeholder workshops—a capability that would enhance future applications.
- **Tool bundling enhances multi-hazard assessment:** Synergies established with Deltares for flood modelling (HEC-RAS integration) demonstrated the value of combining UDCW's thermal comfort simulations with complementary hazard assessment tools, addressing the multi-risk nature of urban climate challenges more comprehensively.
- **Sustainability Corridors provide an integrative framework:** The corridor concept served as a unifying backbone for reconciling multiple planning instruments and competing development priorities. The downscaling process—translating Green, Blue, Brown, and Orange corridor typologies into actionable street sections and intervention nodes—achieved coherence across housing, mobility, ecological, and public space objectives.

The role of the tool in supporting improved decision making

The tool enhances decision-making by strengthening cross-sector capacity and helping municipal offices integrate climate risks, public infrastructure, housing policy, and environmental management into a coherent planning approach. Its evidence-based workflow promotes knowledge exchange on risk modelling and adaptation co-benefits, supporting the adoption of equitable, NSB. It also aligns environmental programmes led by SMAC with community initiatives focused on nature protection and ecological education. By clarifying how the Plano Diretor, Projeto de Estruturação Urbana São Cristóvão, AEIS), APAC, and the expansion of the OUC overlap in the neighbourhood, the tool helps reconcile competing mandates through the city's Sustainability Corridors strategy. The resulting policy recommendations strengthen governance by protecting social-housing areas, requiring redevelopment to follow Sustainability Corridor criteria, and linking public revenues to transparent social and environmental targets—offering a clear decision-support structure for a more inclusive and climate-resilient São Cristóvão.

Looking Towards the Future

Continued synergies: Collaboration between the UCCRN European Hub and Latin American Hub will sustain UDCW implementation with the City of Rio and local partners. Rio will continue serving as a case study for education and training at institutions such as the University of Naples Federico II, New York Institute of Technology, and PUC-Rio. Pilot case in international research: Rio has been included as a pilot city in a Horizon Europe proposal focused on innovative solutions for resilient and climate-adapted coastal communities in the Atlantic.

Global visibility: The work of UCCRN and the Rio prototype will be presented at COP30 in Belém, Brazil, highlighting Rio as a leader in urban climate resilience and showcasing the outcomes of the collaboration on the global stage. The event “Cities Adaptation and Justice in Climate Emergency - Launch of the UCCRN Scientific Assessment Reports, ARC3.3 series: Justice for Resilient Cities and Urban Planning and Design for Climate Action” is organized by PUC-Rio and UCCRN-LA and guested by the Instituto Bem Ambiental (IBAM) COP30 side events.

11.3.10 Case Study 2

Assessments and co-design for the Diotikirion Climate Action Plan

Tool Name: Urban Design Climate Workshop

City and District/Neighbourhood: Thessaloniki, Diotikirion District

Organisations:

- MDTA
- Municipality of Thessalonik
- Draxis

Why the City wanted to use the tool

Thessaloniki adopted the UDCW methodology to support the visioning of a climate-resilient Diotikirion District through incremental and transformative urban scenarios integrating advanced climate simulations and community-based adaption. Thessaloniki chose to use the UDCW tool because it offered a **science-based, participatory, and scalable approach** to link climate information with urban design and community needs, supporting with digital planning scenario modelling and co-design the development of a District Climate Action Plan (DCAP).

Description of case study area:

The Dioikitirion district lies along the western edge of Thessaloniki’s old city centre. Once a vibrant commercial and residential hub, it declined sharply after the 2010 economic crisis, which led to widespread business closures and visible urban neglect. Today, the area faces significant economic, social, and spatial pressures but is again becoming central to broader urban transformation efforts.

Dioikitirion has been selected as a pilot area for climate action and regeneration because it reflects many challenges of Thessaloniki’s core: noise, traffic congestion, limited green space, and declining air quality. These are compounded by tourism-driven development, rising real estate prices, and growing socio-spatial inequalities. The project aims to enhance resilience, reduce emissions, and improve environmental quality while preserving the neighbourhood’s identity and liveability. Defined by Egnatia Street, the western city walls, Olympiados Street, and the Aristotelous axis, the district offers a strategic setting for testing integrated approaches to heritage preservation, social inclusion, and climate adaptation.

Issues facing the city

Dioikitirion concentrates many of Thessaloniki's urban challenges: shrinking residential and economic activity, high vacancy rates, inactive basements, and a fragmented urban fabric. Environmental conditions are strained by scarce, poorly equipped green spaces, insufficient shade, and worsening summer heatwaves, compounded by persistent traffic congestion. At the same time, over-tourism and short-term rentals drive gentrification and weaken neighbourhood cohesion, pushing the district toward a monofunctional leisure-tourism model. These combined pressures undermine liveability and highlight the need for integrated strategies that address environmental quality, social equity, and economic revitalization.

Detailing the process of collaborating with the city

The UDCW provides assessments to quantify the climate benefits of planning and design strategies, offering science-based indicators and co-designed measures that align climate priorities with community needs. The prototype development has been structured according to the iterative process of the UDCW methodology and it has been articulated around three main phases.

- Phase 1 (Jul. 2024-Feb. 2025): applied the UDCW Methodology to the Dioikitirion case through a context and climate analysis, supported by the UDCW simulation toolkit and scenario-based assessments. Insights from the adaptive pathways workshop guided the definition of a resilient development pathway and an integrated urban strategy aligned with UP2030 goals. A preliminary masterplan was developed for 2030 and 2050 scenarios, focusing on green and blue infrastructures, mobility, energy retrofitting, and renewables, heat stress reduction, including existing city plans. In this first stage three strategic focus areas—Old Lachanagora Market, XII Apostol Church, and Antigoniidon Square—were selected for detailed visioning and climate-responsive design. These inputs have been the basis of the co-design phase in which the preliminary design proposals have been discussed with the community and the stakeholders to be further implemented.
- Phase 2 (Dec. 2024 – March 2025): The UDCW facilitation toolkit was applied to guide a co-design and collaborative mapping process involving different target groups, including the elderly, civil servants, and the general public. The co-design was implemented through three dedicated sessions, each tailored to a specific stakeholder or community group. Facilitation tools such as collaborative mapping and city visioning were adapted to the prototype's requirements and supported by extensive capacity-building activities with city liaisons and the Municipality. This phase produced detailed design proposals for the three focus areas, identifying design options and technical solutions for the adaptation of buildings and open spaces. A prototype report was delivered, synthesizing the initial climate analysis and co-design results.
- Phase 3 (March 2025-Sept. 2025): This phase focused on integrating the outcomes of co-design and collaborative mapping into the design proposals, refining the masterplan and its thematic priorities. An additional focus area (Thessaloniki Forum) was introduced to strengthen the integration of community input within the design and assessment process. Climate analysis scenarios integrated the co-design inputs and all the simulations (future climate scenarios and energy and microclimate assessments) were refined through updated models and more precise dataset. Phase 3 concluded with the full implementation of the prototype and its formal contribution to the Dioikitirion District Climate Action Plan (DCAP).

Figure 81: Phases of tools implementation and collaboration with the City

Integrating tool into local context

The UDCW was implemented in Thessaloniki as part of the pilot activities in support of the **Diokitirion District Climate Action Plan**, under development by the Municipality of Thessaloniki. The UDCW methodology, combining simulation and facilitation toolkits, has provided a framework to prototype design solutions, assess climate impacts, and embed co-designed interventions within the local context. The process has enabled the municipality and community actors to identify strategies for improving energy efficiency, evaluate the climate performance of open spaces, and align climate-resilient urban transformations with local priorities.

Integration into Local Planning of Climate Assessments

UDCW methods were embedded into the city’s planning process through a structured sequence:

- Spatialization of Vision Phase results in GIS: Land use, green/vacant spaces, mobility patterns, and accommodation types were mapped to assess heat-wave exposure, district energy consumption, and solar potential. Parallel analyses examined green/blue infrastructure, retrofit opportunities, and renewable energy integration.
- Translation of climate actions into spatial solutions: UCCRN adapted the Adaptive Pathways into a district-level masterplan addressing energy transition, micro-climate responsiveness, sustainable mobility, and urban greening, complemented by non-spatial measures such as education and capacity building.
- Pilot testing supported by the UDCW Simulation Toolkit: Heat-wave simulations for current and future scenarios (2030/2050) were conducted at district scale and for specific focus areas (Old Lachanagora Market, XII Apostolis Square, Antigoniidon Square, later the Thessaloniki Forum), using GIS and 3D modelling. This required extensive data exchange on local assets and regeneration opportunities.

Implementation of the Facilitation Toolkit in the Co-Design Phase

The co-design workshop (February 2025) adapted two core tools from the UDCW Facilitation Toolkit to Thessaloniki’s context:

- Tool 1 — Collaborative Mapping

Used to spatialize local knowledge by: gathering community observations on heat islands, flooding, and environmental or social issues; identifying locations requiring ecological interventions or improvements in mobility and public space.

Participants used analogue and digital mapping tools to create a shared spatial baseline for design refinement.

- Tool 2 — City Visions & Local Need Matching

Used to adapt predefined climate-resilient design proposals by: presenting climate solutions (green infrastructure, energy-efficient buildings, walkable streets); collecting feedback on contextual adjustments; identifying feasible and scalable interventions.

Participants positioned short-term (2030) and long-term (2050) interventions on maps using sketches, models, and structured discussions.

The co-design process engaged residents, civil servants, and experts, revealing priorities such as pedestrianization, greening, shading, multifunctional spaces, and improved safety for vulnerable groups. These inputs informed the revised masterplan targeting four primary areas and highlighting additional sites for future action.

Figure 82: UDCW Facilitation City Visioning, co-design session

3. Iterative process for prototyping

The UDCW process generated a portfolio of co-designed and simulated measures across four thematic categories:

Table 4: co-designed measures generated by the UDCW process

Thematic focus	Measures co-designed and simulated for climate assessment of future scenarios
Energy Transition	HVAC system improvements; PV panels; lighting upgrades; water heating improvements; conversion of abandoned buildings into social housing.
Micro-Climature Responsiveness	Green façades; intensive and extensive green roofs; permeable paving; green canopies; climate shelters.
Mobility & Proximity	Pedestrianization; bike routes and parking; creation of shared spaces; redesign of unsafe crossings; low-traffic routes; safe access to schools; opening urban spaces to the public; parklets.
Urban Greening & Biodiversity	Lawns and green areas; tree pots; pocket parks; green balconies; adoption of trees; new green spaces; retention basins; fountains. Bioswales; green strips; depaving; gutters and storm drains; bird baths; insect hotels.

They combine punctual interventions with spatial strategies, supporting both short-term feasibility and long-term transformation.

A core feature of UDCW implementation was iterative prototyping. Design outputs from the co-design phase were incorporated into the preliminary masterplan and modelled using the Simulation Toolkit. Scenario simulations assessed heat-wave mitigation performance, thermal comfort gains, and energy savings for 2030 and 2050. Feedback loops with Major Development Agency Thessaloniki (MDAT) and DRAXIS ensured technical robustness and alignment with the DCAP.

This iterative cycle enabled continuous refinement and evidence-based validation of climate-responsive design solutions tailored to Thessaloniki’s local context.

Examples of tool being used

UDCW Facilitation Collaborative Mapping, digitalization of co-design session

Figure 83: UDCW Facilitation Collaborative Mapping, digital results

Figure 84: UDCW Simulation, masterplan and heat wave simulations, thermal outdoor comfort 2050 scenario

Lachanagora - 2025

Lachanagora - 2030

Lachanagora - 2050

Figure 85: UDCW Facilitation City Visioning, Old Lachanagora Market- 2025-2030 and 2050 scenarios

Figure 86: UDCW Simulation, Solar Energy potential available on the selected buildings in 2050 Solar Energy Production - 2050 Scenario

Figure 87: UDCW Simulation, Heatwave Hazard - Old Lachanagara Market- 2030 scenario

Figure 88: UDCW Simulation, Heatwave Hazard - Old Lachanagora Market- 2050 scenario

Challenges

The application of the UDCW Toolkits faced several challenges that affected both the technical process and its policy relevance. Developing the preliminary masterplan required extensive local knowledge and intensive data exchange between UCCRN and partners, demanding significant time and resources. The high density of the neighbourhood limited the potential for substantial heat reduction, highlighting instead the risks of inaction on future thermal comfort indicators (UTCI, MRT) and resident well-being by 2050. Data gaps, particularly on building technologies for energy consumption and on impact assessment, further constrained the accuracy of simulations. Technical issues also arose from the evolving nature of the Simulation toolkit (in particular 3D modelling AAD tools), with bugs affecting modelling outputs, while the expansion of project areas after co-design added extra workload for simulations. Finally, the non-binding status of the DCAP and the absence of dedicated implementation resources point out the difficulty of moving from technical planning and policy making to concrete urban transformation.

Outcomes of Tool Use:

Microclimate simulations were performed both at urban and neighbourhood scale through GIS and 3D modelling AAD tools using two KPIs: MRT and UTCI.

Table 5: Current Climate Scenario and assessments

Scale	Assessment
District Scale (Dioikitirion Area)	<p>Heat wave hazard</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High thermal stress hotspots were concentrated in dense, less vegetated urban areas, especially Lachanagora and Dioikitirion Square. • Cooler zones were identified along the Western Walls and Aristotelous axis, where urban greenery reduced heat stress. • The district displayed marked sensitivity to heatwaves, highlighting the role of vegetation and urban form in shaping microclimate.
	<p>Heat wave Impacts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heatwave simulations indicated two levels of population vulnerability, leading to differentiated health risks. • Hospitalization costs for heat-related illnesses were estimated at €368,206 per heatwave event (average stay 3.2 days, ~€1,000 per day). • 80% of hospital admissions occurred through emergency departments, underscoring the acute burden on healthcare systems.
	<p>Energy Consumption</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building stock classified by construction period and insulation standards, reflecting regulatory changes in Greece. • Older buildings (pre-1980s) with poor insulation and outdated HVAC systems are significantly more energy intensive. • Energy simulations showed higher cooling demand in dense districts with low vegetation and heat island effects, compounding vulnerability during extreme heat events. • Buildings constructed post-2000 perform comparatively better due to stricter thermal regulations and improved materials.
Neighbourhood Scale (Focus Areas):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Old Lachanagora Market: High MRT/UTCI values due to impermeable asphalt surfaces and lack of greenery, with discomfort peaking between (12:00–18:00) • XII Apostoli Church: Elevated stress around the church and walls, exacerbated by bare soil and limited vegetation. • Antigonidon Square: Strong discomfort across paved areas and adjacent streets, with heat stress intensifying in afternoon hours. • Thessaloniki Forum: Severe thermal stress due to asphalt, scarce vegetation, and exposure around archaeological ruins and Agiou Dimitriou church.

Table 6: Future Climate Scenario and Assessments

Scale	Assessment
District Scale (Dioikitirion Area)	<p>Heat wave reduction and outdoor comfort improvement 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulations showed a slight improvement in outdoor comfort compared to the current state due to planned measures (e.g., greening, reflective materials, shading). <p>2050</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With higher baseline air temperature (39.2 °C), even with interventions, critical UTCI thresholds (>46 °C) were exceeded in hotspots (Lachanagora, Antigonidon, Forum). • Interventions still provided measurable relief and outdoor comfort improvement
	<p>Heat wave Impacts 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Projected reduction in heatwave-related hospitalization costs, with simulations estimating ~47.9% reduction compared to inaction. <p>2050</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Despite extreme temperatures, applying all planned measures still halved hospitalization costs compared to the no-action scenario, though residual risks remained high.
	<p>Energy Retrofitting 2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant reduction in cooling energy demand in retrofitted buildings due to insulation upgrades, reflective surfaces, and improved HVAC systems. <p>2050</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While rising ambient temperatures increased absolute energy needs, strategic measures (retrofits, shading, renewable integration) mitigated demand growth. • Energy reduction strategies (cool roofs, photovoltaic-integrated shading, greening) were most effective in dense areas like Lachanagora and Forum, where heat stress was also highest.
Neighbourhood Scale (Focus Areas):	<p>2030</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In Lachanagora, MRT reduced by 0.8 °C on average, with local reductions up to 4 °C; UTCI improved by ~1.2 °C. • At XII Apostoli, MRT dropped by ~1 °C, UTCI reduced by 0.2 °C on average (hotspots up to 3 °C). • Antigonidon Square showed modest reductions: MRT ~0.5 °C, UTCI negligible.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thessaloniki Forum experienced notable improvement: MRT decreased from 50.5 °C to 49.0 °C, UTCI decreased by ~0.5 °C. <p>2050</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lachanagora: MRT reduced by 2.3 °C on average, hotspots >5 °C; UTCI dropped by ~1.8 °C. XII Apostoli: MRT decreased by 0.5 °C, UTCI reduced by 1 °C. Antigonidon: MRT reduced by 0.6 °C, UTCI by 0.1 °C. Thessaloniki Forum: MRT reduced by ~1 °C, UTCI by 1.3 °C, hotspots up to 3 °C.
--	---

Table 7: GIS Tools outputs and indicators

GIS TOOLS RESULTS DATA	Indicators
Heat Wave Hazard analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MRT [°C] UTCI [°C]
Heat Wave Impact analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hospitalisation costs [€] Mortality rate [%]
Energy analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average building energy consumption [kWh/m²y] Renewable energy production potential [kWh/y]

Table 8: 3D AAD Tools outputs and indicators

3D MODELLING RESULTS OUTPUT DATA	Indicators
Thermal comfort analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mean Radiant Temperature (TMRT) [°C] UTCI [°C] PMV
Energy analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> End Use Intensity [kWh/m²y] Renewable energy production potential [kWh/y]

UDCW Simulations Insights:

- Urban morphology as a driver of heat stress: dense built-up areas with low vegetation significantly amplify heat exposure, while green corridors and shaded zones mitigate risks. Compact, asphalt-dominated areas are most threaten, making the consideration about the urban form and the integration of depaving solution and rainwater infiltration necessary.
- Localized hotspots require targeted interventions: Hotspots (Lachanagora, Antigonidon, Forum) require combined strategies—cooling infrastructure and building efficiency upgrades.

- Green infrastructure as climate buffer: vegetation (trees, shaded areas, green roofs) emerged as a key lever for reducing MRT/UTCI AC levels and improving thermal comfort.
- Energy-Climate Nexus: Poorly insulated, older building stock amplifies cooling energy demand during heatwaves, reinforcing the urgency for retrofitting.
- Healthcare Burden: Heat stress has measurable financial impacts on health systems, underlining the co-benefits of climate adaptation. Extreme heat directly translates into substantial healthcare costs, demonstrating the socioeconomic dimension of climate impacts.
- Future Risk Trajectories: events classified as “occasional” (2021–2040) are projected to become “frequent” (2041–2070), increasing cumulative exposure risks. Increased frequency of heatwaves will escalate both energy costs and health burdens, reinforcing the importance of pre-emptive resilience planning.
- Policy Leverage: Data highlights the need for integrated planning (urban greenery, energy retrofits, and resilient healthcare systems) to address climate risks.

UDCW Facilitation Toolkit Results

Table 8: Facilitation toolkit results summary

Tool	Result
Collaborative Mapping	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community insights on climate-related issues were gathered and documented. • Areas exposed to climate risks (heat islands, flooding-prone zones) were identified. • Social, economic, and environmental challenges were mapped spatially. • A shared reference map was produced, combining local knowledge and resilience needs.
City Visions and Local Need Matching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design proposals were presented to the community. • Feedback was collected on local adaptation of proposed solutions. • Community visions for integrating climate resilience with daily life were articulated. • Scalable interventions for short-term (2030) and long-term (2050) horizons were localized on maps. • Intervention points were prioritised based on feasibility and community relevance.

UDCW Facilitation Insights:

- Community knowledge integration and Localized adaptation: Proposed solutions required contextual adjustments to align with neighbourhood realities. Residents provided detailed local awareness of climate risks and urban challenges, strengthening technical data. Most importantly they contributed to frame the emerging neighbourhood challenges within decarbonization and resilient development framework. Specific topics and drivers emerged:

- Shared spatial understanding: Collaborative mapping fostered a common visual language and improved communication.
- Scalability and prioritisation: Community feedback helped identify which interventions were both feasible and impactful at scale.
- Temporal perspectives: Distinctions emerged between urgent short-term needs (e.g., heat mitigation, flood control) and long-term visions (e.g., sustainable mobility, green infrastructure).
- Co-design value and climate justice objectives: Active community participation can contribute to increase ownership, trust, and alignment of resilience interventions with local needs. Justice objective have been explicitly accomplished through the use of the tools. Distributive justice has been supported through mapping of hotspot areas, evaluating burdens and benefits, and identifying priorities that link climate measures with fairer access to urban services and infrastructure. Procedural justice has been developed through participatory diagnosis, early citizen engagement, digitalized outputs, and co-design sessions that ensured fair representation and the feasibility of inclusive planning. Recognitional justice has been considered applying a co-production of knowledge methodology, making visible of existing inequalities, and contextualising design solutions based on situated knowledge and lived experience.

Lessons learned

The Dioikitirion pilot provided key insights for refining the UDCW methodology and demonstrating its applicability to European historic urban contexts facing combined climate, economic, and social pressures.

- **Integration of Simulation and Facilitation toolkits is essential for evidence-based climate action:** The Thessaloniki case demonstrates that harmonizing science-driven information with tacit community knowledge produces more robust and actionable planning outcomes. The iterative feedback loop—where co-design outputs were incorporated into simulations and validated against performance metrics—enabled continuous refinement and evidence-based validation of climate-responsive solutions.
- **Data availability determines simulation accuracy:** Gaps in building technology data (insulation standards, HVAC systems) constrained energy consumption assessments. Future applications require early-stage data protocols and agreements with municipal departments to ensure comprehensive inputs for modelling.
- **Local partners are critical enablers for co-design implementation:** Synergies between UCCRN and the Municipality were essential for adapting facilitation tools to the local context, organizing stakeholder sessions, and ensuring capacity-building activities reached target groups (elderly, civil servants, general public).
- **Co-design advances climate justice objectives:** The facilitation toolkit operationalized three justice dimensions: distributive (hotspot mapping linking climate measures with equitable service access), procedural (participatory diagnosis ensuring fair representation), and recognitional (co-production making inequalities visible and grounding solutions in lived experience). This explicit justice framing strengthened community ownership and trust.
- **Non-binding plan status challenges implementation pathways:** The DCAP's advisory nature and absence of dedicated implementation resources highlight the difficulty of translating

technical planning into concrete urban transformation. Embedding UDCW outputs into binding instruments (SUMP, SECAP, Operational Plans) and securing political commitment are necessary for sustained impact.

- **UDCW demonstrates scalability for municipal climate planning:** The methodology's successful application at district scale, with integration into existing city frameworks (Green Infrastructure Plan, Urban Development strategies), confirms that local authorities can effectively use the toolkit for climate planning. The city's interest in upscaling to other districts validates the prototype's replicability.

The role of the tool in supporting improved decision making

The UDCW Toolkit supports evidence-based decision-making by combining advanced simulations with planning instruments to guide climate action in Thessaloniki, individuating real design measures and priority areas. Multi-scale analysis of heatwave vulnerability, energy demand, and renewable potential provides the technical foundation for prioritising interventions, while spatial assessments identify areas for greening and public space transformation consistent with 2030 and 2050 targets. Co-design processes ensure that the proposed solutions are community-based, yet the strength of the tool lies in embedding these outcomes into institutional frameworks, including the Operational Plan, Sustainable Mobility Plan, Green Infrastructure, and Urban Development strategies.

This integration secures continuity with the SUMP and SECAP, turning prototype scenarios into policy-aligned measures. The micro-climate assessment of focus areas interventions—ranging from schoolyard greening and adaptive shading to mobility improvements and reuse of vacant spaces—offer tangible, scalable interventions that link long-term climate goals to immediate implementation pathways. The UDCW significantly supported the Implementation readiness of the prototype as the DCAP outcomes are under discussion for real implementation, bridging the gap between vision and practice.

Furthermore, the tool enhances decision-making by embedding justice considerations into climate planning. It highlights how risks and benefits are distributed across neighbourhoods, identifies vulnerable hotspots, and uses participatory diagnosis to ensure fair representation in design processes. By combining distributive, procedural, and recognitional justice, the UDCW makes inequalities visible and supports solutions grounded in local knowledge and lived experience.

Looking Towards the Future:

By enabling city-wide application, the UDCW can support the continued use of prototype methodology beyond the project in another district of Thessaloniki. The prototype offers a solid basis of design scenarios and comparable mid-term and long-term assessments, encouraging an incremental approach for the implementation of the adaptation and mitigation solutions that can be replicated. The city showed interest in using the DCAP approach and the UCCRN tools to upscale the results.

UCCRN, MDAT and DRAXIS are collaborating for the further project proposal, two already submitted for Horizon EU funds proposing Thessaloniki Metropolitan area and Attica region as pilot cases.

The results of the case are being integrated in the DDS platform by DRAXIS, an on-line digital tool for spatial data visualization and in the Neutrality Story Map of Thessaloniki.

12 University of Cambridge

The University of Cambridge (UCAM) is one of the world's leading universities. For UP2030, UCAM is represented by researchers from the Centre for Sustainable Development, established in 2000 following support provided by the Royal Academy of Engineering, to introduce concepts of sustainability over all their undergraduate engineering courses. The Centre has grown to encompass the delivery of a one-year full-time taught MPhil in Engineering for Sustainable Development and a research community currently covering sustainable development issues in the fields of water, urban flood management, infrastructure resilience, post-disaster recovery, international development, climate change mitigation and adaptation and system dynamic modelling of coupled resource management.

Partner Website: <https://www-csd.eng.cam.ac.uk/>

12.1 Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping

Within UP2030 the majority of cities are working in some capacity to reduce their carbon emissions. However, this is occurring at the neighbourhood or district level. This is of significance owing to the general lack of accurate emissions data at this scale, with cities often possessing city-wide data, which is too inaccurate to be applied. To remedy this, UCAM has developed a methodology to estimate carbon emissions from the 'bottom-up', enabling cities to estimate the emission impacts of urban regeneration projects by focusing on three key areas – household and mobility emissions, as well as carbon sequestration through urban greening. This tool has been developed through a case study in Belfast's Linen Quarter district.

Costs: No funding required

12.1.1 Software Requirements

This tool is Microsoft Excel based and does not require any additional software to perform calculations. For full functionality, the tool should not be used through a web browser and should be downloaded.

12.1.2 Data Requirements

The data required below is to be used to inform calculations, rather than to run models or algorithms.

The specific data used in calculations is dependent on the data available to the user. However, for the calculations to be performed using the methods contained within the tool, the following data is essential:

Household Carbon Emissions Baseline:

Total carbon footprint for households in project area.

- Household area (m²)
- Primary Energy Use (PEU) (kWh/m²/yr)
- Emission factors
- Amount of CO₂ produced per unit of activity, such as kilowatt hours of electricity consumer or kilometres travelled by car. These are usually nation specific.

Mobility Carbon Emissions Baseline:

Total carbon emissions for travel in project area.

- Vehicle ownership data (number of people who have access to vehicle)

- The most recent census demographic data
- Journey purpose and distance data (from travel surveys)
- Vehicle emission factors

Greening Storage and Sequestration:

- Tree species data – the number and locations of different trees
- Tree size data (diameter at breast height)
- Annual growth rate
- Formulas to convert estimated tree biomass into carbon

Whilst the data available will inform the results produced by the calculations, so do the assumptions made in formulating the estimates. The assumptions implemented are influenced by the data available and are therefore context dependent. The assumptions contained within the calculations are as follows:

Household Carbon Emissions Baseline:

- The proportion of PEU produced by heating/hot water and by electricity use

Mobility Carbon Emissions Baseline:

- If a person owns a car they will drive everywhere, whereas if they do not, they will take the bus. Depending on data availability, further non-motorised transportation and active travel can be included.
- Depending on local employment data, plus the proportion of residents who are either parents or carers, a percentage of residents will be affixed weekly travel personas.
- Data based around age and gender should also be used to further improve the accuracy of assumptions.

The below weekly travel assumptions were implemented:

Weekly Persona Trip Assumptions and Number of days a week of travel:

- Full Time Employment (commuting) - 5
- Part Time Employment (commuting) - 2
- Zero Carbon Commute/ Out of Work (commuting) - 0
- Parent (school run) - 5
- Non-Parent (school run) - 0
- Carer (other escort) - 5
- Non-Carer (other escort) - 0
- Leisure & Other (weekend activities) - 2
- Personal business (miscellaneous travel) - 1
- Shopping (weekly food shop) - 1

Greening Storage and Sequestration:

- That all trees of a certain species will grow at the same rate.
- Climatic conditions such as sunlight have not been considered

All data detailed below has been used within the UP2030 project to conduct carbon accounting estimates within the Linen Quarter in Belfast (discussed in more detail in the case study section):

Household Baseline:

- Census household type data (numbers of housing types)
- Energy Performance Certificate data (area, property features and PEU)
- Fuel source emission factors
- Google Maps (to find household postcodes for Energy Performance Certificate data)
- Average domestic energy use data (UK Government)

Mobility Baseline:

- Census vehicle ownership data
- Census demographic data (age, gender, percentages of parents and carers, travelling to work)
- Northern Ireland Travel Survey (national average km travelled per journey purpose)
- Vehicle emission factors (car and bus per person)

Greening Storage and Sequestration:

- Belfast Public Tree data

More specific details concerning the data used within the Linen Quarter project can be found in the appendix of this tool's methodological guide.

12.1.3 Expertise Requirements

The tool has been developed to be as user friendly as possible, however, some knowledge of carbon accounting would be advantageous, for this would allow the tool's outputs to be placed within a broader context. The tool is provided with a digital methodological guidebook.

It has been designed for use by those with intermediate proficiency in using Microsoft Excel.

12.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

The calculations are based on bringing different excel datasets together to create emission estimates; therefore, the process can be fairly time consuming in terms of identifying and formatting data.

Another barrier to use is data availability more generally, with more representative data, such as 'trip' data for estimating mobility emissions, sometimes being siloed within municipal departments.

12.1.5 Tool Use Context

For cities currently working to reduce carbon emissions who are reliant on city-wide emission data but are implementing neighbourhood scale projects and are looking for an approach to estimate the carbon emission productions and savings from that project.

12.1.6 Tool Limitations

The tool is designed to provide estimates of carbon emissions and lacks the capacity to directly monitor emissions. It is therefore intended to be used as a policy guide, offering estimates for practitioners.

12.1.7 City Journey

For cities with experience in conducting carbon accounting at a city-wide scale but are currently unable to account for project level decarbonization actions.

12.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

Below is a brief description the different steps taken to apply the method developed here. Steps 2-7 are to be replicated for each worksheet.

1. Define boundary of project area

Set the boundary of the project area. This will determine the geographic limits of the calculations, setting which spaces will be either included or otherwise within the calculations.

2. Identify Data

Find the data to base the emission estimate calculations on. This will predominately be activity data, such as energy consumed or km travelled, and could either be locally specific datasets or national level data. This step will produce the data to be used.

3. Set Assumptions

Whilst the data collected will inform you on certain elements, there will be gaps present. Therefore, the assumptions made by the user are important in determining the outcome of emission estimations. It is at this point clearly determined and observed assumptions regarding elements like travel behaviour or domestic energy mix are to be devised.

4. Identify Emission Factors

This step takes the combination of activity data and assumptions and converts this data into a carbon emission number. Many countries have their own national level emission factors which are available online.

5. Establish calculations and set formulas

After establishing the data and the emission factors to be used, the next step is to determine which calculations are to be used. From a functional perspective, the setting of Microsoft Excel formulas is important to ensure replicability across the different elements and workbooks contained within the method.

6. Conduct Calculations

Run the calculations determined in the previous step using the data and along the assumptions set in steps 2, 3, and 4. Do this for each datazone. This step produces the datazone specific carbon emissions.

7. Aggregate data zone calculations to produce emission estimation totals

After estimating the carbon emissions for each datazone, combine them to produce an estimate for the regeneration project area as a whole. This produces the estimate of regeneration emissions for an element of the project (for example household emission baseline). Conduct steps 2 – 7 for each element to estimate total emissions.

8. Visualise Results

If desired, the results from the calculations can be visualised.

Figure 89: Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping process flow diagram

12.1.9 Case Study

Urban Regeneration Carbon Assessment in Belfast's Linen Quarter

Tool Name: Urban Carbon Emission Data Flow Mapping

City and District/Neighbourhood: Belfast – Linen Quarter

Organisations:

- UCAM
- Belfast City Council

Case Study Context

The city of Belfast's participation in the UP2030 project centres on the *Linen Quarter* in the centre of the city. Initially focusing on the area's 'Business Improvement District', the UP2030 project area expanded outwards to include the neighbourhoods of Sandy Row, The Market, Donegall Pass and Barrack Street within UP2030. Alongside actions focusing on community engagement and encouraging active travel, one task was to estimate the carbon emissions of the project area and assess the impacts of different approaches to reduce these emissions.

The collaboration between UCAM and Belfast City Council originally concerned understanding the existence and use of carbon emission data within city councils and how information was accessed across the organisation for emissions estimating, accounting and/or budgeting purposes. Further discussions surfaced a particular desire within the Council to gain a better understanding of the potential carbon emissions impact of their urban regeneration plans. This is an important feature of many cities within UP2030, where emission reductions are identified as a key target in the majority of projects. Whilst Belfast City Council currently reports their own organisational emissions to the Northern Irish *Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs*, and has access to citywide emissions estimates provided by the UK's *National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory*, they lack the capacity or resources to conduct neighbourhood level carbon assessment. This is not an unusual position for European cities today.

Belfast City Council, through an early UP2030 workshop, identified three approaches through which they wanted to reduce the Linen Quarter's carbon emissions: household retrofit, active travel and urban greening. To support the Council in this endeavour, UCAM developed a carbon estimating approach through working with the city. While the tool is shaped by data availability, its predominant purpose is to estimate and map emissions that may be influenced by regeneration activity. This is an Excel-based tool, which can be used to estimate carbon emission baselines of housing energy use, resident mobility and urban greening, plus explore the potential emission reductions of improved household insulation and the installation of solar panels, as well as the potential impacts of cycling.

The baseline annual carbon emissions for the above three areas is estimated to be approximately 20,000 tCO₂/yr, of which approximately 13,000 tCO₂/yr is associated with household energy use and 7,000 tCO₂/yr from resident mobility. The annual sequestration rate of city-recorded trees in the area is estimated at approximately 80 tCO₂/yr. The tool then estimated the potential emissions reductions of interventions reduction action for comparative purposes. While it was found that insulation of

housing presents a significant opportunity, this needs to be considered in light of costs and ease of implementation.

To illustrate how the tool has been applied within Belfast, each element is detailed below following the step-by-step format detailed in the previous section.

Figure 90: Map of Linen Quarter project area (pink line) and the census data zones which have a footprint within it (green). There are three gaps, the one at the top is due to that data zone not having a presence in the project area, and the two at the bottom have a limited presence.

The following sections outline the application of the key components of the tool to the case, briefly covering the steps 2-7 (steps indicated in brackets) provided in the step-by-step guide.

Household Emissions baseline

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): According to Belfast's Net Zero Roadmap (Gouldson et al., 2020) domestic carbon emissions account for 39% of the city's total emissions – the single largest carbon source - estimated to reach 50% by 2050. To calculate the project area's household emissions, the case study used publicly available PEU data stored on the UK Government's *Find an energy certificate* platform. Energy certificates provide information on the energy consumption of a household and information regarding energy source, level of insulation and the size of a household. Here, a household's PEU covers the energy required for lighting, heating and hot water in a property and is presented as kilowatt hours per metre squared per year (kWh/m²/yr). When combined with the floor area of a household (available from the same source) and an emission factor (established by the UK Government) a building's carbon emissions can be calculated.

The energy mix has been estimated using the UK's average total domestic energy use. On this basis it was assumed that the energy mix for all households in the Linen Quarter was heating and hot water = 78%, electricity = 22%. By adding together the two totals, the annual carbon footprint (associated with energy use) of each household is estimated. The number of households was identified using (A) the Northern Irish Census to establish how many households and the prevalence of which types (Detached, Semi-Detached, Terrace and Apartments) are in each data zone (see Figure 90 for data zones) and (B) Google Maps, to assign postcodes within each data zone. The postcodes are required to attain PEU and floor area data from the Government's Energy Performance Certificate platform. To manage time limitations a 25% sample of households was analysed and the findings scaled to calculate total emissions for each data zone.

Key data sources were:

- Census household type data (numbers of housing types)
- Energy Performance Certificate data (area, property features and PEU)
- Fuel source emission factors (UK Government)
- Online maps (to find household postcodes for Energy Performance Certificate data)
- Average domestic energy use data (UK Government)

Establish calculations (5): The key equations applied (as formulae in Excel) in this component are listed below: *Where*

- *A, the area of the building (m²)*
- *PEU (kWh/m²/year)*
- *The composition of energy use or 'energy mix' (heating = H%, electricity = Elec%)*
- *The emission factors for the fuel/electricity used (heating = EF_{hr} , electricity = EF_{elec})*

Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7)

Figure 91 outlines the results of the calculations.

Figure 91: Estimated household carbon emissions (associated with energy use) within the Linen Quarter. The numbers correspond to the annual carbon emissions of each Census data zone. The boundaries of some data zones which fall outside the project area have been included in calculations.

Mobility

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): Whilst not as large as those associated with household energy use, mobility emissions are still significant within Belfast. Ideally, emissions estimates would be drawn from ‘trip data’ from a transport model. At the time of estimation, this data was not available, therefore the baseline estimate made here is a more high-level representation of emissions, based upon proxy estimates and available data.

Within the Travel Survey Northern Ireland (TSNI) questions revolve around how far people travel, how they travel, why they travel - commuting, education, driving other people, shopping, leisure and other journeys - as well as how often they are walking and taking journeys by car, train, bus or bicycle. The survey findings are split along age and gender lines. Census data for the Linen Quarter project area has been used to translate the national TSNI data to the local context, by relating census provided age, gender, car or vehicle availability, method of travel to work and economic activity data to the national average travel behaviours of each age and gender group.

In essence, the TSNI data provides information on how individuals of different age and gender groups travel, and the Census data provides information on how many different types of people live within each data zone. The census data was used to create a range of ‘personas’, representations of different types of residents, as a means of applying the individual TSNI behavioural data to the demographic reality of the Linen Quarter. Beyond sorting groups into age and sex, travel characteristics revolved around employment type (full, part time or out of work) and whether the resident is a parent or a carer. Within the TSNI there are observable differences in travel patterns along age and gender lines,

therefore these have been applied to the above personas (so a single person becomes, for example “Female aged 30-59 in Full time work).

This created 54 personas in total, across both car ownership and non-car ownership. Weekly travel totals are scaled by 52 to estimate annual distances. Use of a car is determined by rates of car ownership according to Census data within each data zone. The assumed annual kilometres travelled are converted into carbon estimates through the use of emission factors.

Key data sources drawn upon were:

- Census vehicle ownership data
- Census demographic data (age, gender, percentages of parents and carers, travel to work)
- Northern Ireland Travel Survey (national average km travelled per journey purpose)
- UK Government vehicle emission factors (car and bus, on a per person basis)

Establish calculations (5), Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7)

Figure 92: Annual resident mobility kgCO2/year per person map. The emissions have been presented in terms of per person emissions due to the significant influence of population size on the findings, with a difference of 675 people when comparing the largest and smallest data zones.

Urban Greening – Carbon Storage and Sequestration

Define boundary area (1)

Given the data available, the boundary area for this calculation was an approximation of the project area described earlier. The creation of a square boundary defined by the north, south, east and west limits of the project area enabled coordinates within the project area to be estimated. Coordinates were required to interrogate the tree database outlined below.

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): The approach taken here is structured around three primary actions: the storage of carbon in the trees of the Linen Quarter, the identification of sequestration rates and the total emission reductions of carbon emissions by trees. To begin, this project used Belfast City Council's Open Data Tree Database which details the species and location of 'public' (park and street) trees in the cityscape and includes data on tree location, species, age, health and a key tree dimension *diameter at breast height* (dbh).

Through selecting entries with coordinates within the estimated project area, it is estimated there are 1349 public trees to account for.

Establish calculations (5): The key equations applied (as formulae in Excel) in this component are listed below. The process involved calculating the current carbon storage capacity of each tree by applying tree biomass equations developed by the UK Government's Forest Research organisation to a tree's dbh:

$$b \times dbh^p / 0.75 \times 0.5 \times 3.76 = tCO_2$$

Calculate above ground biomass for tree where b and p are tree specific conversion factors - $b \times dbh^p$

Calculate below and above ground biomass by assuming 25% of tree's total biomass is below ground - $/0.75$

Convert biomass into dry carbon number assuming half of the tree's weight is carbon - $\times 0.5$

Convert dry carbon into carbon dioxide (CO₂) through using conversion factor - $\times 3.76$

Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7): The sequestration rate difference between the original size of the tree and the annual increase in carbon stored. The average rate for the project area was estimated at 18.61 kgCO₂/yr/tree. With an estimated 1,349 public trees in the area, this equates to approximately 25 tCO₂/yr absorbed by public, park and street trees.

A limitation with this initial approach was the use of a square boundary as a rough approximation of the project area, and a focus on public trees only. Belfast City Council published the *Valuing Belfast's Urban Forest Report* in 2022, which estimated tree land-area coverage in the Linen Quarter at 7% (at most). According to the same report, the average tree coverage in Belfast is 14.7% - 61 trees per hectare. On this basis the Linen Quarter tree coverage is estimated at 30 trees per hectare. The project area total was estimated (using the Google Maps area tool this time) to be 150.5 hectares. At 30 trees per hectare, this results in 4,515 trees total. Applying an average sequestration rate of 18.61 kgCO₂/yr results in an estimated 84 tCO₂/yr absorbed by trees.

Household Insulation Retrofit

This tool applies building archetypes to estimate the emission reduction potential of enhancing a household's insulation. By using an archetype and estimating the emissions impact on it through a range of actions (in this case, improving its insulation), a user can apply those emission savings to other buildings of the same type. For this role, the EU's Typology Approach for Building Stock Energy Assessment (TABULA) building archetypes have been used. This project developed 'typologies' for the different forms of housing across 21 EU countries. The Ireland typology, adopted here, contains 26 building archetypes.

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): Within each Irish TABULA archetype there is a range of information relating to the type of building, such as heating system characteristics and level of wall, roof and window insulation. The possible scope of retrofit is also

presented covering the improved insulation of a household and the enhancement of its heating system, whilst also providing an estimate of the potential PEU and carbon emission reductions. Through adopting the TABULA approach, a household's suitability for insulation retrofit is determined by the amount of insulation already in place – with this information being contained within the EPC data used for the household emission baseline calculations.

- Walls: Any insulation less than *insulated* or *filled cavity* is eligible for retrofit
- Roof: Any insulation less than *250mm* is eligible for retrofit
- Windows: Any insulation less than *partially double glazed* is eligible for retrofit

Establish calculations (5), Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7): Emission reductions were estimated based on the extent of the intervention. First, the absolute figures of PEU reduction (Primary Energy Consumption kWh/m²/y) that are applied in TABULA are converted into percentage savings, in order to allow for the consideration of specific household contexts being used to estimate the emissions. With the emission savings estimated through the percentage reduction in heating fuel use. The calculations for insulation retrofit used in this case study produce a relatively conservative estimate of the potential emission reductions, owing to the possibility of replacing insulation not being considered. In total it was estimated that approximately 1,000 tCO₂/yr could be saved.

Solar Panel Installation

If improving a household's insulation enhances its energy efficiency, the decarbonisation of energy supply is an alternative approach to reducing emissions. Within the project context, the installation of solar panels on household roofs was explored. This was built upon estimates conducted within the city's Local Area Energy Plan (LAEP) dataset (shared by Belfast City Council) which provides a detailed list of dwellings which are suitable for installation, owing to each household's roof area and orientation, with each building identifiable through its postcode.

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): A list of Linen Quarter houses with solar potential was produced by cross-referencing the postcodes of the Linen Quarter project area with those in the LAEP data. The LAEP dataset includes the maximum suitable roof area per household. This is used to estimate the number of solar panels which can be installed (assuming panels are 2m²).

Establish calculations (5): Assuming the energy efficiency of the panels are 19.5% (the UK average) and they produce 300 watts of power with an average amount of sunshine being 3.56 hours a day in Belfast, the daily and annual energy output was estimated. To estimate the carbon emission savings, the emission factor for grid electricity in Northern Ireland was applied to the total energy produced by the solar panels across the Linen Quarter.

Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7): Roughly 700 households have been assessed to be suitable for solar installation, representing an estimated 150 tCO₂/yr of emission savings

Cycling Emission Impact Calculator

Identify data (2), set assumptions (3) and identify emissions factors (4): To estimate the number of cyclists in the Linen Quarter, the TSNi's calculation of national levels of recent cycling was applied to the Linen Quarter's population statistics collected for the mobility emissions baseline – again following the same principle of the TSNi survey providing individual behaviours which are applied to the demographic reality of the Linen Quarter. This gave an estimation of 2,202 people in the Linen Quarter having cycled in the past 12 months.

Establish calculations (5): To estimate the climatic conditions which people would cycle within, data concerning Belfast's annual rainfall (days on which it rains and how much), temperatures and sunrise/sunset times (to estimate cycling in day light or at night) were collected. This provides the basis for accounting for the influence of weather. For instance, if people commute to work by bike and only on dry days, in the summer months, during day light hours and when the sun is shining, they will cycle for, at maximum, 118 days a year. Whereas, if they cycle in all weather, light and temperature conditions, which equates to 232 days a year. On top of the climate conditions, is the 'commitment' of a cyclist – how often will they cycle when the weather is right. The tool offers a variable associated with this commitment to cycling with options from occasional cyclist ('I'll dust the bike off every now and then' 25% of the time) to committed cyclists (who will cycle 100% of the time).

Conduct calculations (6) and aggregate results (7): Cycling preferences for an individual is then converted into an emissions saving. This is then scaled to either the data zone level or to the whole Linen Quarter area. The saving on an area basis can be further changed by factors relating to (A) assumption of current propensity to cycle and (B) TSNI-derived 'influences' on propensity to cycle more (e.g. 1% of people would cycle if there were cleaner cycle paths; 37% would cycle more if there were more cycle paths). This includes the potential to estimate the indirect impacts of urban greening on active travel, with 20% TSNI of respondents stating that they would cycle more if there were 'more pleasant cycling routes (e.g. greenways, by the river)'. To assist users, a tool has been developed using Excel which enables users to quickly estimate the emission reductions of different cycling policy options or the broader impacts of an increase in cycling.

Lessons Learned

The tool detailed here serves to provide emission estimates at scales not typically interrogated by city authorities – namely that of urban regeneration projects at the neighbourhood or district level. The research conducted within the Belfast regeneration context has informed the development of an approach which can be implemented across different locations. Although the data sources and the content may be different to those used here, the calculations detailed above can be used within different scenarios where a city authority is seeking to attain a degree of understanding of the carbon emission impacts regeneration efforts.

Therefore, whilst the data used here and the associated calculations present limitations in accuracy, they do provide estimates of impact from different interventions. Leveraging the unique synergies afforded by UP2030 which allowed for an academic institution to closely collaborate with a city council, a tool could be developed to match the specificities of a location.

The calculations conducted here have served to reveal useful insights into not only the emission make-up of the project area, but also the diversity in potential application to reduce the emissions. Firstly, there is a strong correlation between areas which feature older housing stock with higher emissions. This may not be of huge surprise, but it serves to demonstrate that even within a relatively small area – one which is less than a square mile in size – there is diversity in context.

Figure 93: This map demonstrates the clustering of different levels of household emissions. This map combines data zones and loosely, but not exactly, maps onto the different communities within the Linen Quarter – with the original Linen Quarter BID mapped in black

This is further reinforced by the distribution of different emissions reducing actions. Whilst improved insulation potentially more impactful than solar panel installation, this is not uniformly spread across the whole area (and success will be dependent on quality of installation and subsequent user behaviour). There are areas within the Linen Quarter where solar panels may reduce emissions more than further insulation (Figure 94), owing to the types of building, low percentages of households to retrofit (due to the prevalence of prior insulation) and a high percentage of households which are suitable for solar panels, due to their orientation to the sun and roof type.

Figure 94: Estimated carbon emission reductions associated with solar installations presented as a proportion of possible reductions through insulation interventions. If the data zone is blue, this means that installing solar panels may reduce more carbon emissions compared to those where insulation would be more impactful (green)

Another important insight from the case study process is the importance of making the tool ‘future-proof’. This is bound in the idea that to calculate the carbon footprint of a neighbourhood or district is to take a snapshot of it in a certain period of time. Cities are perpetually developing, this is especially true for the urban regeneration context within which every UP2030 project falls. Therefore, the ability for a tool such as this one to be updated to best mirror the reality of the time of implementation is of crucial importance.

Conclusion

This project has supported Belfast City Council by providing a means of estimating the carbon emission impacts of three of their approaches to urban regeneration: household retrofit, active travel and urban greening. This prototype was developed through direct collaboration with the Council, and it was their goals and objectives, coupled with the limitations of their capacities which steered the development of the tool described here. The approach applied here revealed not only the estimated emission reductions of the proposed regeneration measures but also demonstrated variations of impact between different data zones within the Linen Quarter, thereby offering the Council a more granular understanding of carbon emissions than what they previously had access to.

13 GGGI

The Global Green Growth Institute (GGGI) is a treaty-based international, inter-governmental organization dedicated to supporting and promoting green growth and climate action in its member countries. GGGI's operating model maximizes the potential to translate innovative, state-of-the-art approaches into implantable solutions locally, regionally, and nationally. GGGI's country offices are directly embedded in countries' ministries and act as advisors and strategic national and subnational development partners. This facilitates access to government agencies for technical assistance, capacity building, data collection, and policy planning, ultimately enhancing the project's impact, as results will inform ongoing policy implementation projects in the countries and regions where GGGI is present.

Partner Website: <https://gggi.org/>

13.1 UGEM Tool

The Green Economy Model (GEM) has been designed explicitly to analyse green economy and low carbon development scenarios at the national level. GEM is built using the System Dynamics (SD) methodology, serving primarily as a knowledge integrator. The Urban GEM (UGEM), a downscaled version of the GEM, is designed to facilitate policy planning in the medium to long term across key economic sectors and subsectors - energy, industry, waste management, and buildings – which was under development in UP2030.

13.1.1 Software Requirements

UGEM is partially open access. The model source code and documentation are available on an open-access basis (provided on request), but operating and modifying the model requires the Vensim system-dynamics software, which is subject to its own licensing conditions.

Pricing depends on the specific needs and type of buyer. Different pricing options are available for non-academic/academic users and professionals. Prices range between \$478-\$1195 but the license has no expiration. You may pay an annual maintenance at around \$100 to update to the latest software, when released. More info here: <https://vensim.com/purchase/>.

Specifically, as minimum requirement to use all the functionalities of Vensim required to run UGEM, (i) the Professional version of Vensim, (ii) with academic license is required, and costs \$478.

13.1.2 Data Requirements

UGEM uses Microsoft Excel for data processing and integrates with Vensim software for Causal Loop Diagrams (CLDs) and Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA). It is built using the System Dynamics (SD) methodology, a form of computer simulation modelling. Key datasets required (in Excel format):

- GDP, income and employment: national/regional statistics
- Population (as detailed as possible): Census
- Housing (no of dwellings, house price, rent, cost of construction/m², etc.): National Statistics or Stakeholders
- Transport (no of vehicles, public transport structure as no of buses/metro/tram, etc.): National/regional statistics
- Energy (consumption and cost of coal/petroleum/natural gas/electricity/biofuel): National/regional statistics/ or Utility Companies for information of consumption by type of customer

- GHG emissions (CO₂, CH₄, PM, etc.): National/regional statistics
- Land cover and land use (m² or hectares): spatial maps, or municipal statistics
- Previous year data at 10-year span to calibrate the model (less if not available)
- Previous year data at 10-year span to calibrate the model (less if not available)

13.1.3 Expertise Requirements

Using Vensim and UGEM has a learning curve. Users need to be familiar with different components of the model and with SD modelling. Expertise required in urban planning and economics, in order to understand macroeconomic effects and the interrelation of different subsystems (economy, transportation, housing etc.) for efficient use of the model.

13.1.4 Potential Barriers to Use

As the tool is resource intensive (HR, technical capacities, software requirements) cities may not be comfortable or be able to implement the tool without the support from GGGI/ CERTH. Further barrier is the costs of the Vensim Professional license.

Another barrier may be the limited understanding at the outset what the tool could do, what purpose it serves. Its potential results and limitations.

Guidance materials and tutorials on Vensim are available online, primarily in English: https://vensim.com/documentation/users_guide.html.

13.1.5 Tool Use Context

UGEM is built using the SD methodology, serving primarily as a knowledge integrator. SD is a form of computer simulation modelling designed to facilitate policy planning in the medium to long term across key economic sectors and subsectors in the urban downscaled model (energy, industry, waste management, NBS and buildings) not to make precise predictions of the future, or to optimize performance; rather, these models are used to inform policy formulation, forecasting policy outcomes and leading to the creation of a robust and well-balanced strategy. The UGEM is useful to understand the complex interactions between different sectors and their impact on the environment and identify opportunities for urban transitions while improving resource efficiency. More specifically:

- Cross-Sectoral Planning: facilitates medium to long-term planning across key economic sectors (energy, industry, waste, housing), avoiding the siloed planning issue.
- Customizability: tailored to the specific needs and capacities of countries and cities, providing flexibility that surpasses competing models.
- Transparent CBA: offers a high-level analysis of emission pathways, supporting informed policy formulation and raising climate ambition across all emitting sectors
- The tool can be used at a city or neighbourhood level, depending on the granularity of data.

13.1.6 Tool Limitations

Heavy reliance on data, thus accuracy and completeness of data is key. Most are open source at national level. Municipalities might need to purchase city-level data from National Services (reasonable prices, usually below 1,000 euros for all).

13.1.7 City Journey

UGEM supports policy impact evaluation the best with modelling and scenario analysis at the Initial “Evaluate strategies and select alternatives” stages as per the UP2030 planning cycle. But another potential application is evaluation at the end of the cycle in the “Evaluate” phase, to provide feedback on the implemented measures and policies.

13.1.8 Step-by-Step Guide

Figure 95: UGEM process flow diagram

13.1.9 Case Study

The work in UP2030 involved the downscaling to the urban level of the GEM (Bassi, 2015), which was first developed to analyse green economy and low-carbon development scenarios at national level. The general aim was to provide a tool for urban planning (tailor-made to the needs of every Municipality) so that decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios to better allocate their budget and have tangible evidence for claiming funds from various actors (government, European Investment Bank, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, Cohesion fund, etc.). With the support of GGGI, CERTH developed a new Housing module for the UGEM of designed to evaluate housing policy scenarios at the urban level and for testing and implementation in Thessaloniki.

Thus, within UP2030, 1) the GEM was downscaled to an urban level, and 2) a housing module was developed to simulate two scenarios for the city of Thessaloniki based on the city's Action Plan for the 2030 Agenda, namely (1) the impact of social housing for vulnerable city districts, and (2) the indirect impact of energy poverty policies that include energy-efficient measures on urban residencies and consequently carbon footprint mitigation.

Based on the GEM, the downscaled UGEM simulates the dynamics of various systems at the urban level. It covers main urban systems - buildings, transport, local energy supply and related GHG emissions and air pollutants, waste and wastewater generation and management, local economic activity and employment - including a new housing module. With UGEM, decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios and generate evidence for budget allocation. Urban GEM is built based on the original GEM developed at national level, using the SD methodology. A new Housing subsystem from MacAskill et al. (2021) that simulates construction-supply-demand phases for social/public housing policies was adjusted and added to UGEM as a separate module by CERTH.

Additionally, a complementary housing price model was estimated for the subsystem to accurately forecast the impact of social house construction in the study area. On top of that, energy demand and consumption were disaggregated across the residential, commercial, industrial and transport sector, to address the impacts of policy changes such as energy efficiency measures in housing, investments in power generation, and related public investment requirements as well as implications for employment creation. The tool can run scenario simulations up to 2050. In Thessaloniki, the scenarios are based on Thessaloniki's Action Plan for the 2030 Agenda and have an initial simulation span up to 2035. However, as at the writing of this report the housing module's implementation is not yet final: the module is developed with preliminary testing and early simulations done. Implementation is expected to take place in Thessaloniki by the end of December. Final results will be communicated to the mayor, as per GGGI's plans, before the end of the project.

14 Conclusion

This document has served to demonstrate the range of tools related to digital planning and design for climate neutral cities within UP2030, by providing an overview of the technical and use requirements, as well as how to use each tool and a case study highlighting each tool's use. In total, 16 tools from 11 providers have been detailed. Each tool provider listed above has been a partner within the UP2030 project and this document has been curated around a collaborative approach between the tool providers affiliated with Task 3.3.

Overall, the tools included in this deliverable each serve to enhance decision-making capabilities within city authorities. However, this is conducted along different lines. Whilst some support improving the development and implementation of mitigation approaches towards combatting climate change, others focus on adaptation and enhancing the resilience of cities when faced with its effects. Other tools revolve around engagement and support the integration of diverse stakeholders in the decision-making process, be this through engaging the community or better aligning those who work within the city. Another theme which has emerged is the pursuit of improving data use when making climate neutrality decisions and, to conclude, a range of tools supporting the design of neutrality approaches.

The tools presented here embody a multiplicity of approaches to support and enable better climate neutrality actions from a diverse range of providers who each possess a deep repository of expertise which has been leveraged to produce these novel, leading-edge tools and approaches. Depending upon the context for their use, each of these tools is in good stead to enhance any city which desires to implement them. This guide has been created to support the process of selecting the right tools for such cities.

References

- Bassi, A. (2015). Moving Towards Integrated Policy Formulation and Evaluation: The Green Economy Model. *Environmental and Climate Technologies*, 16. <https://doi.org/10.1515/rtuct-2015-0009>
- B-WaterSmart Training: <https://b-watersmart.eu/training-material-for-three-tools/>
- Cardoso, M.A., Brito, R.S., Pereira, C., Gonzalez, A., Stevens J., Telhado, M.J. (2020a). RAF resilience assessment framework – a tool to support cities’ action planning. Special issue Integrated assessment of climate change impacts and urban resilience: from climate and hydrological hazards to risk analysis and measures. *Sustainability* 2020, 12:2349. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12062349>
- Cardoso, M.A., Telhado, M.J., Almeida, M.C., Brito, R.S., Pereira, C., Barreiro, J., Morais, M. (2020b). Following a step-by-step development of a Resilience Action Plan. Special issue "Urban resilience in a context of climate change". *Sustainability* 2020, 12(21), 9017. 22 pp., <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219017>.
- Cardoso, M. A., Brito, R.S., Pereira, C., Gabàs, A., González Gómez, A., Goodey, P., Lopes, R., Martínez, M., Russo, B., Telhado, M.J., Stevens, J., Velasco, M. (2020c). Resilience Action Plans of the RESCCUE cities. RESCCUE project deliverable D6.2. 285 pp. <https://toolkit.resccue.eu/>.
- Gouldson, A., Sudmant, A., Boyd, J., Williamson, R., Barry, J., and Slevin, A. (2020) A Net-Zero Carbon Roadmap for Belfast, Belfast Climate Commission/ Place-Based Climate Action Network
- MacAskill, S., Mostafa, S., Stewart, R.A., Sahin, O. and Suprun, E., 2021. Offsite construction supply chain strategies for matching affordable rental housing demand: A system dynamics approach. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 73, p.103093.
- Raven, J., Leone, M. F., Mills, G., Katschner, L., Gaborit, P., Georgescu, M., ... & Stone, B. (2018). Urban planning and urban design. In *Climate Change and Cities (ARC 3-2)*. Second Assessment Report of the Urban Climate Change Research Network (pp. 139-172). Cambridge University Press.
- Raven, J., Leone, M. F., & Nocerino, G. (2025). The Urban Design Climate Workshop: Integrating Mitigation and Adaptation Strategies to Confront Urban Climate Change. In *Urban Climate and Urban Design* (pp. 167-179). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore
- Rocco, R., Gonçalves, J., & Lopez, H. (2024). The TU Delft Strategic Planning Cycle. TU Delft OPEN Publishing.